

ISTANBUL MEDENIYET UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF GRADUATE STUDIES
DEPARTMENT OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION
ENGLISH LANGUAGE EDUCATION

**Communicative Orientation of EFL Instruction in Primary
Classrooms**

Master's Thesis

Sena Sayıcı

May 2023

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THESIS JURY APPROVAL

This MA thesis titled “Communicative Orientation of EFL Instruction in Primary Classrooms” written by Sena Sayıcı at the Department of Foreign Language Education was accepted by our jury.

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STATEMENTS

Style and Reference Manual Statement

Having reviewed this thesis written under my supervision, I confirm that it has been written in accordance with APA (6th Edition) Manual of Style and used its [footnote/in text] reference format consistently throughout the entire text.

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Declaration of Originality

I hereby declare that all information in this dissertation has been obtained and presented in accordance with academic rules and ethical conduct. I also declare that, as required by these rules and conducts, I have fully cited and referenced all material and results that are not original to this work.

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Sena SAYICI

GENİŞ ÖZET

İlkokul Sınıflarında Yabancı Dil Olarak İngilizce Öğretiminin İletişimsel Yönelimi

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Geçmişten günümüze dil öğretiminde farklı yaklaşım ve metotlar kullanılmıştır. 1970'li yılların sonundan itibaren mevcut yaklaşımlar dil öğrenenlerin ihtiyaçlarını karşılayamamış ve eğitim felsefesindeki ve teknolojilerindeki gelişmeler sonucunda, iletişimsel yeterliği odak noktası olarak kabul eden İletişimsel Dil Öğretim (İDÖ) metodu ortaya çıkmıştır. Bu yaklaşım genel olarak iletişimsel yeterliliği dil öğretiminin hedefi haline getiren, dilin akıcılığının yanı sıra doğruluğuna da vurgu yapan, bunu yaparken dört temel dil becerisini sürecin en başından beri geliştirmeye çalışan ve bu hedefler doğrultusunda bilgi boşluğu, jigsaw, görev tamamlama, fikir paylaşımı, bilgi aktarımı ve akıl yürütme gibi iletişimsel aktivitelerden ve öğrencileri gerçek hayattaki dile maruz bırakmak için otantik materyallerden yararlanan bir yaklaşımdır. Aynı zamanda, öğretmenler daha çok rehber ve kolaylaştırıcı rolündeyken, öğrencilerden aktif katılımcı olmaları beklenmektedir. Ayrıca, öğrencilerin anlam müzakerelerinde bulunabilmeleri için ikili ve grup çalışmaları son derece önemlidir. Bu yaklaşım, ortaya çıktığından beri dünyanın birçok ülkesinin eğitim bakanlıkları tarafından da benimsenmiştir. Aynı durum Türkiye için de geçerlidir ve 1997'de İngilizce

eđitim ve đretim mfredatlarına giren bu yaklařım, daha sonra 2006 yılından itibaren ilkokullarda uygulanmaya bařlanmış, 2013 ve 2018 yıllarında yenilenen mfredatlarda da yerini korumuřtur. Tm bu mfredatlarda dil eđitiminin amacı đrencilerin iletiřimsel becerilerini geliřtirmek olarak belirtilmiřtir. Dnyanın birok yerinde ve zellikle İngilizcenin yabancı dil olarak đretildiđi cođrafyalarda yapılan alıřmalar gstermektedir ki teorik olarak sađlam olan ve uzmanlarca tavsiye edilen İletišimsel Dil đretim yaklařımı birok farklı nedenden tr tam olarak uygulanamamaktadır. Bunlar đretmenlerden, đrencilerden, eđitim sisteminden ya da İletišimsel Yaklařımın kendisinden kaynaklanan nedenler olabilir. Alan yazında yer alan arařtırmalara gre đretmenlerin İngilizce konuřma becerisinde yetkin olmamaları, İD eđitimlerinin yetersizliđi ve bu yaklařımı deneyimleyebilecekleri imkanların azlıđı, đrencilerin İngilizce seviyelerinin ve yabancı dil đrenme motivasyonlarının dřk olması, kalabalık sınıflar, devlet desteđinin kısıtlılıđı, sınava dayalı lme deđerlendirme sistemi ve iletiřimsel yeterliliđi len deđerlendirme aralarının eksikliđi gibi sebepler iletişime dayalı İngilizce đretiminin nndeki bařlıca engellerdir. Aynı řekilde, Trkiye’de yapılan alıřmalar da iletişime dayalı dil đretiminin yeterince uygulanmadıđını, derslerin đretmen merkezli olduđunu ve geleneksel yntemlere dayandıđını, đrencilerin dili hala ezber, eviri ve dilbilgisi odaklı đrendiklerini ve sınıf ortamından dıřarı ıktıklarında kendilerini hedef dilde ifade etmede yetersiz kaldıklarını gstermektedir. Ayrıca, mfredatın ve materyallerin bu yeni yaklařıma uygun olarak dzenlenmesine ve đretmenlere konuyla ilgili hizmet ii eđitim verilmesine karřın đrencilerden beklenen bařarı dzeyi sađlanamamıř ve yaklařımın đretmenler tarafından kullanılmadıđı ortaya ıkmıřtır. Bu durumda resmi olarak kabul edilen iletiřimsel bir mfredat, onun bařarılı ve dzgn bir řekilde uygulanmasını garanti etmemektedir ve uygulama ođunlukla đretmenlere bađlıdır. rneđin, aynı metodu uyguladıđını syleyen

öğretmenler tamamen farklı uygulamalar yaparken, farklı yöntemler kullandıklarını söyleyenler de özünde aynı metot ile öğretim yapabilmektedir.

Sonuç olarak, öğretmenlerin kendi uygulamalarıyla ilgili algılarının yanı sıra gerçekte yabancı dil sınıflarında neler uygulandığını anlamak ve ortaya koymak gerekmektedir. Böylece daha gerçekçi yorum ve sonuçlara ulaşmak mümkün olacaktır. Bu bağlamda, bu çalışma ilkokul sınıflarındaki yabancı dil öğretmenlerinin çocuklara yabancı dil öğretirken İletişimsel Dil Öğretim Yöntemini ne derece uyguladıklarını incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Aynı zamanda, öğretmenlerin fiili uygulamaları ile algılarının karşılaştırılarak aralarındaki farklılıkların ortaya çıkarılması hedeflenmektedir. Son olarak, yabancı dil öğretiminde iletişimsel yöntemin kullanımı açısından herhangi bir fark olup olmadığını tespit etmek üzere devlet okulu ve özel okul bağlamlarının karşılaştırılması da hedefler arasında yer almaktadır.

Bu çalışmada ilköğretim seviyesinde iletişimsel yöntemin kullanımı açısından yabancı dil olarak İngilizce eğitiminin gerçek durumunun araştırılması amaçlanmaktadır. Yani kendiliğinden meydana gelen bir olay veya olgunun olduğu gibi betimlemesi ve aktarılması söz konusudur. Bu nedenle bu çalışma nitel desende tasarlanmış betimsel bir araştırmadır. Türkiye'deki tüm ilkokul yabancı dil sınıflarını gözlemleyerek derinlemesine incelemek mümkün değildir. Bu yüzden, bu çalışma bir ya da birkaç örneğin derinlemesine incelenmesine olanak sağlayan durum çalışması olarak düzenlenmiştir. Bu çalışmada devlet ve özel ilkokulları olarak iki farklı bağlam incelendiği için, çalışmayı çoklu vaka çalışması olarak adlandırmak da mümkündür. Çalışmanın katılımcıları bir amaçlı örnekleme çeşidi olan tipik durum örnekleme ile seçilmiştir. Yani, katılımcı öğretmenler standart bir özel okul ve devlet okulunda çalışan standart/tipik öğretmenlerdir. Çalışma, on iki hafta süreyle sınırlandırılmıştır.

Kısacası, bu çalışma özel ilkokul ve devlet ilkokulu olarak iki farklı okul bağlamında İngilizceyi yabancı dil olarak öğreten öğretmenlerle yürütülmüştür. Çalışmaya başlamadan önce öğretmenler çalışmaya gönüllü katıldıklarını ifade eden onam formunu imzalamışlardır. Çalışmanın verileri ders gözlemleri, Spada ve Fröhlich tarafından 1995 yılında geliştirilen COLT (*Communicative Orientation of Language Teaching*) gözlem formunun A bölümü, yine gözlem sırasında alınan alan notları ve yarı yapılandırılmış görüşme formu ile toplanmıştır. Çalışmanın amaçları doğrultusunda öğretmenlerin her biri art arda on iki hafta süreyle gözlemlenmiştir. Devlet okulundaki öğretmenin bir tane 2. sınıf şubesi (12 hafta) ve özel okuldaki öğretmenin iki tane 2. sınıf şubesi (6'şar hafta) öğretmenlerin ve araştırmacıların uygunluğuna göre haftada bir ders saati olmak kaydıyla gözlemlenmiştir. Gözlemler araştırmacının sınıfın arkasında oturarak hiçbir şeye müdahalede bulunmadığı katılımsız gözlemlerdir. Buna ek olarak, öğretmenlerle belirlenen yer ve zamanda ayrı ayrı görüşmeler yapılmıştır. Verilerin analizi için COLT A gözlem formundaki her bir başlık için ayrılan başlama ve bitiş zamanlarına bakılarak süreler hesaplanmıştır. Sonrasında, her bir başlığın yüzdeliği toplam gözlem süresine oranla hesaplanmıştır. Hesaplamalar yapılırken sadece birincil kodlamalar göz önüne alınmıştır. Bazı etkinliklerin yapısı gereği birden fazla birincil kodlama varsa, onlar tek bir kodlama olarak birleştirilmiş ve yeni bir başlık oluşturulmuştur. Görüşme verileri analizi betimsel analiz ile incelenmiştir ve bulgular öğretmenlerin konuyla ilgili ifade ettikleri görüşlerini karşılaştırabilmek için benzerlik ve farklılıkları dikkate alarak bütüncül olarak rapor edilmiştir.

Bu çalışmanın sonuçları katılımcı organizasyonu, derslerin içeriği ve sık kullanılan etkinlikler, öğrencilerin meşgul oldukları dil becerisi (modalite) ve derslerde kullanılan materyaller olarak birkaç farklı başlık altında toplanabilir. İlk olarak, sınıf içi iletişim her iki okulda da büyük ölçüde öğretmen ile öğrenci

veya tüm sınıf arasında gerçekleşmiştir, yani dersler büyük ölçüde öğretmen odaklıdır. Aynı şekilde, her iki okulda da bireysel aktiviteler, ikili çalışma ve grup çalışmalarından çok daha fazla zaman almıştır. Fakat, özel okuldaki öğrenciler devlet okulundaki öğrencilere kıyasla daha fazla birbirleriyle iletişim kurmuşlardır ve derslerde daha fazla aktif oldukları gözlemlenmiştir. Bu nedenle, devlet okulundaki derslerin daha geleneksel ve daha öğretmen merkezli olduğu söylenebilir. Her iki okulda da derslerin içeriğini, materyalleri ve etkileşim türlerini öğretmenler belirlemiş, bu konularda öğrencilerin bir söz hakkı olmamıştır. Kısacası, bu iki okul bağlamında öğretmen ve öğrenci rolleri geleneksel ve öğrencilerin daha aktif olduğu, birbirleriyle daha çok iletişim halinde oldukları ve öğretmenlerinse daha çok kolaylaştırıcı rolünde olduğu İletişimsel Dil Öğretimi ile uyuşmamaktadır. Teoride tavsiye edilen öğrenci ve öğretmen rollerinin tersine, yakın dönemdeki diğer çalışmalar da yabancı dil derslerinin öğretmen odaklı olduğunu göstermektedir.

İkinci olarak, derslerin içeriğinin hem özel okulda hem de devlet okulunda yapı/kelime odaklı olduğu, fakat iletişimsel yeterliğin diğer öğeleri olan sosyodilbilimsel yeterlik ve söylem yeterliğini içermediği, dilsel işlevlerin ise çok az yer aldığı görülmüştür. Oysa, iletişime dayalı yabancı dil öğretiminde iletişimsel yeterlik bütüncül olarak ele alınmalıdır. Bunların yanı sıra hem devlet okulu hem özel okul derslerinde sık kullanılan etkinlikler vardır. Örneğin, çoğu zaman öğretmen tarafından yönetilse de oyunların kullanımı özel okulda çok sıkken, devlet okulunda nadirdir. Özel okul öğretmeni sadece kitaba bağlı kalmayıp dersleri diğer etkinliklerle zenginleştirmek isterken, devlet okulundaki öğretmen daha fazla yapı çalışması içerdiğinden fazladan iki kitap kullanmıştır. İki öğretmen de tekrarlama yönteminden faydalansa da bu oran devlet okulunda daha fazladır. Ayrıca, devlet okulu öğretmeni açık dil bilgisi öğretiminden, yönerge ve kelimeleri açıklarken çeviriden faydalanmıştır. Öte yandan, özel okul

öğretmeni örtük gramer öğretiminden yana olduğu için bu etkinlikler özel okulda gözlemlenmemiştir. Bunlara ek olarak, ödev ve ödev kontrolü, tahta kullanımı, soru-cevap etkinlikleri gibi geleneksel yöntemler devlet okulunda yaygın kullanılmıştır. Diğer yandan, devlet okulu öğretmeni iletişimsel aktiviteleri az kullanmasına gerekçe olarak ölçme-değerlendirme sistemi, yoğun müfredat, İngilizce derslerine ayrılan sürenin yetersizliği, kendini hedef dilde yeterli bulmaması gibi engellerden bahsetmiştir. Literatüre bakıldığında da nerdeyse aynı faktörlerin iletişimsel aktivitelerin uygulanmasını engellendiği görülmektedir.

Üçüncü olarak, öğrencilerin derste kullandıkları dil becerilerine bakıldığında, her iki okulda da en fazla dinleme yaptıkları görülmüştür. Sınıflar öğretmen odaklı olduğu için bu da öğrencilerin çoğunlukla öğretmenlerini ya da işitsel bir materyali dinlediklerini göstermiştir. Aynı şekilde, devlet okulu öğretmenin daha fazla ana dil kullanması ve özel okuldaki yabancı dil ders saatlerinin daha fazla olması sonucu, özel okul öğrencilerinin yabancı dilde daha fazla anlamlı girdiye maruz kaldığı tespit edilmiştir. Bunlarla beraber, dinleme ve konuşmanın aynı anda kullanılmasını gerektiren etkinlikler her iki okulda da yaygındır. Ayrıca, dinleme ve duyduğunu anlama üzerine yapılan diğer etkinlikler ya da sadece diğer etkinlikler (toplam fiziksel tepki, çizip boyama, sayma, el çırpma, kesme-yapıştırma vb.) özel okulda biraz daha sıklıkla olmakla beraber her iki okulda da kullanılmıştır. Diğer yandan, okuma etkinlikleri her iki okulda da az kullanılırken, devlet okulundaki öğrenciler dikkate değer bir zamanlarını yazma etkinlikleri ile geçirmişlerdir. Fakat özel okulda böyle bir durum söz konusu değildir.

Bu çalışma ayrıca derslerde kullanılan materyallerin türlerine ve kaynaklarına da bakmıştır. İlk olarak, her iki okulda da en çok görselli metinler yani görseller ile

desteklenen ders kitapları ya da bilgi kartları hayli kullanılmıştır. Alan yazındaki çalışmalar da çocuklara İngilizce öğretiminde resimlerin kullanılmasının iletişime dayalı dil öğretimi ile bağdaştığını göstermektedir. Ayrıca, her iki okulda da hiçbir materyal kullanılmadan geçen süre bir hayli fazladır. Bu süre zarfında genellikle disiplin sorunları ile ilgilenilmiş ya da yönergeleri açıklamak, öğrencileri derse hazırlamak gibi prosedürle ilgili etkinliklerin yanı sıra toplam fiziksel tepki ve oyun aktiviteleri yapılmıştır. Materyallerin kaynaklarına bakıldığında her iki okulda da en çok ana dili olmayanlara dil öğretmek üzere tasarlanan materyaller kullanılmıştır. Otantik (ana dili konuşuru olanlar için hazırlanmış) ya da öğrenciler tarafından hazırlanan materyallere ise çok nadiren yer verilmiştir. Yabancı dil sınıflarında otantik, uyarlanmış ya da dil öğretme amaçlı üretilen materyaller olmak üzere çeşitli materyaller kullanıldığı bilinmektedir.

Tüm bu başlıklar dikkate alındığında ne devlet okulu öğretmeni ne de özel okul öğretmeni geleneksel yöntemi körü körüne takip etmemektedirler ve farklı seviyelerde de olsa derslerini daha anlam odaklı ve çocukların ilgisini çekecek şekilde düzenlemeye çalışmaktadırlar. Yani, her iki sınıf da öğretmen merkezli olsa da daha sıklıkla yer verilen anlam odaklı etkinlikler nedeni ile özel okul öğretmenin dersleri daha iletişimseldir. Aynı zamanda, bu sınıftaki öğrenciler daha aktiftir. Diğer yandan, devlet okulundaki öğretmen derslerinde anlam odaklı aktiviteler ile geleneksel dil öğretim metotlarını birleştirmiştir. Yani özel okul öğretmeni anlamlandırma odaklı öğretmenler grubuna yakınken, devlet okulundaki öğretmen daha derlemeci/eklektiktir ve bu da özel okuldaki derslerin iletişimsel dil öğretimine odaklı olan son müfredata daha uygun olduğunu göstermektedir. Nihai olarak, yaklaşımların etkili bir şekilde uygulanmasında öğretmenlerin birincil rolü hala elinde tuttuğu sonucuna varmak mümkündür.

Son olarak, çalışmadan elde edilen sonuçlar ışığında politika yapıcılar, alanda görev yapan öğretmenler ve konuyla ilgilenen araştırmacılar için bazı önerilerde bulunulmuştur. Eğitim fakültelerindeki İngilizce Öğretmenliği müfredatlarına *Çocuklara Yabancı Dil Öğretimi* dersi 2006 yılından sonra eklenmiştir, ancak o tarihten önce mezun olan öğretmenler hali hazırda görev yapmaya devam etmektedir. Bu hususta özellikle bu tarihten önce mezun olan öğretmenlerin seminer, internet tabanlı seminer ya da atölyeler aracılığı ile bu konularda eğitilmelerini sağlamak üzere çalışmalar yapılmalıdır. Öğretmenlerin 1997 müfredat değişikliğinden sonra İletişimsel Dil Öğretim yöntemi ile ilgili bilgilendirildikleri bilinmektedir. Ancak, eğitim sürekli devam eden bir süreçtir. Öğretmenlerin bu konu hakkında düzenli aralıklarla toplanıp sadece teorik olarak değil kendi bağlamlarına uygun olarak bu metodu çocuklara nasıl uygulayacaklarına dair pratik ipuçları ile de desteklenmeleri tavsiye edilmiştir. Ayrıca, öğretmenlerin İletişimsel Dil Öğretim yönteminde hayli önemli olan ikili çalışmaları ve grup çalışmalarını sınıflarında yeterince kullanabilmeleri için sınıf mevcutlarının azaltılması ve haftalık ders programında İngilizce derslerinin arttırılmasına yönelik çalışmalar yapılmalıdır. Öğretmenlere ilk olarak eğitim öğretim yılı başlamadan önce müfredatlarını okuyup onlardan ne beklediğini öğrenmeleri tavsiye edilmiştir. Buna ek olarak, öğretmenlere çocuklara yabancı dil öğretimi ve İletişimsel Dil Öğretimi ile ilgili mesleki gelişim programlarını takip etmeleri tavsiye edilmiştir. Araştırmacılar için ise benzer çalışmaların daha fazla öğretmen ile farklı eğitim seviyelerinde yürütülmesi önerilebilir. Ayrıca iletişime dayalı yabancı dil öğretimini destekleyecek uygulamaları tespit edebilmek için deneysel çalışmalar da yapılabilir. İletişimsel yabancı dil eğitimindeki rollerini ve bakış açılarını ortaya çıkarmak için öğrencileri, ebeveynleri, yöneticileri ya da öğretmen eğitimcilerini de kapsayan daha geniş çaplı çalışmalar yapılabilir. Son olarak, hizmet öncesi öğretmenlerin çocuklara

iletişimsel dil öğretimine ne kadar hazır olduğunun araştırılması için çalışmalar yürütülebilir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Yabancı Dil Olarak İngilizce, İletişimsel Dil Öğretimi, İlkokul Sınıfları

ABSTRACT

The Communicative Language Teaching has been used in the world and in Turkey since the late 1970s. However, studies show that this approach is not fully implemented for various reasons in language classrooms, especially in contexts where English is taught as a foreign language. In this respect, this study aims to investigate the communicative orientation of language classrooms in Turkey by observing the real practices of two different primary school EFL teachers practicing in different settings: a private and a public school. Additionally, the study aims to demonstrate if there are any differences between these school contexts in terms of applying the principles of CLT and if there are any discrepancies between what the teachers believe and what they implement in reality. This qualitative study was designed as a case study in order to examine the teachers' practices in-depth. The data were collected through observation by using the COLT Observation Scheme (Part A) developed by Spada and Fröhlich (1995), field notes, and semi-structured interview forms. For the analysis of the observations, the amount of time allocated for each activity and episode of each lesson was determined, and the percentages of the categories in the observation form were calculated accordingly. Besides, the data obtained from the interviews were analyzed through descriptive analysis. The results showed that the private school teacher was more interpretation-oriented and tried to follow the principles

of the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) method more than the public school teacher. It was also revealed that the public school teacher was more eclectic and mixed traditional and meaning-oriented activities in her lessons.

Keywords: English as a Foreign Language, Communicative Language Teaching, Primary School Classrooms

DEDICATION

To my beloved family...

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

- ALM:** Audio-Lingual Method
- BC:** British Council
- CEFR:** Common European Framework References
- CLIL:** Content and Language Integrated Learning
- CLT:** Communicative Language Teaching
- COC:** Communicative-Oriented Curriculum
- COLT:** Communicative Orientation of Language Teaching
- EFL:** English as a Foreign Language
- ELT:** English Language Teaching
- ESL:** English as a Second Language
- EU:** European Union
- FL:** Foreign Language
- GTM:** Grammar-Translation Method
- INGED:** The English Language Teachers' Association in Turkey
- INSET:** In-Service English Language Teacher Training and Development Unit
- L1:** First Language
- L2:** Second Language
- MEB:** Milli Eğitim Bakanlığı (Ministry of National Education)
- MNE:** Ministry of National Education
- NATO:** The North Atlantic Treaty Organization
- OECD:** The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
- SLT:** Situational Language Teaching
- TEYLs:** Teaching English to Young Learners

TPR: Total Physical Response

USIA: United States Information Agency

ZPD: Zone of Proximal Development

1. INTRODUCTION

This study aims to investigate the communicative orientations of two EFL classrooms in a private and a public primary school in Istanbul based on lesson observations. It is also aimed to depict the teachers' perceptions regarding their use of CLT in their EFL instruction with the overserved young learner groups. Thus, it is intended to examine any potential similarities and distinctions between the teachers' implementations as well as the discrepancies between their beliefs and practices, if there are any. With these purposes in mind, this chapter introduces the outline of the current study. First, a comprehensive background regarding EFL teaching to young learners through the use of CLT is provided along with a brief literature review to portray the current picture in Turkey. Second, the problem addressed in the current study is clarified. Third, the purpose and the research questions are stated. Then, the significance of the study and its limitations are presented. Finally, definitions for the key terms are given respectively.

1.1 Background of the Study

Learning an additional language is quite common in most communities; therefore, the number of bilinguals and multi-linguals is higher than monolinguals in the world (Spada & Lightbown, 2013). Accordingly, effective, and efficient language teaching has remained one of the greatest concerns for decades. Hence, specifically the 20th century witnessed the emergence and adoption of several different approaches and methods in the hope of successful L2 teaching. The historical development of the language teaching methodology can be examined in four major periods: pre-twentieth-century trends, early and mid-twentieth-century approaches, more recent approaches, and post-methods era (Celce-Murcia et. al., 2014).

The pre-twentieth century period includes the approaches such as grammar-translation, the direct method, and the reform movement. In this era, the form and meaning of the languages were generally delivered by the teachers through aural-oral techniques. The second period covering the early and mid-twentieth century witnessed the popularity of the reading approach, the audiolingual approach, and the oral-situational approach. In

this period, reading comprehension, accurate pronunciation and drill activities, and practicing new structures and vocabulary around some specific situations were the focus of the language lessons respectively. Third, the second half of the twentieth century introduced more recent approaches to language teaching such as the cognitive approach (Chomsky, 1966) the affective-humanistic approach, the comprehension-based approach, and the communicative approach, which was first proposed by Hymes, Firth, and Halliday. Hence, other features of language learning such as rule acquisition in a systematic way instead of habit formation and rote learning, language learning as a social process in a secure and positive atmosphere and using language as a real communication tool were emphasized in this third era. Finally, in the post-methods era, language teachers have gained the freedom to design their own teaching methods by adopting a more eclectic approach in accordance with learner needs and contextual differences (Celce-Murcia et. al., 2014).

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) emerged in the late 1970s after Situational Language Teaching (SLT) became outdated due to its being inefficient to meet real communicative needs (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). This new method aimed to develop communicative competence and make intercultural and international communication a lot easier. Consequently, it gained wide popularity, and many countries across the world incorporated CLT into their national curriculum with the aim of improving EFL instruction. In the same vein, CLT was introduced to the Turkish curriculum as a methodology for teaching foreign languages (Kırkgöz, 2007b).

CLT has specific characteristics differentiating it from other approaches and methods. First, it aims at developing communicative competence which is made up of the following four components rather than the sole mastery of linguistic structures: discourse, sociolinguistic, strategic, and linguistic competence (Brown, 2000). Second, both accuracy and fluency are required and emphasized for successful communication (Littlewood, 1981). Third, the use of pair and group work is considered indispensable to give students the opportunity to negotiate meaning which is highly important in real-world communication (Larsen-Freeman, 2000). Additionally, CLT lessons are less teacher-centered and the teacher acts as a facilitator more than a director or authority (Harmer,

2007; Richards & Rodgers, 2014). Thus, students are expected to be more active and autonomous so that they can take the responsibility for their learning (Richards, 2006). Moreover, learners should work with authentic materials to get exposed to real language use in the classroom (Li, 1998; Wu, 2009). Finally, CLT favors activities and tasks enabling students to share information, negotiate for meaning and communicate in pairs or in groups. Accordingly, a CLT classroom utilizes such typical activities as jigsaw, task completion, opinion sharing, information transfer, reasoning gap tasks, and role plays (Richards & Rodgers, 2014).

Despite being a theoretically well-designed method, the implementation of CLT has turned into a great challenge mostly in EFL contexts like Bangladesh (Hamid & Honan, 2012; Hoque et. al., 2018; Islam, 2016), Kuwait (Al-Nouh, 2008), China (Hu, 2005b), Malaysia (Hardman & A-Rahman, 2014; Muhridza & Sataniphy, 2019), and Korea (Han, 2016; Kim, 2008). It is understood that this challenge mainly stems from teachers, students, educational systems, and the approach itself (Li, 1998). That is, teachers' lack of professional and methodological knowledge as well as their deficiency in L2, low learner motivation and L2 proficiency, difficulties in obtaining CLT resources, large class sizes, examination systems, and inefficient tools to measure students' communicative competence are referred as the common obstacles for effective use of CLT (Ansarey, 2012; Li & Baldauf, 2011; Sherwani & Kılıç, 2017). Additionally, teachers are not capable of implementing CLT effectively due to their confusion about the approach although they have positive perceptions of it (Rahman et. al., 2018). However, it is clear that L2 learners enjoy communicative activities a lot more than traditional ones (Shrestha, 2013; Yuliawati & Aprillia, 2019).

English has become the lingua franca in today's global world; therefore, learning and teaching this language has become a fundamental issue for all countries to be able to contact the rest of the world (Broughton et. al., 2002). In a similar vein, EFL instruction gained prominence in Turkey right after the establishment of the republic in 1923 in order to meet international needs and to catch up with technological developments (Kırkgöz, 2009). EFL instruction became even more significant for Turkey due to its key geopolitical location among Asia, Europe, and Africa as a member of international

organizations such as NATO, UN, and OECD (Demirel, 2021). Consequently, English has been the compulsory foreign language instructed at Turkish schools for decades.

Turkey has taken significant steps to improve EFL instruction and English language curriculum within mainstream education. In this sense, when the compulsory English instruction was increased to 8 from 5 years in accordance with the Ministry of National Education Development Project, the year 1997 became a milestone in terms of foreign language policies in Turkey (Küçüköğlü, 2013). It was this 1997 curriculum innovation which introduced the use of the Communicative Approach to the Turkish education system starting from the primary schools. Then, the EFL curriculum was revised and updated a couple of times still keeping CLT as the main methodology for language instruction. First, foreign language education became standardized in accordance with the requirements of EU membership (MEB, 2006). Then, the principles of CEFR were adopted and, the onset of EFL instruction was lowered to age 6 (2nd grade) along with the switch to the 4+4+4 education system (MEB, 2013) by following the global trend of lowering the age for foreign language instruction to achieve economic and political development (Baldauf et. al, 2011; Butler, 2015). Most recently in 2018, the EFL curriculum was updated once more to integrate values education into the program (MEB, 2018).

However, in time it was seen that the curriculum innovations were not implemented by the practitioners and the language programs could not reach their expected goals. For example, the 1997 curriculum did not have the intended effect on language classrooms due to several reasons. These obstacles were listed as textbooks not supporting communicative teaching methodology and the dense content of the curriculum. Similarly, the time allocated for each grade was not sufficient and the class size including many students made the implementation of the approach difficult. Another reason was that most of the schools lacked the required resources (Kırkgöz, 2007a). Similarly, factors such as the assessment type favoring the knowledge of English rather than use in addition to the crowded classes and insufficient resources had a negative effect on implementing CLT in Turkey (Mutlu & Kaşlıoğlu, 2015). In the same vein, it has been turned out that the language programs in Turkey are inefficient although the country tries to adopt new

methodologies by changing the language education programs and the materials as well as giving in-service education to teachers. Thus, the aims have not been achieved because there is no inspection monitoring if the sources are used effectively or not and if the teachers are compatible with the approach or not (Paker, 2012). Additionally, two main reasons might explain why the Turkish foreign language education system falls behind the expected success and is mainly based on traditional approaches such as GTM: the foreign language teacher education system and methodological faults and deficiencies of language policies resulting from it (Işık, 2008).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

As can be understood from the background provided above, EFL instruction is mainly based on CLT in the Turkish education system when 1997, 2006, 2013, and 2018 curricula are considered. Yet, it is impossible to make sure of the proper implementation of the method in actual EFL classes as highlighted by various studies in the related literature.

Although the official curriculum document has been warranting the adoption of a communicative approach in EFL instruction in Turkey since 1997, it is known that English lessons are mostly teacher-centered since really few teachers follow the principles of CLT in their classes (Coşkun, 2011; Dencki Akkaş & Çöker, 2016; Haznedar, 2010; Kırkgöz, 2007b; Kırkgöz, 2008a; Kırkgöz, 2008b). Moreover, the program seems to have failed to accomplish its objectives since students are unable to communicate efficiently when they graduate after studying the language in a mechanical way by memorizing vocabulary or structures rather than communicating for real purposes (Paker, 2012). Similarly, although the 2013 curriculum reflects the principles of CLT as well as being appropriate for young learners, it was revealed that its implementation was different from the expected (Yücel et. al., 2017). Consequently, it is understood that an official communicative language teaching curriculum does not guarantee a successful and proper implementation, which in fact depends on teachers (Yeni-Palabıyık & Daloğlu, 2016). That is, teachers stating that they use different methodologies might be utilizing the same activities in their lessons whereas the ones favoring a particular methodology might be doing distinctive things (Kumaravadivelu, 2003). Similarly, when asked about their perceptions, teachers seem to

favor a communicative language teaching methodology although they are actually teaching in a traditional way in reality (Coşkun, 2011; Gürsoy & Eken, 2018).

As a result, there occurs a need to understand what is going on in real EFL classes through observation rather than relying only on teachers' own perceptions or beliefs. This will render possibly more realistic and reliable interpretations of the implementations of teachers. In this regard, there is obviously a gap in the literature displaying the real CLT practices in actual language teaching and learning processes, especially in the Turkish context. Hence, it is supposed that the current study would contribute to the field by providing the results of the lesson observations and the perceptions of teachers. In brief, it is necessary to depict a thorough picture of primary EFL classrooms in the Turkish context with regard to the implementation of CLT and the recent English language curriculum which makes up the main problem addressed within the scope of this current study.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

Considering the problem stated above, this study aims to investigate to what extent EFL teachers implement CLT with young learners in primary schools. In addition, it is also aimed to compare teachers' actual practices and their perceptions to reveal any discrepancies between them. Last, public and private school contexts are compared to show any potential differences in terms of the use of CLT in EFL instruction.

1.4 Research Questions

Having all the concerns explained above, this study has three questions to be answered:

- 1) To what extent does EFL instruction have a communicative orientation in Turkish primary schools?
- 2) Are there any discrepancies between what the EFL teachers believe and what they do in reality?
- 3) Is there a difference between the public and private school contexts in terms of the implementation of CLT?

1.5 Significance of the Study

The current study is significant in many aspects. To begin with, as to the knowledge of the researchers, the studies investigating to what extent CLT is implemented in Turkey are very few when taking into consideration the period that CLT was adopted by the MNE (Coşkun, 2011; Denkci Akkaş & Çöker, 2016; Haznedar, 2010; Hunutlu, 2011; Kırkgöz, 2007b; Kırkgöz, 2008a; Kırkgöz, 2008b; Özşevik, 2010). Second, studies examining the use of CLT in primary classrooms are also quite limited to come to a conclusion (Kırkgöz, 2007b; Kırkgöz, 2008a; Kırkgöz, 2008b; Haznedar, 2010; Hunutlu, 2011; Özşevik, 2010). Third, most of those studies are not based on real classroom observations as in the current study. For instance, although the studies of Kırkgöz included observation to collect data, Haznedar, Hunutlu, and Özşevik used only questionnaires in their research. Fourth, the mentioned studies conducted to see the CLT practices in primary classes can now be accepted as outdated since, after those mentioned studies, many things have changed in the Turkish context. For example, in 2013, the educational system shifted to a system called 4+4+4 and, the starting age of English language teaching was lowered to 2nd grade while it was 4th grade before. Later, in 2018 the curriculum was changed again, and values education was added to the curriculum. After these curriculum innovations, no studies have been detected examining the recent status quo of primary ELT classrooms in Turkey, especially the 2nd grades. Thus, there is a gap in the literature showing the real practices of teachers in primary classrooms in terms of their CLT use in recent times. Fifth, because it is clear that the perceptions and implementations of teachers may not match, this study used both observations to see the actual practices of teachers and interviews to reveal their beliefs to collect data so that they can be compared before reaching any solid conclusions. Furthermore, the duration of the observations is relatively long because both classrooms were observed for one educational semester (3 months/12 weeks). Moreover, it is generally considered that private schools are more successful in English language teaching in Turkey and are preferred by many parents for that reason. This study also aims at investigating if there is such a difference between those different school contexts in terms of language learning and teaching practices. Last but not least, this study would allow us to see what is going on in real language classrooms in terms of

CLT implementations, and thus would provide feedback for policy makers and program designers so that they can take precautions and improve the language teaching programs accordingly.

1.6 Limitations of the Study

Considering the current study, there are some limitations to be mentioned here. First of all, this study is limited to the data obtained from two teachers working in two school settings in Istanbul. Second, this study is limited to the analysis of the data collected via Part A of the observation schemes generated by Spada and Fröhlich (1995). Third, the perceptions and opinions of teachers are also limited to the interview questions prepared for this study. Finally, the findings of this study are limited to the observed lessons of the two participant teachers.

1.7 Definitions of the Terms

Some significant terms related to this study are defined as follows:

Communicative Language Teaching: It is defined as the methodology that “aims broadly to apply the theoretical perspective of the Communicative Approach by making communicative competence the goal of teaching and acknowledging the interdependence of language and communication” (Larsen-Freeman, 2000, p. 121).

Communicative Orientation of Language Teaching Observation Scheme: It is described as “an instrument used in the observation of teaching and learning in second language (L2) classrooms” (Spada & Fröhlich, 1995, p. 1).

Young Learners: It is defined that “in EFL contexts, younger children are generally referred to children aged six to twelve” (Haznedar & Uysal, 2020, p. 4).

English as a Foreign Language: It describes “situations where students are learning English in order to use it with any other English speakers in the world – when the students might be tourists or businesspeople” (Harmer, 2007, p. 19).

Case Study: It is defined as “an intensive study of a single unit with an aim to generalize across a larger set of units” (Gerring, 2004, p. 341).

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In this chapter, the theoretical framework related to communicative language teaching (CLT), the use of CLT in Turkey, and the literature review about CLT are provided. First, the historical development and characteristics of CLT are explained. Then, the most common misconceptions are clarified, and the challenges encountered in its implementation are presented. Later, the context approach to CLT and the relationship between CLT and teaching English to young learners (TEYLs) are explained. Next, the introduction and development of CLT in Turkey are summarized with respect to Turkish EFL curriculum innovations. In addition, the latest Turkish EFL curriculum that adopts a communicative approach is introduced in detail. Last, the literature regarding the use of CLT in the world and in Turkey is reviewed briefly.

2.1 Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)

Communicative language teaching has been one of the most popular methods in the world for decades. It developed out of a need of the learners to be able to communicate context appropriately and is basically defined as the methodology that “aims broadly to apply the theoretical perspective of the Communicative Approach by making communicative competence the goal of teaching and acknowledging the interdependence of language and communication” (Larsen-Freeman, 2000, p. 121). Below is provided a detailed introduction and background for the method. It should be noted here that the Communicative Approach (CA) and Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) are used interchangeably in this paper, thus accepting CLT as a philosophy of language and/or a general approach rather than a specific methodology (Spada, 2007).

2.1.1 How CLT Emerged as a Language Teaching Method

The history of foreign or second language teaching has witnessed the development of various approaches and methods which have targeted learning or teaching additional languages in the most efficient and quick ways. Some of those methods focused on teaching how to use the language (oral proficiency) while others paid attention to mastering its structures (Celce-Murcia, 2001). Before and during the first half of the

twentieth century, the very traditional methodologies like the Grammar-Translation Method, the Direct Method, the Reform Movement, the Reading Approach, the Audiolingual Method, and the Situational Approach were widely utilized (Celce-Murcia et. al., 2014). Each of the above-mentioned methods emerged as a reaction to the drawbacks or limitations of the previous ones; therefore, they all highlighted a different aspect in accordance with the context and needs of the era and as a result of the questions about how to improve the language learning process in foreign language classrooms (Richards & Rodgers, 2014).

Additional language learning which was restricted to only a small elite community before the 60s turned into a common requirement in secondary public schools with the expansion of compulsory education to all children (Mitchell, 2003). Additionally, by this time Situational Language Teaching (SLT) had already been outdated due to its inefficiency to meet communicative needs. Therefore, a *paradigm shift* took place with the demand in the fast-growing world for more effective language teaching approaches and the advances in educational philosophies and technology. Moreover, the contributions of many British applied linguists such as Christopher Candlin and Henry Widdowson, sociolinguistic research by Hymes and Labov, and philosophical work by Austin and Searle, as well as the studies by language teaching specialists, paved the way for the emergence of *the Communicative Approach* which was widely welcomed all over the world starting from the mid-70s (Richards & Rodgers, 2014).

The Communicative Approach was significant in terms of its underlying theory of language which made *communicative competence* the goal of language teaching in addition to fostering the development of four skills and acknowledging the difference between language and communication. In other words, CLT was based on a functional theory of language, which views language as a way of communication. This particular perspective was mainly shaped by the functional views of Hymes and Halliday, who put the emphasis on *communicative competence* as a reaction to Chomsky's *linguistic competence* (Liu & Shi, 2007; Richards & Rodgers, 2014).

Obviously, *communicative competence* is the core of CLT (Savignon, 2002). Therefore, it is not possible to understand CLT without clarifying the construct of

communicative competence. To put it simply, *communicative competence* refers to the mastery of both linguistic forms and social rules such as the knowledge of when, how, and to whom those forms it is appropriate to use (Paulston, 1971, as cited in Hymes, 1992). More precisely, it is made up of four dimensions: *grammatical competence*, *discourse competence*, *strategic competence*, and *sociolinguistic competence*. First, *grammatical competence* refers to the knowledge of rules or simply linguistic competence. Second, *discourse competence* is much more about understanding the messages in relation to the coherence and cohesion of a text or discourse. Third, *strategic competence* helps speakers to continue communication by getting over the breakdowns. Last, *sociolinguistic competence* refers to the knowledge of how to use language in certain social contexts (Canale & Swain, 1980). When the above-mentioned construct of communicative competence is considered, it is readily apparent that it is not enough to know the structures of a language in order to use it communicatively; also, knowledge of language functions and discourse, which is beyond the sentence level is a must (Berns, 1983).

Another development leading up to the birth of CLT was the rise of *functional-notional syllabi* which were designed to compensate for the shortcomings of the structural materials. As a reflection of the *functional approach* which suggests using language for communication, a functional-notional syllabus highlights the use of a language over its usage (Berns, 1983). At this point, clarification is needed for the concepts of *functions* and *notions*. Basically, *functions* are the things people do through language (Berns, 1983) or the performatives in linguistic terms (Austin, 1962) such as inviting, refusing, or apologizing whereas *general notions* are concepts used in oral communication like space or importance and *specific notions* are the vocabulary particular to a topic such as name, surname or address for personal identification (Berns, 1983). Following the focus on notions expressed with language and socially appropriate functions in various linguistic research, teachers started to train their pupils about how to say things in certain contexts (Harmer, 2007).

In the same era, starting from the 1980s, other methods came into existence out of the umbrella term of the *Communicative Approach* such as Content-Based Instruction (CBI), Task-Based Language Learning (TBLT), and Participatory Approach. However,

these methods use the target language communicatively to achieve their goals which are integrated with language learning rather than focusing on the functions of the language and making the communication or using the language to create meaning itself their primary objective as in Communicative Language Teaching (Larsen-Freeman, 2000). Hence, rather than the methodology they use, they differentiate from one another in terms of the content of the instruction. Still, they can also be listed under the communicative methods or be considered as manifestations of CLT because over time the distinction has blurred, and the *communicative approach* has turned into an umbrella term (Spada, 2007).

Likewise, it is accepted by many linguists that CLT is more of an approach rather than a method and there is no best CLT as an authority, but it has some forms termed as strong and weak versions. In its simplest terms, while the strong form of CLT refers to ‘using English to learn it’, the weak form is ‘learning to use English’ (Richards & Rodgers, 2014, p. 86). In other words, while in the strong form, the lessons are based on meaningful tasks, in which students use the target language with the aim of communication; in the weak form, again the aim is communication, but it is practiced through more controlled and form-focused activities (Nassaji & Fotos, 2011).

2.1.2 Characteristics of CLT

There are certain characteristics of Communicative Language Teaching which distinguish it from other language teaching methods. These typical features are briefly explained below in accordance with the following titles: *goals, teaching and learning process, typical activities and materials used in CLT lessons, and teacher and learner roles*.

2.1.2.1 Goals

The primary goal of a typical CLT lesson is defined as focusing on the development of *communicative competence* so that learners can improve themselves both for grammatical and pragmatic language use (Brown, 2000). A high level of linguistic as well as communicative competence is aimed to use the structures appropriately in certain contexts (Littlewood, 1981). Moreover, both fluency and accuracy are addressed as they

complement each other in effective communication. Obviously, the learning and teaching processes are shaped in accordance with these overall goals set for language learners.

2.1.2.2 Teaching and Learning Processes

In CLT, the direct practice of communication without waiting for mastering the structures is prioritized (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). Therefore, lessons are designed in a way that provides students with chances to share their ideas in a typical social context as in real life so that they can learn about language functions and practice using the language to carry out these functions. In addition, as in real-life communication, students need to *negotiate meaning* to be able to maintain a conversation. This naturally requires the use of *pair* and *group work* very often which has also become one of the essential parameters of CLT (Larsen-Freeman, 2000). As for the activities, they are less controlled with little or no teacher intervention (Harmer, 2007) and so lessons are highly learner-centered (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). Finally, authentic materials are quite important to ensure that learners can be exposed to real language use relevant to their own lives (Li, 1998).

2.1.2.3 Communicative Activities

Furthermore, a CLT lesson should include communicative activities which have certain features. First, a communicative activity should include *information gap*, *choice*, and *feedback*. That is, the activity should be designed in a way that one side of communication knows about something while the other does not, and students are free to what to say and how to say it. Also, they should receive feedback from their interlocutors which lets them negotiate meaning (Johnson & Morrow, 1981, as cited in Larsen-Freeman, 2000). Correspondingly, activities can be placed on a continuum from extremely communicative to non-communicative ones. Accordingly, extremely communicative ones involve a desire to communicate with a communicative purpose. Furthermore, the focus is on content rather than form, and students use a variety of language rather than one specific form. Likewise, the teacher does not interfere with the flow of conversation, and materials do not control or dictate the language used by students. On the other hand, non-communicative activities show the absence of these features (Harmer, 2007).

Similarly, another distinction can be made between *pre-communicative* and *communicative* activities. While the former group refers to quasi-communicative and

more-controlled activities such as question and answer chains or drills prioritizing the correct language use to prepare the students for communicative tasks, the latter zeros in on meaning and the appropriate use of language in particular real-life situations (Littlewood, 1981). A similar differentiation is clarified for *functional communicative* and *social interactive* activities. Functional communicative activities aim to convey the meaning to the other side as effectively as possible rather than producing grammatically correct and context-appropriate sentences (Mitchell, 2003) whereas social interactive activities train students on using socially acceptable sentences; that is, using the right language at the right time to the right person (Littlewood, 1981).

In accordance with the descriptions given above, it is possible to mention some activities *typically* used in CLT lessons. The most commonly used ones include games with an information gap, choice, and feedback, scrambled sentences contributing to the development of cohesion and coherence, and role plays, either structured or less structured, creating opportunities for real-life-like conversations (Larsen-Freeman, 2000). Similarly, simulations that allow for realistic communication, puzzles for which students need to share information, and collaborative creations like writing a poem or a story in groups are also listed as popular communicative activities (Harmer, 2007). Lastly, other suggested communicative tasks include jigsaw, task-completion, opinion sharing, information transfer, and reasoning gap activities which are implemented in pairs or groups to increase opportunities for communication (Richards & Rodgers, 2014).

2.1.2.4 Communicative Materials

Considering the significance of exposure to real language use, *authentic* materials which are created for native speakers (Li, 1998; Wu, 2009) are preferred in CLT lessons rather than the ones deliberately produced for language teaching. However, in practice, a variety of materials are benefitted including authentic, adapted, or pedagogical ones, which all depend on real word interactions and genres (Mitchell, 2003). Moreover, the textbooks designed to teach languages by various international publishing companies today claim that they adopt the CLT methodology. For instance, the EFL textbooks in Taiwan and generally in Asia declare to be following CLT, though not found efficient by teachers (Huang, 2016).

2.1.2.5 Teacher and Learner Roles

CLT teachers have quite different roles from the ones in the traditional approaches. First of all, Breen and Candlin (1980) defined two fundamental roles for teachers in a communicative methodology. First, they are facilitators of the communicative atmosphere in the classroom among all participants. Second, they are ‘interdependent participants within the learning-teaching group.’ (Breen & Candlin, 1980, p. 99). Richards and Rodgers (2014) mention three additional roles for CLT teachers. First, as a *needs analyst*, they are meant to discover learner needs either formally or informally and plan their lessons accordingly. Second, as a *counselor* they make the communication as effective as possible through their feedback, paraphrasing, and confirmation questions. Last, as a *group process manager* they guide and monitor the communicative activities and note down the drawbacks of linguistic or meaning-based competence to comment on them later on, not to interfere with the flow of the communication.

Likewise, learner roles have been exposed to a paradigm shift and CLT lessons have become more *learner-centered* as opposed to the ones in traditional classes. In CLT, students are expected to participate in the activities cooperatively rather than deal with individualistic work. In contrast to seeing the teacher as the only role model, students interact with and learn from their peers in pairs or groups. Additionally, learner autonomy is highly emphasized since students are expected to take the responsibility for their own learning (Richards, 2006). Similarly, learners are considered as improvisers and negotiators as they should produce the language in unrehearsed situations and negotiate meaning with their peers (Qinghong, 2009).

2.1.3 Misconceptions about CLT

Throughout the development of CLT, some misconceptions have also appeared and spread among language teachers. For instance, it was thought that CLT means controlled role-play activities although peer interaction can be benefitted from at every stage of the lesson to ensure that learners also have control over their learning, and they learn from one another (Savignon, 1991). Likewise, in contrast to the general perception suggesting that teachers should not give feedback because it interrupts communication; in

fact, students can be provided with corrective feedback (even with explicit ones) in CLT lessons (Spada, 2007). Therefore, the following part is reserved to provide brief explanations for the most common three misconceptions regarding listening and speaking activities, grammar instruction, and L1 use in CLT.

First, because it is called communicative, it is generally thought that the focus is solely on listening and speaking activities. In fact, not just the oral skills but all four skills are emphasized from scratch. Just like in oral communication, there is also a negotiation of meaning between the reader and the writer and the meaning does not lie just in the text (Larsen-Freeman, 2000). By the same token, it is maintained that the principles of CLT are valid not only for listening and speaking but also reading and writing activities so that learners can develop confidence in all areas of language (Thamarana, 2015).

The second misconception is about the place of *grammar* in the approach. According to the general assumption, grammar instruction has no place in communicative classrooms. The studies in second language acquisition in the 1980s also had an influence on this idea. Since the two meaning-based hypotheses with no attention to form proposed by Krashen (Comprehensible Input Hypothesis) and Long (Interaction Hypothesis), it was supposed that CLT is an approach focusing only on listening and speaking and grammar teaching was of no importance (Spada, 2007). In contrast, since the beginning of the approach, it is known that communication also requires the correct use of structures and focusing on meaning does not necessarily result in neglecting the teaching of grammar. In addition, it is believed that in CLT, grammar instruction is more inductive, and students are meant to induce the rules on their own, which means that grammar is not overlooked at all (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). In this respect, it is argued that grammar learning is even easier when it meets the communicative needs of the learners (Savignon, 1991), and the teaching and learning process becomes more successful when form-focused and meaning-focused activities are implemented in a balanced way (Spada & Lightbown, 2013). Similarly, in CLT, the combination of form and meaning is more beneficial for L2 learners and explicit form-focused instruction is more effective than implicit one (Spada, 2011). In summary, grammar is touched on with different degrees according to the CLT

version adopted: the strong form which is more communicative or the weak form which is more controlled/focused on structure (Nassaji & Fotos, 2011).

The third misinterpretation is that in communicative classes L1 use is totally prohibited. It mainly resulted from the fact that the monolingual principle or the L2-use-only has been adopted since the grammar-translation method was criticized for its L1 use (Littlewood & Yu, 2009). However, CLT allows for limited or judicious use of it, but it should be minimized to ensure that learners are exposed to the target language as much as possible (Larsen-Freeman, 2000), especially in foreign language contexts in which the exposure to L2 is limited to the classrooms (Spada, 2007). Moreover, L1 is used both by students and teachers for many purposes, and when used in a reasonable amount, it has even some benefits (Yıldız & Yeşilyurt, 2016). For instance, L1 use can help save time and make some vocabulary or grammar instruction clearer (Turnbull, 2001). Additionally, it is used by teachers for various purposes such as giving instructions, supporting an enjoyable learning atmosphere, classroom management, providing collaborative interaction, establishing closer social relationships, and encouraging students' confidence in the classroom (Sert, 2005; Yıldız & Yeşilyurt, 2016). Furthermore, L1 can be used optimally in foreign language classrooms to construct the knowledge of L2 and facilitate interpersonal interactions; and the use of it should be decreased from introductory to the lower-intermediate levels (Pan & Pan, 2010).

2.1.4 Challenges to Apply CLT

CLT has been adopted to teach various foreign languages in many countries across the world, but mainly by the ones in which English is taught as a foreign language. However, CLT is a western-based approach and there are many difficulties to adopt the method in the EFL context, so it has drawn criticism since it has fallen short to meet all learners' needs in those parts of the world (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). It is obvious that teachers and policy makers from various countries have faced significant challenges in the implementation of CLT in EFL classes. For instance, several different challenges were found in Iran by Anani Sarab et. al. (2016), in Turkey by İnceçay and İnceçay (2009), in

Taiwan by Chang and Goswami (2011), in China by Wei et. al. (2018), in Afghanistan by Noori (2018), and in Bangladesh by Ansarey (2011) and by Ahmed (2016).

Despite the efforts to implement the method successfully, four categories of reasons were found explaining why CLT does not reach a high level of success. First, there are *difficulties caused by teachers* and they can be listed as teachers' deficiency in spoken English, lack of CLT training, and few opportunities to practice CLT. Second, there are *difficulties caused by learners* such as their low level of proficiency, and lack of motivation. Third, the *difficulties caused by educational systems* can be regarded as large classes, insufficient funding, lack of support by the government, and the examination system. Last, *difficulties caused by the CLT itself* refer to the lack of effective and efficient assessment instruments for measuring students' communicative competence (Al Asmari, 2015; Li, 1998). In the same vein, common conceptions coming from the traditional approaches that are against the principles of CLT such as the teacher as a knowledge transmitter rather than a facilitator, and the unwillingness of parents who think that the approach may result in unsuccessful exam results also cause some difficulties in the implementation of the approach. (Littlewood, 2013). Additionally, teachers cannot apply what they believe in due to some contextual hindrances including discipline problems, difficult working conditions, the tension between covering the material and dealing with students' questions, and a set syllabus. (Borg, 2003).

Although it is sometimes hard to implement the methodology in all contexts, the benefits of CLT for the teaching and learning process cannot be disregarded (Özşevik, 2010). That's why it seems that CLT will continue to be used in English language teaching both in ESL and EFL contexts. On the other hand, the focus of language teaching is shifting from methodology-only to considering contextual factors. Copland et. al. (2014), after conducting a mixed-methods and a worldwide study, found that teachers face many difficulties resulting basically from the lack of training, knowledge, and resources. Hence, they suggested that rather than focusing on the contemporary teaching methodologies in teacher education programs, the emphasis should be on the challenges and the skills they may require to overcome them, which would lead the teachers to have a more contextualized approach that is explained in the following section.

2.1.5 Context Approach to CLT

Although various approaches and methods have been developed for decades, there is popular wisdom asserting that CLT is the best and can work in any context. Despite this absolutist view about the appropriacy of CLT (Liao, 2004), there is also a tendency to support the view that contextual factors come before the methodology itself to have successful language education (Bax, 2003; Hu, 2005a; Kumaravadivelu, 2003; Littlewood, 2013; Spada, 2007). Accordingly, it is claimed that the term *method* itself is limited, and Kumaravadivelu (2003) prioritizes the dimensions of particularity, practicality, and possibility instead. First, the methodology should consider the particularity of teachers, students, goals, contexts, and sociocultural milieu. Second, it should be developed through practices rather than the reverse. Last, language education will help individuals to build their own subjectivity and social transformation with the help of sociopolitical consciousness. In this respect, there is no superiority of one method over the others. This is mainly because different approaches may be perfect for different English language teaching situations. Consequently, it is useless to label methods as good or bad, and the term ‘best’ is controversial because one approach cannot be functioning in all possible contexts and the best method may change from one teacher to another (Prabhu, 1990).

This new trend in language teaching has been termed as *Context Approach* by Bax (2003). Rather than implementing CLT with a focus on contextual factors, he claims that we do not need CLT but need a new approach, although not totally new. It prioritizes the context and needs analysis, then suggests choosing the suitable method according to each specific context, which again has the objective of communicative competence; thus, not ignoring the principles of CLT completely. While Bax (2003) represents the strong version of the context approach, the researchers in general shed light on the fact that any single approach cannot be suitable for all contexts all around the world. So, teachers should take their own situational realities into consideration to have successful outcomes in their teaching and create their methodology accordingly (Littlewood, 2013) rather than adopting one single methodology all the time.

2.1.6 CLT and Teaching English to Young Learners (TEYLs)

Although officially accepted as individuals under 18, the term ‘*young learners*’ is a controversial issue in second language studies. While it refers to children under 11-12 including preschoolers and primary school students (Ellis, 2014), in EFL contexts young learners may indicate children between 6-12 as well (Haznedar & Uysal, 2020). In an effort to develop both economically and politically, the starting age of English instruction has been decreased to the primary level in the recent past in various countries. For example, English language education starts in the 3rd grade in China, Korea, and Taiwan whereas pupils in Japan start to learn English in the 5th grade with one or two hours of instruction per week (Butler, 2015). Similarly, in other Asian countries including Bangladesh, Malaysia, Nepal, Singapore, and Timor-Leste, foreign language education begins in grade 1 which corresponds the age of 6-7 (Baldauf et. al., 2011). In Turkey, which is the context of the current study, the starting age of learning English as a foreign language is 6-6,5. That is, Turkish kids start to learn English in the 2nd grade in primary school and continue taking this course for the following ten years mandatorily.

Despite this latest trend to decrease the onset of age for foreign language learning, the motto ‘the younger the better’ is still a big controversy. In fact, a bulk of studies point out that in EFL settings, rather than starting earlier, the quality and the intensity of instruction are of much importance in terms of the success of foreign language education (Copland & Garton, 2014; Spada & Lightbown, 2013). On the other hand, in ESL contexts, because adolescents and adults are cognitively more developed than kids, they are more advantageous in the initial stages of learning a new language in its natural setting; however, children can catch up and overperform in the long term (Pinter, 2011). It is proved by a number of research that the claim ‘the younger the better’ is valid in terms of the acquisition of a native-like pronunciation (Ortega, 2013) even though there are exceptional adult learners (Pinter, 2011).

Teaching young learner groups requires distinctive expertise since there are particular issues to be considered while designing L2 instruction for young learner groups. In other words, child pedagogy (how to teach children) gains importance since it is necessary to consider developmental stages, create lessons according to the target age group, and so to

adopt an age-appropriate methodology. First, rather than focusing on language, using child-friendly pedagogy is more helpful for young learners (Zein, 2017). Accordingly, cognitive and social development of children, as explained and described by Piaget and Vygotsky should be regarded in L2 instruction as well (Harmer, 2007). For example, Piaget describes four stages for child cognitive development which are sensorimotor (0-2 years), intuitive (2-7 years), concrete-operational (7-11 years), and finally formal operational stage (11-16 years). According to these stages, children start to think about actions in the concrete-operational stage and they can think in abstract terms and hypothetically only in the final stage (Singer & Revenson, 1996). Vygotsky, on the other hand, emphasized social interaction with others while explaining learning and contributed to the field of language learning with his concepts such as the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) and scaffolding through which he explains the learning of a child in the social context (Ortega, 2013).

Second, the characteristics of young learners should be considered while designing EFL lessons. That is, young learners learn indirectly and focus on meaning, their attention span is short, and they are active learners. Hence, more TPR activities, a cooperative learning environment, and more enjoyable/engaging tasks are recommended for language classes with young learners (Kırkgöz, 2018). In the same vein, the intended age-appropriate methodology means using English as the communication medium, involving artistic components like games, songs, and stories, creating meaningful contexts, and providing children with real-life practice (Nguyen, 2021; Shin, 2017). When it comes to teaching an L2 to this specific group of learners, the following issues should be considered as well. First, L2 learners acquire some forms in a predictable order regardless of their L1. Therefore, kids do not always learn simple structures first; on the contrary, they may learn complex ones before easier ones although EFL syllabi are usually designed based on structural complexity (Haznedar, 2020). Finally, young learners get more motivated and engaged in English lessons when their preferences and perceptions are taken into account in the instructional design (Pinter & Zandian, 2014).

Curriculum policies have required the adoption of CLT in primary English classrooms in many countries in addition to decreasing the onset of L2 instruction. This, however,

resulted in some problems in practice. Especially, EFL teachers have faced some challenges while implementing CLT in primary classes (Khanam & Hoque, 2021; Ansarey, 2012; Othman & Kiely, 2016). First, shortage of primary-level English teachers specialized in the field, shortage of appropriate books, teachers' low proficiency both in English and pedagogy, large classes, unmotivated students, and grammar-based examination system were reported as the common issues in this respect (Copland et. al., 2014). Second, teachers' implementations do not match the methodology most of the time since the training for the methodology is not sufficient in most cases (Copland & Garton, 2014). Finally, such principles of CLT as authenticity and functional use of English are not found as applicable while teaching young learners because kids do not have an immediate need to communicate outside the class (Ohashi, 2015).

2.1.7 Introduction and Development of CLT in Turkey

Turkey is a monolingual country where the official language is Turkish. The most common compulsory foreign language taught at Turkish schools is English although there are some other elective foreign languages such as German or French offered in a few public and private schools. The dominance of English can be explained with its spread as a lingua franca and its contribution to international communication and catching up with technological developments after the establishment of the Turkish Republic in 1923 (Kırkgöz, 2009). As a developing country, there have been various educational reforms made in Turkey to improve the education system in general and the EFL curriculum in particular. In brief, the reforms in 1997, 2006, 2013, and lastly in 2018 can be considered as the touchstones of the current EFL curriculum in the Turkish education system.

2.1.7.1 The 1997 Curriculum Innovation

In the 1997 curriculum, compulsory education was increased to 8 years by combining primary (5 years) and secondary (3 years) education. Additionally, there were crucial changes affecting the ELT curriculum. First, the onset of EFL instruction was decreased to the fourth grade from the sixth grade in secondary school. Thus, for the first time, Turkish education system experienced TEYLs. Second, CLT was introduced to the curriculum for the first time declaring that the general objective of primary level EFL

instruction was to develop communicative competence so that students could communicate in the target language (Kırkgöz, 2007a). The objectives of the 1997 curriculum for 4th and 5th grades were ordered as follows: “(a) raise pupils’ awareness of a foreign language, (b) promote a positive attitude towards learning English language, (c) increase pupils’ interest and motivation towards learning English language, (d) establish classroom situations in the context of games so that pupils can have fun while learning English, and (e) set up dialogues and meaningful contextualized learning activities” (Kocaoluk & Kocaoluk, 2001, as cited in Sarıçoban, 2012, p. 2645). In addition, the teacher was displayed as a facilitator pointing out a more student-centered classroom environment as opposed to the previous tradition. Finally, the time devoted to English lessons was determined as two hours for 4th and 5th grades and four hours for the 6th, 7th and 8th grades in the 1997 curriculum (Kırkgöz, 2020).

Five years after the 1997 curriculum reform, during the 2002-2003 educational year, Kırkgöz conducted a study to see the effects of the new curriculum change. As a result, it was found that 70% of the teachers, who were quite experienced, were still teaching in the traditional way through L1 explanations while only a few were early adopters of the new curriculum who received in-service training. On the other hand, the majority of teachers found the objectives of the new curriculum appropriate for their students’ age although they also complained about the heavily loaded curriculum for upper grades (grades 6, 7, 8), non-authentic activities, insufficiency of teaching time, and crowded classes. Yet, they were positive about lowering the age for EFL instruction and were satisfied with the well-illustrated books (Kırkgöz 2007b).

The introduction of TEYLs in Turkey required a revision of the ELT teacher education curriculum as well. Thus, courses were added to familiarize pre-service teachers with young learners and the expertise to teach them (Kırkgöz, 2017). In addition, with the help of several organizations such as INSET, INGED, BC, and USIA, the ministry of education tried to train in-service teachers of English through workshops and seminars about the reform (Kırkgöz, 2007a).

2.1.7.2 The 2006 Curriculum Innovation

Turkey as a country trying to get full membership in the European Union, had some attempts to align its education system with their requirements; hence, in 2005, another curriculum innovation was made by MNE (Kırkgöz, 2007a). In that curriculum, which was put into practice in the 2006-2007 educational period (Kırkgöz, 2017), there was an emphasis on communicative competence as in the 1997 reform. In addition, the program highlighted multiple intelligences, experiential learning through drama and art activities, content and language integrated learning (CLIL), and a more constructivist approach suggesting that students learn better when they construct their own knowledge through individualistic and cooperative learning. Additionally, it adopted a performance-based assessment system with the use of portfolios (Kırkgöz, 2012).

After the innovation in 2006, Kırkgöz conducted three studies to explore the implementation of the revised curriculum. In the first one, it was revealed that the experienced/old teachers were transmission oriented, who focused on the delivery of the knowledge and put more emphasis on teaching grammar, and were using L1 (Turkish) in their lessons. These teachers were not familiar with TEYLs, did not have any training on or experience with young learners, and were only teaching adults before. In comparison, interpretation-oriented teachers emphasized the use of CLT (defined as COC, the communicative-oriented curriculum in the study), used varied activities, and taught vocabulary through games and songs as well as using the TL (English). These teachers had in-service training about CLT, and their beliefs about the objectives and the way children learn the language were consistent with CLT and TEYLs. In sum, it was concluded that EFL teachers needed to learn more about TEYLs (Kırkgöz, 2007b; Kırkgöz, 2008a). In a similar study conducted with 32 teachers, Kırkgöz (2008b) observed the lessons of the 4th and 5th grades and had interviews with the teachers as data-collecting instruments. In the end, it was found that while half of the teachers were transmission-oriented (traditional) teachers, 6 were interpretation-oriented following the principles of CLT, and the last 10 were more eclectic-oriented teachers who combined the traditional methods with the new ones. Thus, the requirement for teacher development activities was highlighted, especially for eclectic and transmission-oriented teachers. Finally, a third

study evaluating the EFL coursebooks provided free of charge by the MNE after the renovation in 2006 indicated that those materials were effective and compatible with the objectives of the curriculum since they were believed to support the use of CLT (Kırkgöz, 2009).

2.1.7.3 The 2013 Curriculum Innovation

Later, in 2012, several fundamental updates were made to cope with the deficiencies in the 2006 version of the curriculum. First, the shift in the educational system from the 8+4 model to the 4+4+4, combining primary, elementary, and secondary education necessitated an update in all the programs. Second, the starting age of English teaching was lowered to the 2nd grade while it was previously in the 4th grade, and the time devoted to English lessons was increased. Third, the principles of CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference) that includes communicative competence, learner autonomy, and intercultural awareness were adopted. Furthermore, the priority for grades 2-4 was determined as listening and speaking activities while the teaching of reading, writing, and grammar was not the focus in this version of the EFL curriculum. Thus, 10 simple units for each grade involving familiar and engaging topics for young learners were created based on the spiral approach with an emphasis on home and world cultures (Kırkgöz et. al., 2016; Kırkgöz, 2017).

The most significant innovation in this version of the curriculum was obviously lowering the onset of L2 instruction to 2nd grade. Therefore, several studies were conducted to reveal primary school teachers' (Gürsoy et. al., 2013) and teacher trainers' (Damar et. al., 2013) views on this issue, their beliefs about TEYLs and/or suitable methodology of foreign language teaching to young learners. Finally, it was concluded that both teachers and teacher trainers were in favor of starting EFL instruction in primary school or even at preschool due to some reasons including the critical period hypothesis, the advantage of better pronunciation, and kids' being more motivated and enthusiastic for language learning. In addition, they were pleased with the curriculum for young learners which was based on listening and speaking through visual and kinesthetic activities instead of grammar practiced with worksheets (Damar et. al., 2013; Gürsoy et. al., 2013).

In summary, in 1997 CLT was introduced to the language teaching program in Turkey and English was taught at the primary level (4th grade) for the first time. Later, in 2006, with the aim of standardizing language education according to the EU requirements, multiple intelligences, CLIL, and performance-based assessment were taken into consideration in designing the English curriculum. In the following years, in 2013, the education system was changed to 4+4+4, the age of English teaching was lowered to the 2nd grade (6-6,5 yrs.), and the principles of CEFR were added to the curriculum in addition to learner autonomy and intercultural awareness. Lastly, in 2018 the curriculum was revised for the last time, and values education was added to all programs including English.

2.1.7.4 The Latest Primary Level EFL Curriculum in Turkey

The latest curriculum update was done in 2018, and the related document was published by the Ministry of National Education (MNE) on the official website. In terms of its philosophy, the principles of CEFR were highlighted as it was in 2013. Additionally, as a reflection of CLT, the program put the emphasis on real-life learning/authentic learning environment, English as a medium of communication, the development of positive attitudes towards English, and the use of authentic materials in the classroom (MEB, 2018).

Some specific features of this program should also be mentioned here. First, the program refers to key competencies that each and every citizen of a country should have, as suggested by the EU, like traditional skills (communication in mother tongue and in foreign languages), digital skills (literacy, basic skills in math and science), and horizontal skills (learning to learn, social and civic responsibility, initiative and entrepreneurship, cultural awareness, and creativity). Second, the new curriculum includes values education embedded in the units/topic of the syllabi. These universal and national values include friendship, justice, self-control, honesty, respect, love, responsibility, patriotism, and altruism. Teachers and material designers are expected to choose the characters, texts, and visuals age-appropriately and in line with the adopted values. Third, it emphasizes process-oriented testing as well as self-assessment. In addition, teachers may benefit from formal testing such as written/oral exams, quizzes, projects, and homework. It is noted

that formative or summative tests can be used starting from the 4th grade to assess the learners' language proficiency while these cannot be applied to the 2nd and 3rd grades.

In general, the curriculum aimed to enable students to use the target language as a medium of communication for true communicative purposes in meaningful and interactive contexts relevant to their real-life experiences; to create a learning environment with 'interesting, engaging, and fun' activities; to teach age-appropriately to young learners through music, dance, plays, games, arts, and craft activities; to utilize various learning strategies both for teaching and assigning; and to achieve testing with a positive washback effect. The objectives for the 2nd grade are not different since it is aimed to help young learners love their foreign language and have fun while learning it.

In accordance with the above-mentioned objectives, ten units along with the functions and useful structures, language skills, and learning outcomes as well as suggested contexts, tasks and assignments are all provided in the program for teachers. Additionally, a theme-based approach relevant to students' immediate environment is adopted. Therefore, themes such as *words, friends, in the classroom, numbers, colors, at the playground, body parts, pets, fruit, and animals* are covered within the units regarding learners' existing knowledge. Activities are also suggested to create a communicative atmosphere rather than a traditional one. Second graders are expected to fulfill basic communicative functions such as greeting, introducing themselves, and describing objects by using relevant words targeting to achieve [A1] level competency as defined in CEFR by the end of primary school. *Listening* and *speaking* activities are emphasized while reading and writing activities which should not include more than 10 words can only be benefited from as out-of-class activities since limited reading and writing tasks are allowed in the 3rd and 4th grades. To sum up, the English language teaching program for second grades highlights the features of CLT as it refers to the use of meaningful interaction with a focus on listening and speaking activities in real-life-like situations through authentic materials, age-appropriate activities such as songs and games, a thematic curriculum pertaining to students' close contexts such as friends, school and playground, the ability to use basic communicative functions as well as referring to some key competencies, values education, and process-oriented assessment.

2.2. Literature Review

This section presents a comprehensive review of the literature regarding the use of CLT in various contexts. Within this scope, a total of 27 studies conducted in different countries across the world including Kuwait, Bangladesh, China, Taiwan, Iraq, Indonesia, Korea, Malaysia, Lao PDR, the UK, and Turkey from 2005 to 2020 were examined. As clear, most of these studies were carried out in EFL countries especially from the far east and at the primary level, as in the current study, in addition to a few more at secondary and/or high school levels. While some aimed at studying the current use of CLT in the above-mentioned countries, some others concentrated on the factors hindering or supporting its implementation. Finally, a few studies investigated learner and/or teacher perceptions about the use of the method.

CLT has been introduced to L2 teaching in various countries by their ministries of education since the late 20th century. Consequently, numerous studies were conducted to depict the actual use of CLT, especially in EFL contexts including Turkey. If not applied efficiently, some also reported the reasons hindering the use of the method. First, the studies conducted in EFL contexts, and then the ones from Turkey are provided below in detail.

2.2.1 Research on the Current Use of CLT in the World and Turkey

To begin with, believing that there is not a true match between the methodologies and the real practices in the classrooms and the social context of teaching should be taken into account to study the effectiveness of a methodology, Hu (2005b) wanted to investigate ELT practices across China and determine the level to which CLT was applied in classrooms, and the contextual factors facilitating the adoption of the methodology. The data were collected through a questionnaire 252 secondary school graduates responded to. In consequence, it was revealed that language teaching implications in the under-developed regions had more traditional features while the ELT practices in socio-economically advantageous regions reflected CLT principles more. Thus, it was suggested to have a more ecological perspective considering language classrooms within social,

cultural, and historical contexts rather than accepting the universal effectiveness of one single methodology.

Given the fact that the approach promoted in the language teaching curriculum does not guarantee its application in the classrooms, Al-Nouh (2008) wanted to investigate thoroughly the extent to which the EFL teachers used CLT in their classrooms in Kuwait. He aimed to find out if there was a mismatch regarding the curriculum objectives, materials/textbooks, teacher training programs, assessment/testing, and language practices in the classroom. With this purpose in mind, curriculum objectives, materials/textbooks, teacher training programs, and the assessment system were all examined. In addition, 23 EFL teachers of 4th graders with different teaching experiences randomly chosen from 5 different educational zones and/or schools were observed and interviewed. The observations were analyzed via the COLT scheme developed by Spada and Fröhlich in 1995. In the end, the following conclusions were made. First, the curriculum aimed to develop students' fluency as well as accuracy while using English with the integration of four skills, which was stated as a weak version of CLT. Second, the Fun with English textbook had some grammar points as the focus and notions/functions were taught around those topics. Those grammatical points and functions were all given in a meaningful context. While there were controlled form-focused activities, there were also meaningful activities including songs, stories, puzzles, and linguistic games. Third, the pre-service and Ministry of Education training courses familiarized teachers with CLT as well as the other teaching approaches and methods, teaching 4 skills including grammar and vocabulary, and assessment. Last, only linguistic competence was tested with form-focused items that evaluated accuracy while testing communicative competence and oral fluency was neglected. On the other hand, the observation revealed that the lessons were teacher-centered with a focus on language and accuracy rather than fluency. Moreover, although teachers had sufficient information about CLT and its principles, they found it difficult to implement in their context due to some reasons such as teaching kids, lack of time and resources, testing, and directions by the English Inspectorate not to use songs or stories. They could not help correcting errors

to prevent fossilization even if they knew that they should not be doing so. Finally, they had difficulty in teaching grammar in context.

After the curriculum supporting the learner-centered communicative approaches, especially CLT, was enacted in Korea in 2001, Kim (2008) aimed to depict the status quo of the new curricular reform and its implementation in the classroom. For this reason, she conducted a case study with an 18-year-experienced teacher. The data were collected through observations, interviews, and a stimulated recall procedure. The teacher's 32 low-proficiency level classes were observed in addition to four during and four post-observational interviews. During the stimulated recall procedure, the teacher watched some of her classes and was asked to explain her decisions. A comprehensive content analysis was conducted with the data. The study concluded that the teacher described herself as an old generation, and she used L1 (Korean) more than L2 (English) most of the time. The pattern of classroom interaction was found as IRF (Initiation - Response - Follow-up). The lessons were teacher-centered, and the students were passive participants in the lessons. The teacher tried to cover the textbook and prepare the students for the exams. Although she took many training sessions about CLT and new methodologies, the teacher continued to use the traditional ones such as GTM because it was the way she learned the language. She also confessed that what she believed and what the curriculum said were not compatible. The teacher believed that learning a language is a sequential process and that to be able to produce the language, the learners should learn basic grammar and vocabulary. The teacher valued drills and repetition through which, she thought, the learners could internalize vocabulary and structures. In the end, it was recommended that curricular reforms should not be done in a top-down manner, and being the real implementers of any innovation, teachers should know the reason why they are using the methods they are using, and they should reflect on their practices in the classroom.

In order to see the applicability of the CLT in a Bangladeshi setting at the primary level, Hamid and Honan (2012) wanted to provide a thorough picture of L2 pedagogy in action with respect to classroom discourses and interaction types, educational activities, teaching, and learning resources, organization of students, and teacher and learner

behaviors. Besides, the researchers aimed to provide data concerning L1 pedagogy which was considered to depict the language and literacy activities in Bangladeshi primary classrooms. 252 classroom observations which were provided by the English in Action project were used for the study including primary and secondary school lessons. Second, the data were used from the research carried out by Hamid (2010), in which he observed 27 primary classes and had informal interviews with the teachers and the students. The results demonstrated that the L1 and L2 classes lacked meaningful communication practices and they were mostly led by teachers who left little opportunity for learner-focused activities, and creativity development. Thereby, the authors suggested that various factors should be considered while discussing the issues hindering the goal of communicative competence: e.g., resource allocation and personal availability, learner-readiness, or socio-educational setting. Lastly, rather than taking the approach as it is without any changes, local features (not the universal) should be taken into consideration, and it should be adapted to the new linguistic ecology and academic culture.

Thinking that there are many different approaches and methods to teaching languages, Intarapanich (2013) aimed to detect which of those approaches, methods, and strategies were used in Lao PDR. In this qualitative study, the researcher observed five different teachers from primary and high school (secondary) levels for three weeks and also conducted in-depth interviews with them about their teaching styles and strategies. After all, the researcher found that teachers used GTM, and prioritized writing, translation, and TPR exercises at the primary level. In addition, role-plays were observed very rarely at that level. In the lower-secondary level, CLT activities were utilized such as role-plays, discussions, dialogues, debates, and pair and group work, during which L1 was also used very frequently. ALM was also utilized when the students listened to an excerpt, completed it, and then repeated the utterance. In the upper-secondary level, though, CLT activities were rather dominant with the teacher being a facilitator most of the time. All in all, it was obvious that GTM, ALM, and CLT were the most used methodologies in the classrooms of Lao PDR.

Considering the language teaching curriculum renovation in 2011 in Malaysia, Hardman and A-Rahman (2014) aimed to investigate the extent that teachers used CLT in

their classes and what they understood from the principles of the new curriculum and its practical implications to be used in their classrooms. Thus, the data were collected from 8 teachers through observations (4 classes of each) along with the field notes, systematic observations, which means the observation of lesson recordings, stimulated recalls of lesson recordings in which the teachers watched their lessons and commented on the significant points, and through the teacher interviews. For the analysis of systematic observation, the transcriptions of the lessons were analyzed (discourse analysis) to show the interaction type between the teacher and the students; the most common one was suggested by Sinclair and Coulthard as the three-part IRF pattern (initiation, response, follow up). In the end, the observation of 32 lessons revealed that only one-fourth of the time teachers interacted with the students. Most of the time teachers led the classes and the students were busy with individual tasks or textbooks at their desks. The analysis of systematic observation with the percentages of IRF patterns demonstrated that the teachers were mostly busy with clarifying, questioning, and giving examples on the board with a focus on rule teaching, which was verified by the stimulated recalls of lesson sessions, too. This finding suggested that the teachers were not using CLT in their classes and most of them were unaware of the principles of communicative approaches and the importance of teacher-student talk patterns. The analysis of the interviews showed that teachers had difficulty in applying communicative activities due to large class sizes, the heavily loaded curriculum, students' low levels, and the stress of the examination held at the end of the year. Some teachers also reported the incongruence between the curriculum and the assessment which depended mostly on writing. Thus, the researchers concluded the study by stating that teachers are one of the key elements in a successful education system, and to be able to implement the new curriculum effectively teachers should internalize what the new curriculum suggests and also be trained about the new requirements such as dialogic educational methods or learner-centeredness.

Considering CLT as the current approach suggested by the Ministry of Education in Bangladesh, Islam (2016) aimed to study how far it was applied in primary classrooms because it was the root level in teaching English in the country. The researcher used qualitative methods including interviews with 10 teachers, group interviews with 42

students, and 5 classroom observations. For the observations, a checklist with five criteria was utilized. The study revealed several findings. First, eight out of ten teachers had no idea about nor any training on CLT, and most of the time they preferred L1 (Bangla) over English. Second, the teachers neglected to use listening and speaking activities and used pre-communicative activities such as question-answer, fill-in-the-blanks, and grammar-based exercises. Third, teachers prioritized accuracy rather than fluency. Fourth, the interaction pattern in the classrooms was teacher-centered where the students were not engaged much and there was no pair or group work. Therefore, CLT was not as effective as it should be at the primary level in Bangladesh and it was not applied well enough due to the reasons mentioned above and other factors such as the exam system, students' phobia to learn English, insufficient facilities, and large class sizes.

There are also studies investigating the implementation of CLT at other educational levels, as well. For instance, Han (2016) examined the lesson plans of four teachers and conducted two semi-structured interviews with each. In addition, the researcher analyzed the teachers' lesson plans and observed three teachers' actual practices, too. For the data analysis, she used the reflexive-dialectical perspective. For the analysis of the lessons, the COLT scheme was used but analyzed qualitatively rather than calculating the minutes and the percentages of each activity. The study showed that although the teachers had some positive views about CLT they also had conceptual confusion. In addition, teachers did not have communicative goals in their lesson plans probably because the state did not provide the teachers with appropriate guidelines about using CLT. All the teachers focused on teaching grammar and translation activities because they believed that the students needed basic grammar and vocabulary knowledge to be able to communicate. Similarly, GTM was the way they learned the language. The teachers also focused on teaching reading and using GTM to prepare the students for the exam. Although there were some information gap activities in the lessons, students' production was quite limited. In addition, the exam-oriented education system hindered the use of CLT. Another problem was teachers' insufficient speaking skills and students' lack of listening skills. Excessive load of administrative work made it hard for teachers to prepare communicative activities. In the end, the researcher suggested organizing

programs for teachers' professional development and designing a curriculum considering the contextual realities.

Taking into consideration the poor status of ELT for about forty years, Hoque et. al. (2018) conducted a comprehensive study of the current language practices in Bangladesh. They included all stakeholders in the study: the ELT practitioners, head teachers, teacher trainers, learners, and national ELT specialists. A questionnaire regarding the perceptions of CLT was filled in by randomly chosen 100 teachers from different rural parts of Bangladesh. Later, semi-structured interviews were conducted with ten ELT practitioners, five CLT trainers, and ten head teachers. In addition, a workshop was held with those interviewees. On top of that, five English lessons were observed with a checklist. The data were analyzed using qualitative and quantitative techniques. The findings suggested that CLT was not implemented effectively, learners at the primary level did not get skilled in any communicative abilities, and the goals hitherto in the curriculum were not met. Additionally, the ELT setting in Bangladesh lacked a CLT-friendly environment due to uninteresting activities, few technological opportunities in the classrooms, little input outside the school as well as insufficient teacher training.

Likewise, Muhridza and Satanihpy (2019) attempted to examine the use of CLT in Malaysian primary classrooms. With regards to their goals, a 90-minute lesson of a 3rd grade was analyzed through content analysis. The results revealed that the teacher supported the active participation of the students; however, it was between the teacher and the students and learner-learner interaction (pair/group work) was missing in the lesson. Also, the teacher was overcorrecting the students during class time, which is contrary to the principles of CLT. In addition, the teacher used both L1 and L2 to be able to have meaningful communication. Students generally responded in L1, but they also did understand what was going on. All in all, the teacher had a communicative approach in the general sense and could use different strategies to make the students alert and catch their attention.

Since there is a paradigm shift in teaching languages towards more communicative approaches all over the world and in South Korea, An (2020) aimed to show the picture of English language teaching in Korean primary schools, where CLT was emphasized by

the government. Accordingly, the researcher observed twelve primary language classrooms (3rd, 4th, 5th, and 6th grades) of eight different schools, and conducted interviews both with 25 pupils and 16 teachers. In addition, 191 teachers and 880 students completed a questionnaire to state their views about the current ELT practices in the country. Later, the data obtained from the interviews and the observations were analyzed qualitatively with thematic analysis while the data from the questionnaires were analyzed with quantitative methods on SPSS. During the observations, the researcher targeted the interactions, activities, and materials. In the end, the data of the observations focusing on reading and writing classes revealed that the lessons were reflecting CLT principles. In regard to the interaction types, the lessons were led by the teachers, but later students also started interactions especially while asking for help. Although many student-student interactions were observed, they were mainly in the L1 (Korean) whereas the teacher-student interaction was held in the target language most of the time (English). Related to the activities, it was found that, in the reading classes, teachers used pre-, while, and post-reading activities. In the writing lessons, they used controlled, guided (most of the time), and free writing activities. Additionally, teachers used activities integrating other skills such as speaking, thus enabling the students to use the target language in a meaningful and authentic context. Regarding the materials, the main one was the textbook suggested by the government. The teachers also benefited from other materials such as flashcards, story books, worksheets, and PPT slides. The results of the questionnaires indicated that teachers preferred game-like activities in their lessons so that their students would have fun. They used group work for reading activities and more individual work for writing; while the students thought that they had group work both for reading and writing. Teachers valued integrating the skills instead of focusing on one. On the other hand, teachers had difficulties due to the fact that the students varied in their level of English proficiency, which was verified in the students' questionnaire, as well. To enable more scaffolding among students, teachers preferred to mix the students with different proficiency levels, and they used more guided and slightly easy tasks in the lessons because providing individual help was not an easy thing in crowded classes. Lastly, since the teachers were not satisfied with the textbooks provided by the government, they modified them when

needed and used other materials to attain their goals. Hence, the major findings of the study could be listed as such: teachers tried to use interesting activities in meaningful situations to increase student participation, and teachers prioritized group work activities that enabled students to learn from each other (although they used L1 rather than L2). In addition, teachers and students found it essential to read and write in English before communicating. The most significant obstacle for teachers was the differentiation in their students' proficiency.

Another study examining the use of CLT was conducted by Guzmán-Alcón (2019) in the UK. Since learning languages has many advantages and arouses the students' interest in other cultures, he wanted to look at the principles of CLT used in CLIL and FL classrooms in an international primary school in Oxfordshire, UK. The principles studied in the research were the use of tasks, collaborative work, rich meaningful input, corrective feedback provision, and the use of L1 and L2. In addition, both classes were observed for the interaction types. The researcher used action research and observed five FL sessions (Spanish) and five CLIL sessions of Math taught in Spanish. In the end, it was concluded that FL and CLIL sessions reflected the principles of CLT to a great extent. However, FL classrooms lacked meaningful tasks and cooperative learning; instead, there were more teacher-centered and focus-on-form activities while in CLIL classrooms the students learned the language through tasks.

Likewise, some studies with a similar scope were conducted in the Turkish context as well. First, Kırkgöz (2007b) conducted a study in Adana, following the curriculum innovation in 1997, to reveal teachers' practices and perceptions about curriculum innovation, and the appropriateness of the new program for young learners. Accordingly, a questionnaire was filled in by 50 teachers from different primary schools, one class hour of 18 teachers was observed, and 7 of them were interviewed. The study concluded that 70 percent of the teachers used grammar-based approaches supported by L1 explanations rather than CLT-based activities such as songs, dialogues, or games. Hence, they were referred to as transmission-oriented (Kırkgöz, 2008a). These teachers were dominantly experienced teachers with a set of beliefs regarding teaching a language in their mind, who had taught adult learners before. Only eight teachers with previous in-service training

were found to be communicative and integrated different approaches in their lessons in accordance with learner needs. So, they were called interpretation-oriented. These teachers had in-service training about CLT, and their beliefs about the objectives and the way children learn the language were consistent with CLT and TEYLs (Kırkgöz, 2008a). Moreover, the teachers found the curriculum appropriate and realistic for 4th and 5th graders thanks to the use of illustrations making the process meaning-based and fun for young learners. However, the transition from grade 5 to 6 was not smooth and the programs designed for 6th, 7th, and 8th grades were too dense which did not allow for practice. In addition, the teachers expressed that lowering the age would be fruitful for learners and the course books of 4th and 5th grades were well illustrated and user-friendly. Likewise, they welcomed the books provided by the government at no cost. However, they were not pleased with the activities in the books since they were inauthentic and decontextualized. Also, there was dissatisfaction with the insufficient weekly meeting hours and the large class size making it difficult to cover the curriculum. Consequently, it was suggested that more in-service teacher development activities should be organized, and course books should be improved.

Then, Kırkgöz (2008b) conducted a similar study with 32 teachers. The lessons of the 4th and 5th grades were observed, and the teachers were interviewed. The study showed that 6 teachers were interpretation-oriented following the principles of CLT while half of them were transmission-oriented (traditional), and the last 10 were more eclectic-oriented and combined traditional methods with more modern ones. Consequently, teacher development activities were suggested especially for eclectic and transmission-oriented teachers.

After the theoretical improvements in language teaching approaches and methods, Haznedar (2010) wanted to study to what extent they were adopted by primary and high school language teachers in their classrooms, the problems they had, and what they needed in general. Thus, a survey was filled in by more than 500 teachers in Istanbul. In addition, she gave seminars to teachers and learned more about their problems. As a result, she reached the conclusion that although the teachers were aware of the communicative ones, they were still using traditional teaching methods. In addition, although most teachers

were teaching in primary classrooms, they did not use appropriate materials and activities for their learners. Moreover, it was revealed that one-third of the teachers found in-service teacher training programs quite useless. Thus, it was suggested that these programs should be led by academicians who know what is going on in real classrooms, who are experienced in teacher training, and who conduct research with them. Another recommendation was that teacher training programs in Turkey should be enriched to make teachers more knowledgeable about applied linguistics, second language acquisition, teaching English to young learners, and language policies.

Another case study indicating the use of the communicative approach in Turkish high school classrooms was conducted by Denkci Akkaş and Çöker (2016). Regarding that CLT is quite popular in the world but cannot be applied enough in Turkey due to some challenges, the researchers aimed to reveal how the CLT method was conducted in 9th-grade high school classrooms besides depicting the teacher and student perceptions. While collecting data, the researchers observed one hour of two different 9th-grade classes in a week for a semester. In addition, they had interviews with the teachers and the students. To analyze the data collected via the COLT observation scheme, the percentages were calculated for each heading. Later, a content analysis was applied to the interview data. In the end, it was reported that the lessons were more communicative in the Anatolian high school when compared to the ones in the general high school; however, it was still not the ideal one as explained and suggested in the Turkish curriculum. Additionally, the researchers recommended that teacher training activities during the first years of a curriculum change are quite important to be able to see the effects of it.

As a result, the studies above show that CLT is not utilized for EFL instruction properly in most countries including Turkey, and lessons are still mostly traditional/teacher-centered because of various hindrances (Al-Nouh, 2008; Hamid & Honan, 2012; Han, 2016; Hardman & A-Rahman, 2014; Haznedar, 2010; Hoque et. al., 2018; Hu, 2005b; Intarapanich, 2013; Islam, 2016; Kırkgöz, 2007b; Kırkgöz, 2008a; Kırkgöz 2008b; Kim, 2008). However, this literature review also revealed a few cases indicating a more communicative EFL instruction (An, 2020; Guzmán-Alcón, 2019; Muhridza & Satanihpy, 2019). It is also understood that the research on CLT was mostly

conducted in primary classes although there were also several studies from the secondary or high school levels (Denkci Akkaş & Çöker, 2016; Han, 2016; Hu, 2005b; Kim, 2008).

2.2.2 Research on Factors Hindering the Use of CLT

Given that CLT is not applied as efficiently as expected, some researchers specifically examined the difficulties in its implementation so that they can be eliminated. The studies from different countries involving Bangladesh, China, Iraq, Taiwan, and lastly the ones from Turkey are briefly reviewed below.

There has been a shift from more traditional approaches to communicative ones such as task-based, learner-centered methods, and CLT since 2001 in the English language teaching curricula of China. In the same curriculum, the type of assessment was regulated in a way that supported testing the students' competence rather than phonological or grammatical knowledge. It was also a reality that there were some factors affecting the implication of CLT such as large class size, insufficient teacher proficiency, lack of resources and class meeting time, examination stress on students, and cultural resistance. The study by Li and Baldauf (2011) aimed to explore the role of these factors in hindering the use of CLT. To collect data, they had semi-structured focus group interviews with 73 primary and secondary Chinese teachers. Five main categories were detected in the content analysis: teaching materials, teachers, educational system, teaching methodology, and assessment. First, the teaching materials were too difficult and loaded for the learners and incongruent with the current testing system. Second, teacher training programs were found ineffective and impractical by most teachers. Most teachers lacked positive attitudes towards the 2001 curriculum and did not study that curriculum in detail. Likewise, many teachers struggled to use the new, more challenging textbooks to execute the new curriculum. Additionally, there was a shortage of teachers, meaning that the government did not provide all the areas including suburban and rural ones with new and qualified teachers. Thus, those schools had to hire people knowing some English from different fields to teach it. Third, the educational system remained the same and students had to pass one final exam to be able to study at higher levels, and this forced them to be exam-oriented, which was in contrast with the new curriculum promoting communicative

competence. Next, teachers had problems in applying the new curriculum and CLT-based, learner-centered activities because of large class sizes, overloaded weekly programs, and insufficient competence in the English language and the curriculum. Teachers also found it risky to implement new approaches because they had to prepare students for the exams. Lastly, the summative assessment was a critical issue because it determined the students' future.

Likewise, Ansarey (2012) attempted to study the elements encouraging or preventing the use of CLT in the Bangladeshi context. She used questionnaires filled in by 30 teachers from primary and secondary levels and had interviews with five of them. The data from the questionnaire were analyzed through SPSS and the content analysis was conducted with the interview data. The results showed that although the teachers intended to use CLT in their classrooms, four major obstacles hindered its use in Bangladesh: teachers, students, the educational system, and CLT itself. First of all, the teacher-related factors were lack of sufficient oral skills for L2, limited knowledge of sociolinguistics, lack of training for CLT, little time for preparing the materials for communicative activities, and misinterpretation of CLT. Second, student-related factors were listed as low proficiency and passive learning style with little desire to participate in communicative activities. Third, the system-related factors were reported as the lack of support and authentic materials, large class sizes, and assessment depending only on grammar knowledge. Last, the CLT-related factor was the fact that there was not an adequate explanation about how to implement the method, specifically in an EFL context.

As one of the countries making some regulations in L2 policies promoting the language as a communication tool, Taiwan had a new language curriculum supporting the use of CLT in 1994 and 95. Accordingly, Huang (2016) aimed to study the perceptions of rural EFL teachers about difficulties in the implementation of the method. The researcher used both quantitative and qualitative data collection tools which included a questionnaire about the perceived difficulties in applying CLT and an interview about the teachers' general views about CLT and how they practiced it in the classroom. 75 teachers took the survey while 15 of them also participated in the interviews voluntarily. After the data analysis, several constraints were detected affecting the use of CLT in classes:

students' low L1 resources affecting their new language learning, students' lack of proficiency and learning motivation, their unwillingness to communicate, parents' indifferent attitudes, teachers' insufficient English proficiency and the lack of in-service training with little emphasis on the use of CLT, crowded classes, insufficient class meeting time, uninteresting books with little CLT focus and lastly the paper-based testing system ignoring the oral performance of students.

In a similar vein, Sherwani and Kılıç (2017) targeted to discover the attitudes of 58 Iraqi EFL teachers towards CLT and the factors hindering and facilitating its use. To see the attitudes of teachers, a five-point Likert scale was used. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted with six teachers. SPSS and thematic content analysis were used to analyze the data. The research concluded that although the teachers had positive attitudes towards CLT, the following factors might be hindering its use: the education system including a test-based curriculum and large class sizes, educators lacking competence in English and needing CLT training, learners who are not fluent, and the CLT approach itself which is not contextually suitable for Iraq, where English is only used in the classroom.

Similar studies were also conducted in the Turkish context. First, Özşevik (2010) aimed to study the major difficulties confronted in the implementation of CLT in primary and secondary-level classrooms in Turkey. Thus, the data were collected through online questionnaires completed by sixty-one Turkish EFL teachers from primary and secondary levels and semi-structured interviews with six of them about their perceptions of the use of CLT. A content analysis was conducted for the qualitative data while statistical analysis and frequency calculations were used for the quantitative part. The study concluded that teachers had a clear perception of the method. In addition, four main sources of difficulties in implementing CLT were discovered: teachers, students, the education system, and the method itself (CLT). First, the problems related to the teachers were realized as their insufficiency in oral English abilities, lack of sociolinguistic knowledge, inadequate training in CLT, insufficient time for developing communicative materials, and misperceptions about CLT. Second, the student-related problems were detected as their low level of English proficiency and passive way of learning, reluctance to engage in

communicative activities, and indifference to having communicative competence. Third, the problems caused by the educational system were mentioned as a lack of support from colleagues and the administration to use the CLT method as well as financial support from the government. Additionally, the teachers mentioned the need for authentic materials, large classes, and an assessment system evaluating the grammar knowledge of the students. Last, there were challenges reported by the teachers: insufficient evaluation tools, and little specification of CLT in the EFL settings. Second, considering that CLT was not applied as efficiently as should be in Turkish classrooms, Hunutlu (2011) conducted a study to investigate the beliefs of 111 primary and secondary teachers about CLT and their classroom practices as well as the relationship between them. In order to collect data, she used a questionnaire and analyzed the data on SPSS. As a result, it was found that although the teachers had positive beliefs about CLT, they had some difficulties while implementing the method in their classrooms, which were non-communicative textbooks, lack of materials for CLT, and limited class hours. Third, another study conducted by Coşkun (2011) aimed to reveal the Turkish teachers' attitudes towards some features of CLT and to compare them with their actual classroom practices. In the end, it was found that there were mismatches between what the teachers believe and apply in reality. As for the problems in implementing CLT, he found the major difficulties as large class size, grammar-based examination system, and little time to prepare communicative materials. Fourth, Mutlu and Kaşlıoğlu (2015) aimed to see the factors promoting and hindering the application of CLT as well. With this purpose in mind, they conducted semi-structured interviews with six secondary school teachers (three from a state school and three from private a school). In the end, they concluded that teachers' understanding of the method and the students' willingness to communicate were supportive of implementing CLT. On the other hand, the Turkish educational system depending on test-based assessment, crowded classes, and insufficiency of instructional hours as well as deficiency in reaching materials supporting CLT and the coursebooks provided by the government were counted as the limitations.

As a result, the literature investigating the factors hindering the application of CLT revealed that they are related to teachers, students, the educational system, and CLT itself.

First of all, the factors related to teachers were found as follows: teachers' lack of proficiency in L2, lack of training for CLT, insufficient time to prepare communicative activities, and shortage of language teachers. Second, the student-related factors were reported as their unwillingness to communicate, lack of motivation, and their low level of English proficiency. Third, the factors related to the educational system were listed as the text-based assessment, large class size, lack of materials supporting the use of CLT including textbooks and videos, overloaded curriculum, and the mismatch between the curriculum and the assessment. Last, the CLT-related factors were found as its inappropriacy in some contexts, insufficient assessment tools to measure students' communicative competence, and little explanation about using the method in EFL contexts.

2.2.3 Research on Teacher and Student Perceptions About the Use of CLT

Finally, there are a few recent studies from Bangladesh and Indonesia investigating teacher or student perceptions about their experience with the communicative method. To start with, Shrestha (2013) conducted research in different parts of Bangladesh with 600 primary-level students to reveal their perceptions about their foreign language learning designed in accordance with communicative language teaching due to a project called English in Action. To collect data, he had semi-structured group interviews with 100 different groups of six participants, each from a different school. Based on the qualitative data analysis, he concluded that reciting and drills, use of songs, pair and group work, playing games, listening to the audio, and the use of visuals were the concepts most mentioned by the students. Hence, the students enjoyed the activities such as role plays and dialogues more than grammar instruction and translation; however, at the same time, they had positive attitudes towards reciting and drills. Although the amount of English used by the teachers and communicative activities seemingly increased, the teachers continued to use mixed methods (traditional and communicative) while applying those activities in the classrooms.

In addition, considering that teaching English vocabulary to young learners is different from teaching adults, pictures and games, which are extensively used in CLT,

are quite attractive to young learners; Yuliawati and Aprillia (2019) aimed to study the advantages of using games and pictures in teaching English vocabulary. The researchers used action research as their method, and they collected the data through observation, conversation, and interview. The participants were 30 students from Indonesia in an after-school institution. Before using games and pictures, the researchers used traditional ways such as word lists and memorization to teach vocabulary. Then, they had an interview with the students and concluded that the students found learning vocabulary in the traditional way rather difficult. However, after the inclusion of games and pictures, the students were more interested in learning new vocabulary, and it was more understandable for them.

On the other hand, some other studies focused on teacher perceptions. For instance, Rahmawati (2018) intended to investigate the perceptions and experiences of teachers regarding the use of CLT in their classes. She collected the data qualitatively from six teachers (two from each level - primary, secondary, and university) through a questionnaire and in-depth interviews. The study concluded that all the teachers had a rudimentary comprehension of CLT since they focused on the notion of communication while defining the approach and they were all aware of its importance. However, most schoolteachers stated that CLT is teaching speaking but not grammar, which can be considered a misconception since in CLT grammar teaching is not forbidden but is seen as the basement for communication. However, university-level teachers were aware that grammar is important and can be taught through several different ways such as songs, media, newspapers, pair or group works, and games. Also, almost all the teachers stated L1 can be used to help students understand the materials and build their self-confidence, as well as to explain complex issues although CLT suggests that the mother tongue should be minimized.

Likewise, thinking that teachers' beliefs and practices may not match, Rahman et. al. (2018) wanted to inquire into the relationship between those beliefs and the real implications of CLT in Bangladeshi classrooms. For this reason, a case study was conducted with two teachers trained in TESOL who were teaching at the secondary level. To collect data, the researchers used semi-structured interviews and classroom

observations. The results indicated that the teachers had some contradictory beliefs with regard to CLT. While the teachers believed that the classrooms should be learner-centered and the teaching should focus on all four skills which are congruent with CLT, they also believed in the power of error correction and the L1 use to explain the meaning. Also, the classroom observations indicated the teachers were not focusing on listening and speaking activities because the exam system did not assess those skills, which can be counted as contradictory to their beliefs. Similarly, even though they believed in learner-centered classrooms, the lessons were led by teachers most of the time because the classes were too crowded to have pair or group work. In line with their error correction, they corrected their students' errors so as not to cause fossilization. They also used L1 many times, and they explained that it was always demanded by the learners, but the researchers found out that they were given even the smallest instructions in Bangla. The researchers concluded that the mixed beliefs of teachers may have been affected by their own language learning periods rooted in GTM. Furthermore, they marked that the reason why the teachers cannot implement what they believe may be the contextual factors such as large size classes and the examination system.

In general, the studies examining the teachers' and students' perceptions demonstrated that students enjoyed communicative activities more than traditional ones. On the other hand, it was also pointed out that some teachers did not have a thorough idea about CLT despite having positive perceptions of it. Nevertheless, teachers reported that they could not implement it all the time as it should be due to several reasons.

3. METHOD

In this part, the research methodology is explained. Accordingly, detailed information regarding the research design, setting and participants, the procedure, the data collection instruments, and analysis techniques is provided in the following sections.

3.1 Research Design

This study aims at depicting the inclusion and implementation of Communicative Language Teaching in EFL instruction at the primary level in Turkey where the central and national EFL curriculum has been based on the development of communicative competence since the curriculum reform in 1997. In line with this aim, this study has been designed as a qualitative one for several reasons. First, a qualitative study comes up with a description of naturally occurring phenomena without the intervention of any experiment or treatment. Likewise, no intervention or treatment was implemented for this research since the focus was not to reveal a cause-and-effect relationship. Second, this study has a holistic perspective to collect as much data as possible and it is heuristic in the sense that very few or no decisions were taken prior to the start of the investigation (Seliger & Shohamy, 1989). That is, although this study started with a question, no hypothesis was generated beforehand. Third, Creswell and Poth (2018) defined qualitative research as the study of a problem related to society and people for which the researcher obtains the data from the natural setting and then provides some patterns out of that investigation. Likewise, this current research aims to see the actual situation of EFL instruction in terms of the use of CLT at the primary level *in-depth* rather than focusing on one specific aspect of the second language learning period. Fourth, in order to depict the actual case as it unfolds, observations are needed rather than just presenting the perceptions of the participants about the issue since they might be biased. Hence, both observations and interviews were conducted to reveal the findings reflecting the actual case and any discrepancies between the perceptions and the reality. Fifth, this qualitative research has been designed as a case study which is a common approach to this type of inquiry, since it is not possible to observe all the primary classes in the Turkish EFL context, and a case study is defined as ‘*an intensive study of a single unit with an aim to*

generalize across a larger set of units' (Gerring, 2004, p. 342). Furthermore, this is an *instrumental case study* as it involves some participants representing the group of interest to diagnose a situation or concept (Hancock & Algozzine, 2006). Finally, this can be called a *multiple case study*, enabling the researcher to present different viewpoints on the subject (Creswell & Poth, 2018) since two different contexts were included: a public and a private school.

3.2 Setting and Participants

A case study has some parameters such as the place and the time the study is conducted as well as the people who participate in it (Creswell & Poth, 2018). As it is apparent that one cannot observe all the primary classes in Turkey, the boundaries of this research, namely the setting, time, and people to be involved were all determined beforehand. First, the contexts of this study are two second-grade classes from a public and a private primary school. Public and private are the main categorization for primary schools in the Turkish education system and both school types were included within the scope of this study so that any possible similarities and/or differences between them regarding the phenomenon under examination could be indicated. Representative samples for a public and private school were selected for the study by using *typical case sampling* -which is a type of purposive sampling-, thinking that the participant EFL teachers are typical/standard ones working in typical private and typical public schools (Etikan et al., 2016). Second, the time allocated for this study is limited to three months (twelve weeks in total). Finally, the people in the study are two EFL teachers from the selected schools. In short, this study was conducted with two EFL teachers in two different school settings: a private and a public school from a relatively high socioeconomic neighborhood in Istanbul. The participant teachers were interviewed, and their lessons were observed for the current research purposes. Below is given detailed information about each school, the participant teachers, and the observed classes.

The private primary school was founded in 1991 and it is on the same campus with a secondary and a high school. There is one refectory, one computer laboratory, two guidance services, and an infirmary room in the building. In primary school, there are

students starting from kindergarten to fourth-grade students. Additionally, there are twelve classrooms with their own class teachers and 250 students. So, in each class, the number of students changes from 15 to 20. The lesson time devoted to each class is 35 minutes. The number of English teachers at the primary level is five (except kindergarten), with four of them particular to each class level (main course) and one for skills (mostly speaking) lessons.

The private school teacher studied English Language and Literature at Istanbul University and graduated in 2005. Then, she participated in a one-year pedagogical formation program including an internship, which is compulsory in Turkey to get employed as a teacher. She has 16 years of teaching experience in total and has been teaching in the same school since her graduation. She taught in kindergarten for 10 years and since 2016 she has been working at the primary level. In the 2021-2022 educational year, she taught only the second graders in three sections for eighteen hours per week. Thus, she was teaching the “*Main Course*” for six hours in each section.

Two sections from her second-grade classes were observed for the purposes of this study. The second graders had eight hours of English instruction in total: six hours of *main course* English and two hours of *skills* classes which were mostly based on speaking skills. While the number of students was eighteen in one section, there were fifteen students in the other one. All the students were nine years old. Since students in private schools are generally exposed to their foreign language starting from the kindergarten level, the majority of the students in the observed classes were already familiar with the language and its basic use.

On the other hand, the public school of the study was founded in 1963 and the building was renewed in 2010. There were eighteen classrooms, one conference hall, one gym, one refectory, one guidance service, one branch meeting room, one kindergarten, one laboratory, one special education class, and an infirmary in the school. There were 510 students at the primary level, 17 class teachers, and two English teachers. One of the English teachers was not tenured but was employed as an hourly-paid instructor. The school had been educating kids from kindergarten up until the fourth grade since the adoption of the 4+4+4 educational system. The average class size was 30 at this school.

English was taught starting from the second grade for two hours a week which means third and fourth-grade students also took English classes for two hours per week. The lessons in the school lasted 40 minutes.

The public school teacher graduated from Bursa College of Foreign Languages in 1984 and completed a pedagogical formation program with an internship at another university. She had 37 years of experience in total and taught various age groups including adults, and high school, secondary, and primary school students throughout her professional career. Although the teacher had been working in the same school since 1994, she had only been teaching at the primary level since 2013. During the 2021-2022 educational year, she taught nine sections from second and third grades and she had two hours of instruction with each section making up eighteen hours of teaching load per week.

One section from the second grade she was teaching was observed within the scope of this study. In that class, there were twenty-seven students who were also nine years old. That is, this group was almost twice as crowded as the one at the private school. In addition, most of the students in this group were introduced to English as a foreign language for the first time that year based on the national curriculum for the English language published by the Ministry of National Education.

3.3 Data Collection Instruments

Researchers conducting case studies collect qualitative data in different ways such as through observations, interviews, reports, and documents or audiovisual materials. In this study, the qualitative data were collected via COLT observation schemes developed by Spada and Fröhlich (1995), field notes taken during the observations, and the interviews conducted with the two participant teachers separately. Below is given a detailed introduction for each instrument.

3.3.1 COLT (Communicative Orientation of Language Teaching) Observation Scheme

First, the participant EFL teachers' lessons were observed for twelve weeks, and field notes were taken during the observations, which were later used to fill in the COLT

observation schemes. The observation was a non-participant one, with the researcher sitting at the back of the classroom without intervening in what was happening at the time. **COLT** is the abbreviation of the Communicative Orientation of Language Teaching Observation Scheme. It was developed by Spada and Fröhlich in 1995 to observe learning and teaching activities in foreign language classes. It consists of two parts, including A and B, but only part A was used in this study. **COLT Part A** indicates the activities in the lessons by focusing on seven parameters: time, activities and episodes, participant organization, content, content control, student modality, and materials. Below are given the explanations by Spada and Fröhlich (1995) for each parameter.

- **Time:** This parameter refers to the duration of each activity performed in the lesson. This is significant since it is helpful to determine the amount of time allocated for communicative aspects of foreign language instruction. This takes up the first column in the observation scheme. The exact hour and the minutes in which the activities take place are noted under the first column.
- **Activities and episodes:** Activities and episodes are different instructional sections of a lesson in the sense that one activity can involve a few episodes. As an example, an activity can be a game or drill while the episodes are the steps of that activity such as *the introduction of dialogue, the teacher reads the dialogue, students repeat the dialogue, and the students read the dialogue aloud*. This parameter is coded under the second column in the scheme. In this column, the activities and episodes should be written clearly enough so that the people who do not exist during the observations can reconstruct them later on if they want. For instance, it should be obvious which *episode* belongs to which *activity* as in the example: AI, EI; AI, EII, AII, EI, etc. This column shows us the general outline of the lessons, and so their relationship with the use of CLT, which makes it important for the researchers.
- **Participant organization:** Participant organization refers to the organization of the students in the classroom and there can be three ways of it: *class, group, and individual*. Thus, the students can participate in the lessons as a whole class, in groups, or individually. The organization of the students gives an idea about the use of CLT

because pair and group work are widely used in this approach. This parameter is coded under columns from 3 to 9 as follows.

- **Class:** This category covers the columns 3,4 and 5. First, *T-S/C* is coded if the teacher is leading the activities in the class such as standing in front of the students and explaining something. Second, *S-S/C* is coded if the interaction is between the students or between a student and the whole class. Third, if, for instance, the students repeat after the teacher or answer the teacher's questions altogether, *choral* is coded.
 - **Group:** This category covers the columns 6 and 7. If the students work in pairs or groups to complete the same task *Group Same Task* is coded whereas if groups work on different tasks, *Group Different Tasks* is coded.
 - **Individual:** This category covers the columns 8 and 9. If the individual students work on the same task *Individual Same Task* is coded whereas if they each work on different tasks, *Individual Different Tasks* is coded.
- **Content:** Content basically refers to the topic of the lessons that the students are engaged in by reading, writing, listening to, or speaking. It can be about managerial issues, language/structure, or other topics. Because this section shows the nature of the activities, it is quite important for the researchers to investigate the situation of CLT in the classes. This parameter is coded under the columns from 10 to 17 based on three main subcategories as follows:
 - **Management:** This category covers the columns 10 and 11. The expressions related to *procedure* and *discipline* are coded here if they last more than one minute. Procedure refers to the directives of the teacher such as '*Open your books.*' while discipline is more about statements referring to the discipline of the class such as '*I am getting annoyed due to the noise in this class.*'
 - **Language:** This category covers the columns 12, 13, 14, and 15. The activities about language such as *form*, *function*, *discourse*, and *sociolinguistics* are coded under the relevant column. First, form refers to activities involving grammar, vocabulary, or pronunciation. Second, function refers to the

functions of the language such as requesting or inviting. Third, discourse is about combining the cohesion and coherence between the sentences to describe a process such as planting herbs. Last, sociolinguistics refers to the appropriate use of language in certain situations such as the use of language at a funeral.

- **Other Topics:** This category covers the columns 16 and 17. If the content is related to the students' immediate environment such as school and/or family, it is coded as *narrow*, but if it is about more general or international issues *broad* is coded.
- **Content Control:** This parameter is about the authority figure deciding the topic of the lessons, which may be the teacher or the text, the teacher/text/student together, or the students on their own. This parameter is coded under the columns from 18 to 20 and the coding is done accordingly for *the teacher or the text*, *the students*, or *the teacher/text and students*, if determined by all of them together. Because the control of the students is also expected in CLT use, this column bears importance for understanding the link between the lessons and the approach itself (CLT).
- **Student modality:** This parameter shows the skills that the students are engaged in such as listening, reading, speaking and other (TPR activities, drawing, acting, etc.) while doing the activities. A combination of skills is also possible according to the scheme. This parameter is coded under the columns 21 to 25. The coding is done according to the students' modalities or the activities they are busy with such as *listening*, *speaking*, *reading*, *writing* and *other*. For this age group involved in this study, *writing* means writing individual letters, and words or completing sentences as well as writing or copying quite short sentences. *Other* means clapping their hands, stomping their feet, drawing, coloring, or doing other TPR actions. Multiple coding is more common in this section because one activity may require different skills. For example, if the students answered the questions of the teacher, both *listening* and *speaking* were coded because to be able to answer the question they should listen to the teacher. Similarly, *listening* and *other* were coded if the students did what the

teacher said such as ‘stand up’ and ‘turn right’. In terms of the use of CLT, different modalities are expected to be seen throughout the lessons and not just the receptive skills such as listening and reading.

- **Materials:** This parameter aims to describe the classroom materials used in a lesson regarding their types and sources. Because authentic materials are quite essential in CLT, this column is important. This parameter is coded under the columns from 26 to 33 based on two sub-categories as follows:
 - **Type:** This category covers the columns 26, 27, 28, and 29 and shows if the material is *text* (either minimal or extended), *audio* or *visual*. *Text* has two types that are minimal and extended. *Minimal text* includes captions, isolated sentences, and words/word lists. On the other hand, *extended text* means paragraphs, linked sentences, stories, or dialogues. *Audio* is any recorded material used for listening activities in class. *Visuals* are simply pictures or posters.
 - **Source:** This category covers columns 30, 31, 32, and 33. *Source* refers to for whom those materials are designed, and the scheme offers four options: *L2-NNS*, *L2-NS*, *L2-NSA*, and *Student-made*. That is, this subcategory questions whether the material is originally created for non-native speaker L2 learners (non-authentic), for native speakers (authentic), or designed for the L1 speakers and then adapted for the L2 learners. Lastly, *student-made* indicates that the materials are created by the students themselves.

3.3.2 Semi-Structured Interview Form

The second data collection tool in this study was a semi-structured interview form. The questions in the form were prepared based on the related literature regarding the perceptions of teachers about CLT as well as the parameters highlighted in the COLT observation scheme. The draft interview form was shared with three experts in the field (a professor, an assistant professor, and a research assistant specialized in ELT) and two EFL teachers working with young learners for feedback. The form was revised based on

their feedback and comments and the final interview form was prepared accordingly. The language of the interview was chosen as Turkish so that the teachers can feel secure and competent during the conversation and explain themselves without any restrictions. Additionally, the interview form includes nine main questions with eleven drilling questions in total under seven of them (see Appendix 4).

3.4 Data Collection Procedure

As stated above, the data of the study were collected in two ways: observations and interviews. Prior to the data collection, the ethical approval was obtained from the Istanbul Medeniyet University Faculty of Educational Sciences Ethical Committee and official permissions were taken from the Provincial Directorate for National Education in Istanbul. In addition, the participant teachers were informed about the study with a written document under which they gave their consent for voluntary participation.

3.4.1 Lesson Observations

The participant EFL teachers' lessons were observed for twelve weeks, and field notes were taken during the observations, which were later used to fill in the COLT observation schemes. The observation was a non-participant one, with the researcher sitting at the back of the classroom without intervening in what was happening at the time. Table 1 summarizes the procedure for lesson observations in both contexts.

Table 1. Lesson Observation Procedure

Setting	Number of Sections Observed	Class Size	Duration	Mode
Private School	2	18 / 15	12 weeks (6 for each section)	11 weeks in person 1 week online
Public School	1	27	12 weeks	12 weeks in person

As can be seen in Table 1, in the private school, two different second-grade sections instructed by the same teacher were observed equally: six lessons for each group according to the convenience of the researcher at the time. While the number of students in one section was eighteen, there were fifteen students in the other group. Although eleven lessons were observed in person in the real classroom at the time of teaching, one of them was an online lesson because of the pandemic; so, the observer participated in the zoom session to complete the scheme. On the other hand, in the public school, one section of the second-grade classes with 27 kids was observed for twelve weeks, which were all conducted in person.

During the observations, the researcher took field notes and noted down everything that took place in the lesson with the exact timing. Right after each observation, the columns for *time* and *activities and episodes* were completed by the observer based on her notes and fresh memory. Then, the observer had a meeting with the other researcher to discuss and determine the activities and episodes properly. Once a mutual agreement was achieved, both researchers did the coding separately in order to compare and see the amount of consistency and/or discrepancies between their coding in another meeting. All the coding is done according to the COLT A coding conventions described for the seven major categories by Spada and Fröhlich (1995) and as explained in the *Data Collection Instruments* section above. As it is possible to mark multiple columns, researchers also showed which ones were primary by circling or coloring the coding.

3.4.2 Interviews with the EFL Teachers

After the observations and the coding of COLT schemes were completed, the researcher scheduled a day with each participant teacher separately in a place and time convenient to them. Thus, an online zoom session was held with the private school teacher and a meeting outside the school was held with the public school teacher. The interviews were semi-structured; therefore, the researcher asked the questions in the interview form and used the follow-up questions if the answers were not explanatory enough. Additionally, the teachers were free to talk more about their experiences and opinions.

With the consent of the teachers, the interviews were recorded with a voice recorder. Each interview took approximately one hour.

3.5 Data Analysis

After completing the data collection period, the researchers analyzed the data to demonstrate the overall picture in a clearer way and to comment on it. Hence, first of all, the COLT observation schemes were analyzed, and the calculations were done accordingly. Second, the interviews were analyzed using transcriptions, and the key points were covered under the related headings below.

3.5.1 Analysis of the COLT Observation Data

The analysis of the COLT observation data requires the calculation of the time allocated for each category under the main parameters. The COLT schemes filled in for each lesson were analyzed for this purpose. First, the time spent for each category was calculated by looking at the starting and ending times of the activities and episodes through a simple subtraction. Second, the ratios were calculated as percentages compared to the entire time of the observation. Only the primary focuses were included in the calculations to show the categories that became prominent in the lessons. So, the marks or ticks without the primary focus were excluded from the calculations. If there was more than one primary focus, it was calculated accordingly, and the multiple categories were combined into a new category such as *audiovisual*. Then, for each school, the categories were tabularized to indicate the actual time devoted to each subcategory and their percentages within the overall observed instruction. In addition, the percentages were also shown in pie charts to visualize the comparison of the two contexts clearly.

3.5.2 Analysis of the Interview Data

A descriptive analysis was conducted using the participant teachers' interview data, which is defined as the descriptive summary of data components in a logically arranged manner and appealing to the reader (Lambert & Lambert, 2012). First, the recordings of the two interviews were transcribed. Then, the significant opinions and statements

regarding the use of CLT were determined and highlighted from the teachers' responses in the transcriptions. Finally, the findings were reported holistically based on the similar and different perspectives found in those transcriptions to be able to compare the teachers' views on the issue. In addition, related quotations were provided under suitable headings to support the findings with the teachers' own words.

3.6 Validity and Reliability of the Study

Validity is generally defined as the appropriateness and usefulness of the assumptions or interpretations that the researchers made based on their collected data (Fraenkel et. al., 2012). The researchers of the current study thus aimed to ensure the validity of the study by collecting their data from several different sources to have *triangulation* in their study, as explained in detail in the data collection section above. In addition, by making the observation period long enough (three months), *prolonged involvement* was established. Moreover, during the analysis, the researchers were in contact with the participant teachers and asked some questions repeatedly about the unclarified points to be sure of the results; so, *member checking/respondent validation* was enabled with the help of this process.

Furthermore, because the COLT A schemes were coded by the two researchers separately, thus having *multiple coding* for the study; the researchers aimed to have *inter-rater reliability* and compared their codings later on with the calculation which was defined by Miles and Huberman (1994: 64) as follows:

$$\text{reliability} = \frac{\text{number of agreements}}{\text{total number of agreements + disagreements}}$$

Table 2. Inter-Rater Reliability Degree for Both Schools

Number of Lessons	Public School Reliability	Private School Reliability
Lesson 1	.83	.86
Lesson 2	.62	.87

Lesson 3	.78	.80
Lesson 4	.86	.91
Lesson 5	.90	.87
Lesson 6	.87	.95
Lesson 7	.72	.85
Lesson 8	.86	.82
Lesson 9	.90	.80
Lesson 10	.77	.86
Lesson 11	.83	.86
Lesson 12	.90	.84
Total	.82	.86

So, the researchers applied this formula for each COLT A document (24 in total, 12 for each school). Table 2 shows that they attained a reliability degree of .82 for the public school (968/1171) and .86 for the private school (652/756). Hence, the overall reliability degree, including both schools and 24 lessons, is .84. At first, the value was not more than .70, but it got closer to .90 after the reconciliation of the researchers about the codings. Therefore, the study has high inter-rater reliability (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

4. FINDINGS

This section presents the findings of the data analysis. First, the results gathered both from the COLT observation schemes of 24 lessons (12 for each school) are given. Then, the findings from the interviews conducted with the private school and the public school teachers are presented.

4.1 Findings from the COLT Observation Schemes

The data obtained from the observations (12 lessons for each school) were grouped into five main categories according to the COLT observation schemes. Thus, the findings regarding *participant organization*, *content*, *content control*, *student modality*, and *materials (type and source)* are provided in this section.

4.1.1 Findings Regarding the Participant Organization

The first category in the observation scheme is related to “participant organization”. A comparison of the EFL classes at the private and state schools regarding this category is presented after they are explained separately for each school first. Accordingly, Table 3 below provides the results of the organization of the EFL learners during the observed classes in the private school.

Table 3. Participant Organization for the Private School

		PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION													
		Class				Group				Individual					
Private School		T- S/C		S-S/C		Choral		Same task		Different tasks		Same task		Different tasks	
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%
1	29	24	82.8	4	13.8	-	0	-	0	-	0	1	3.4	-	0
2	29	18	62.1	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	11	37.9	-	0
3	33	29	87.9	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	4	12.1	-	0
4	33	10	30.3	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	20	60.6	3	9.1

5	30	6	20	23	76.7	1	3.3	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
6	31	19	61.3	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	12	38.7	-	0
7	30	30	100	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
8	26	13	50	-	0	5	19.2	-	0	-	0	8	30.8	-	0
9	33	33	100	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
10	35	22	62.9	-	0	3	8.6	6	17.1	-	0	4	11.4	-	0
11	32	17	53.1	6	18.8	1	3.1	-	0	-	0	8	25.0	-	0
12	33	9	27.3	16	48.5	3	9.1	-	0	-	0	5	15.2	-	0
Total	374	230	61.5	49	13.1	13	3.5	6	1.6	0	0	73	19.5	3	0.8

As can be seen in Table 3, in the private school, the observed lessons predominantly included whole class activities whereas there were fewer individual and group work tasks as well. First, 61.5 % of the class time was spent with teacher-initiated activities which allow for *teacher-to-student* or *teacher-to-class* interaction. In addition, the time allocated for the *student-to-student* or *student-to-class* interaction makes up 13.1% of the class time which was mostly in the form of role-plays whereas only 3.5% of the instruction was spent on *choral work* for which the students repeated after the teacher or audio. The second most dominant participation organization is individual activities which take up a very small portion of the class time when compared to the whole class activities. When the percentages in Table 3 are considered, it is understood that the students spent 19.5% of their time working *individually on the same task* while only 0.8% of the class time was allocated for *individual work on different tasks*. Third, the least observed participation organization was *group work* activities. That is, the students worked in groups on the same task only once which takes up only 1.6% of their class time. Finally, Table 3 shows that a considerable amount of the class time was allocated for the teacher-to-student or class interaction (f=12) and individual work on the same task (f=9) in almost every lesson whereas the tasks which require student-to-student or student-to-class interaction (f=4), or choral work (f=5) were pretty infrequent. What is more, the activities which require individual work on different tasks or group work on the same task

were observed only in one lesson while the students never worked in groups for different tasks throughout the observations.

Likewise, Table 4 summarizes the findings regarding the participant organization in the observed classes at the public school. In addition, detailed explanations are made below the table.

Table 4. Participant Organization for the Public School

		PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION													
		Class				Group				Individual					
Public School		T- S/C		S-S/C		Choral		Same task		Different tasks		Same task		Different tasks	
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%
1	35	29	82.9	-	0	3	8.6	-	0	-	0	3	8.6	-	0
2	32	9	28.1	6	17.6	8	23.5	-	0	-	0	9	28.1	-	0
3	38	13	34.2	4	10.5	1	2.6	-	0	-	0	20	52.6	-	0
4	35	22	62.9	-	0	7	19.4	-	0	-	0	6	17.1	-	0
5	34	25	73.5	-	0	2	5.9	-	0	-	0	7	20.6	-	0
6	29	5	17.2	-	0	18	50	-	0	-	0	6	20.7	-	0
7	35	35	100	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
8	34	30	88.2	2	5.9	2	5.9	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
9	33	17	51.5	-	0	9	35.1	-	0	-	0	7	21.2	-	0
10	36	14	38.9	3	8.3	1	2.8	-	0	-	0	18	50	-	0
11	32	21	65.6	-	0	2	5.9	-	0	-	0	9	28.1	-	0
12	35	29	82.9	6	17.1	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
Total	408	249	61.0	21	5.1	53	13	0	0	0	0	85	20.8	0	0

Table 4 shows that most of the EFL teaching in the public school was organized as *class* activities while there were a few *individual* tasks as well. However, no *group work* was conducted in any of the observed lessons. First, the learners in this group spent

most of their class time on *class* activities that allow for the *teacher-to-student* or *teacher-to-class* interaction (61%) while very little time was devoted to *choral work* (13%) and *student-to-student/class* interaction (5.1%). This shows that the observed EFL lessons at this school were almost always led by the teacher. Second, the students spent 20.8% of their class time on a common *individual work*; that is, they never worked on different tasks individually. Third, the students never worked in pairs or groups for any of the EFL activities in the observed lessons. Considering the weekly distribution of the participant organizations, it is possible to say that in every lesson the teacher interacted with individual students or the whole class (f=12) and that almost every lesson included choral work (f=10) and individual tasks (f=9) although the devoted time was relatively much shorter. Finally, the activities promoting *student-to-student* interaction were a lot less frequent (f=5).

Furthermore, the figure below has been prepared to display the similarities and differences in the participant organization in the two observed EFL contexts. Figure 1 shows the pie charts for each school with the percentages for all the participant organization types allowing for a comparison.

Figure 1. A Comparison of Private and Public Schools Regarding Participant Organization

The pie charts above help to compare the observed EFL lessons in both schools regarding the distribution of the participant organization. As seen in the charts, the two EFL classes have a similar pattern in general for participant organization. First, the teacher-initiated interaction is obviously dominant taking up more than half of the class time both at the private school (61.5%) and the public school (61%). Similarly, the second most prominent type is the one in which students work individually on the same task in both schools with very close percentages like 19.5% and 20.8% for the public and private schools respectively. On the other hand, it is seen that the EFL lessons are different from each other when it comes to the third dominant organization. That is, 13.1% of the class time was spent with *student-to-student/class* (S-S/C) interactions in the private school while almost the same proportion of the class time was allocated for the *choral work* in the public school (13.4%). Consequently, choral work is one of the least observed patterns in the private school (3.4%) whereas it is *student-to-student/class* (S-S/C) interactions in the public school (5.1%). Finally, the activities in which the students worked as a group

on the same task (1.6%) and individually on different tasks (0.8%) were observed rarely in the EFL lessons at the private school whereas they were not detected at all at the public school.

4.1.2 Findings Regarding the Content

The second category in the observation scheme is related to “content”. First, the explanations are made for each school; and then, their comparison concerning the same category is provided. Hence, Table 5 below shows the results of the content of the observed lessons in the private school.

Table 5. Content for the Private School

Private School	CONTENT																
	Management				Language								Other topics				
	Procedure		Discipline		Form		Function		Discourse		Socioling.		Narrow		Broad		
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%
1	29	6	20.7	7	24.1	16	55.2	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
2	29	6	20.7	1	3.4	22	75.9	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
3	33	6	18.2	6	18.2	20	60.6	-	0	-	0	-	0	1	3	-	0
4	33	4	12.1	4	12.1	25	75.8	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
5	30	3	10	3	10	24	80	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
6	31	5	16.1	7	22.6	19	61.3	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
7	30	19	63.3	7	23.3	4	13.3	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
8	26	-	0	9	34.6	16	61.5	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	1	3.8
9	33	4	12.1	-	0	24	72.7	5	15.2	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
10	35	17	48.6	3	8.6	15	42.9	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
11	32	2	6.3	5	15.6	17	53.1	-	0	-	0	-	0	8	25	-	0
12	33	7	21.2	7	21.2	19	57.6	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
Total	374	79	21.1	59	15.8	221	59.1	5	1.3	0	0	0	0	9	2.4	1	0.3

With respect to the content of the lessons, it is seen that the lessons were mostly based on *language* (60.4%), which was followed by *management* (36.9%) and *other topics* (2.7%) respectively. First, under *language*, *form* was the most dominant category (59.1%), often referring to vocabulary activities. The students worked on grammar and pronunciation briefly in some lessons as well. On the other hand, *functions* of the language were realized 1.3% of the time (f=1) in the observed lessons. *Discourse* or *sociolinguistics* never became the content of the lessons during the observations. Second, the issues related to *procedure* (21.1%) and *discipline* (15.8%) cover 36.9% of the observed time in the private school. This shows that *managerial* topics were the second most observed content in the EFL lessons. Last, *other topics* about *narrow* -familiar topics related to school, personal information, everyday/family life, routines or so- (2.4 %) and *broad* - topics with broader references such as international or imaginary events, instruction about some other subjects including science or geography- (0.3 %) were hardly seen throughout the observed lessons, as can be seen in Table 5.

Similarly, Table 6 demonstrates the findings regarding the content of the observed lessons at the public school. Further descriptions are made below the table, as well.

Table 6. Content for the Public School

Public School	CONTENT																
	Management				Language				Other topics								
	Procedure		Discipline		Form		Function		Discourse		Socioling.		Narrow		Broad		
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%
1	35	-	0	-	0	35	100	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
2	32	-	0	-	0	8	25	24	75	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
3	38	3	7.9	3	7.9	6	15.8	26	68.4	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
4	35	2	5.7	-	0	33	94.3	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
5	34	4	11.8	-	0	30	88.2	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
6	29	1	3.4	-	0	28	96.6	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
7	35	9	25.7	3	8.6	23	65.7	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0

8	34	3	8.8	-	0	31	91.2	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
9	33	-	0	6	18.2	27	81.8	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
10	36	-	0	3	8.3	29	80.6	-	0	-	0	-	0	4	11.1	-	0
11	32	6	18.8	-	0	23	71.9	1	3.1	2	6.3	-	0	-	0	-	0
12	35	2	5.7	7	20	26	74.3	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0
Total	408	30	7.4	22	5.4	299	73.3	51	12.5	2	0.5	0	0	4	1	0	0

Table 6 shows that in the public school, the content was primarily constructed by the topics related to *language* (85.8%). *Form* (vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation activities) was the most dominant theme during the observed lessons with 73.3%. Issues concerning the *functions* of language also occupied 12.5% of the time while the content about *discourse* was only seen 0.5% of the time. However, this class never engaged in a topic from *sociolinguistics*. Secondly, issues related to classroom management like *procedure* (7.4%) and *discipline* (5.4%) constituted the second most observed content in the lessons (12.8%). Lastly, *other topics* were only seen 1% of the time. In addition, this very limited time was devoted to *narrow* topics whereas no activity covering *broad* topics was observed in this group. One significant thing worth mentioning here is that language form became the topic in every observed lesson (f=12) whereas the topics related to procedure and discipline were relatively less frequent. Additionally, the frequency of the topics concerning language functions (f=3), discourse (f=1), and other topics (f=1) was very low when compared to the total lesson observations.

Furthermore, Figure 2 below demonstrates the similarities and differences regarding the content with the help of percentages in the two observed EFL contexts.

Figure 2. A Comparison of Private and Public Schools Regarding Content

As depicted in Figure 2, *language* (form, function, discourse) was the most prioritized content both in private (60.4%) and in the public school (85.8%). However, it is obvious that there is more emphasis on language in the public school. In addition, it is mainly constituted by vocabulary, pronunciation, and some grammar activities respectively. While the topics related to the function of the language were covered 1.3% of the time in the private school, it was 12.5% in the public school. Therefore, the EFL lessons in the public school focused relatively more on language functions. The time spent on discourse was very limited, only 0.5% of the total observed time in the public school, while it was not observed in the private school at all. *Management* (procedure and discipline) was the second most prominent content in both schools; however, the percentage is quite low in the public school (12.8%) when compared to the private school (36.9%). Lastly, *other topics* (narrow and broad) constituted the least observed content in both schools. While narrow topics were observed in both schools with very low percentages, broad topics were not detected in the public school, and it was only seen 0.3% of the time in the private school.

4.1.3 Findings Regarding the Content Control

The third category in the observation scheme is “content control”. After the details about this category are provided for both the private and the public schools separately, a comparison of them is given, as well. Table 7 below presents the results regarding the content control for the private school.

Table 7. Content Control for the Private School

Private School		CONTENT CONTROL					
		Teacher/text		Teacher / text / student		Student	
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%
1	29	29	100	-	0	-	0
2	29	29	100	-	0	-	0
3	33	33	100	-	0	-	0
4	33	33	100	-	0	-	0
5	30	30	100	-	0	-	0
6	31	31	100	-	0	-	0
7	30	30	100	-	0	-	0
8	26	26	100	-	0	-	0
9	33	33	100	-	0	-	0
10	35	35	100	-	0	-	0
11	32	32	100	-	0	-	0
12	33	33	100	-	0	-	0
Total	374	374	100	0	0	0	0

As shown in Table 7, it was always *the teacher* or *the text* (textbook) that controlled the content of the lessons in the private school (100%). On the other hand, the students never had an impact on the choice of topics or content in any of the observed lessons. The teacher never let the students determine the content of the lesson on their own either. Thus, it is obvious that the content was controlled only by the primary textbook of the course or the teacher herself.

Table 8 below likewise shows the findings concerning content control in the observed classes at the public school. Additionally, further information is provided below the table.

Table 8. Content Control for the Public School

Public School		CONTENT CONTROL					
		Teacher/text		Teacher / text / student		Student	
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%
1	35	35	100	-	0	-	0
2	32	32	100	-	0	-	0
3	38	38	100	-	0	-	0
4	35	35	100	-	0	-	0
5	34	34	100	-	0	-	0
6	29	29	100	-	0	-	0
7	35	35	100	-	0	-	0
8	34	34	100	-	0	-	0
9	33	33	100	-	0	-	0
10	36	36	100	-	0	-	0
11	32	32	100	-	0	-	0
12	35	35	100	-	0	-	0
Total	408	408	100	0	0	0	0

As shown in Table 8, the same pattern concerning content control emerged in the public school. That is, the content of the lesson was determined by *the teacher* or *the text* (textbook) all the time with no contribution from the students in all the observed classes at the public school. The students did not have partial or total freedom to determine the topic of their EFL classes.

Additionally, the comparison of the content control in the two observed EFL settings is shown in the figure below. The pie charts for each school are displayed in Figure 3 together with the percentages for the content control type to enable a comparison.

Figure 3. A Comparison of Private and Public Schools Regarding Content Control

As Figure 3 demonstrates, the observed EFL lessons have exactly the same pattern in terms of content control. What would be covered in L2 lessons was always determined by the teacher or the text in both schools. In other words, the students neither in the private nor in the public school had a word in determining the topic of their English lessons.

4.1.4 Findings Regarding the Student Modality

The fourth category in the observation scheme concerns “student modality”. First, the explanations pertaining to this category are given distinctly for each EFL context observed. Then, a comparison of them is given so that the similarities and differences between them would be clear to the reader. Table 9 thus illustrates the results related to modalities of the EFL learners in the private school.

Table 9. Student Modality for the Private School

		STUDENT MODALITY															
Private School		Listening		Speaking		Listening & Speaking		Reading		Writing		Reading & Writing		Other		Listening & Other	
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%

1	29	13	44.8	-	0	4	13.8	-	0	2	6.9	-	0	6	20.7	4	13.8
2	29	20	69.0	-	0	-	0	5	17.2	-	0	-	0	2	6.9	2	6.9
3	33	15	45.5	-	0	3	9.1	-	0	-	0	-	0	4	12.1	11	33.3
4	33	10	30.3	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	20	60.6	3	9.1
5	30	3	10	-	0	1	3.3	-	0	-	0	-	0	23	76.7	3	10
6	31	12	38.7	-	0	7	22.6	6	19.4	-	0	6	23.1	-	0	-	0
7	30	3	10	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	27	90
8	26	3	11.5	-	0	11	42.3	-	0	5	19.2	-	0	1	3.8	6	23.1
9	33	4	12.1	-	0	19	57.6	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	10	30.3
10	35	9	25.7	-	0	4	11.4	-	0	-	0	-	0	6	17.1	16	45.7
11	32	13	40.6	-	0	12	37.5	-	0	7	21.9	-	0	-	0	-	0
12	33	2	6.1	-	0	7	21.2	-	0	-	0	-	0	21	63.6	3	9.1
Total	374	107	28.6	0	0	68	18.2	11	2.9	14	3.7	6	1.6	83	22.2	85	22.7

As Table 9 depicts, there is a variety in terms of student modality in the private school. First, the most dominant modality is *listening* because the students spent 28.6% of the observed lessons by listening to their teacher, audio, or a song. Second, the students were engaged in *listening & other* activities for 22.7% of the class time. Hence, the students were listening to their teacher and then respond to her by doing things. *Other* is the third dominant modality since the student did clapping, cutting, counting, circling, drawing, or coloring for 22.2% of the observed time. Fourth, the students were busy with *listening & speaking* activities for 18.2% of their class time, for which they interacted with their teacher or their peers or repeated after the teacher or an audio. Finally, the least observed modalities were *writing* (3.7 %), *reading* (2.9 %), and *reading & writing* (1.6 %) respectively. *Speaking* was not observed at all on its own except for in a combination with listening.

The results of the student modality in the public school lessons are also reported in Table 10. Additionally, thorough explanations are provided below the table.

Table 10. Student Modality for the Public School

STUDENT MODALITY																	
Public School		Listening		Speaking		Listening & Speaking		Reading		Writing		Reading & Writing		Other		Listening & Other	
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%
1	35	18	51.4	-	0	3	8.6	-	0	14	40	-	0	-	0	-	0
2	32	16	50	-	0	9	28.1	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	7	21.9
3	38	32	84.2	-	0	1	2.6	2	5.3	3	7.9	-	0	-	0	-	0
4	35	19	54.3	1	2.9	1	2.9	-	0	-	0	-	0	3	8.6	11	31.4
5	34	7	20.6	-	0	2	5.9	-	0	-	0	15	44.1	3	8.8	7	20.6
6	29	4	13.8	-	0	19	65.5	-	0	2	6.9	-	0	8	27.6	4	13.8
7	35	14	40	-	0	7	20	-	0	-	0	-	0	14	40	-	0
8	34	4	11.8	-	0	13	38.2	-	0	15	44.1	-	0	-	0	2	5.9
9	33	6	18.2	-	0	24	72.7	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	3	9.1
10	36	3	8.3	-	0	15	41.7	-	0	18	50	-	0	-	0	-	0
11	32	11	34.4	-	0	6	18.8	-	0	10	31.3	-	0	-	0	5	15.6
12	35	4	11.4	-	0	10	28.6	-	0	17	48.6	-	0	-	0	4	11.4
Total	408	138	33.8	1	0.2	110	27	2	0.5	79	19.4	15	3.7	28	6.9	43	10.5

As shown in Table 10, a similar variety emerged regarding the student modality in the public school. First, the most dominant modality is also *listening* in the public school since the students spent 33.8% of their class time listening to their teacher, a song, or audio. The second dominant modality is *listening & speaking* since the students spent 27% of the observed classes with activities frequently in the form of choral work/repetition or answering the teacher's questions. Third, they were engaged with *writing* for 19.4% of the observed class time. The fourth frequent modality in the public school is *listening & other* because the students spent 10.5% of their time acting, cutting or coloring as they were listening to the teacher, audio, or a song. This modality is followed by *other* activities for which the students did clapping, cutting, counting, circling, drawing, and coloring for 6.9% of the total observed classes. On the other hand, the time spent on *reading & writing* was highly limited making up 3.7% of the observed time. Finally, the students spent only

0.5% of their time on *reading* and only 0.2% on *speaking* independently. When considered from another perspective, it is also seen that the EFL students did some *listening*, *listening & speaking* in every lesson, and *listening & other* almost every week whereas they did *reading & writing* only once in the twelve observations but wrote something in 7 lessons out of 12.

Consequently, the comparison of student modality in the two observed EFL contexts is illustrated in the figure below. Figure 4 thus depicts the pie charts for each school along with the percentages for all student modality categories so that they can be compared.

Figure 4. A Comparison of Private and Public Schools Regarding Student Modality

As can be seen in Figure 4, the comparison of the student modality reveals a similar pattern for the observed EFL classes. First, it is understood that *listening* was the most dominant one among all the modalities in both schools with close percentages: 22.7% for the private and 33.8% for the public. Second, the students spent a significant amount of their time on *listening & speaking* or *listening & other* activities in both schools. Likewise, the time spent on *reading*, and *reading & writing* or *speaking* is very limited in both observed classes. However, the *other* activities allowing for non-linguistic communication were relatively more common in the private school (22.7%) whereas the students in the public school spent quite a lot of time on *writing* (19.4%) which was rare in the private school (3.7%).

4.1.5 Findings Regarding the Material Types

The last category in the observation scheme is seen as “material” under which *type* and *source* categories are also presented. After providing the details regarding material type for each observed EFL context, a comparison of them is given to see the distinction between them clearly. Table 11 hence demonstrates the results concerning to material type mostly used in the private school.

Table 11. Material Type for the Private School

Private School		MATERIAL											
		Type											
		Text				Text + Visual	Audio	Visual	Audio + Visual				
		Minimal		Extended									
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%
1	29	3	10.3	-	0	9	31	-	0	5	17.2	1	3.4
2	29	8	27.6	-	0	2	6.9	4	13.8	-	0	-	0
3	33	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	10	30.3	7	21.2
4	33	-	0	-	0	25	75.8	-	0	-	0	3	9.1
5	30	-	0	-	0	23	76.7	-	0	-	0	1	3.3
6	31	-	0	-	0	19	61.3	-	0	-	0	-	0

7	30	-	0	-	0	21	70	-	0	-	0	-	0
8	26	6	23.1	-	0	5	19.2	-	0	1	3.8	-	0
9	33	4	12.1	-	0	15	45.5	-	0	-	0	5	15.2
10	35	-	0	-	0	18	51.4	-	0	-	0	4	11.4
11	32	-	0	-	0	7	21.9	-	0	5	15.6	7	21.9
12	33	-	0	-	0	7	21.2	-	0	-	0	-	0
Total	374	21	5.6	0	0	151	40.4	4	1.1	21	5.6	28	7.5

As can be seen in Table 11, texts and visuals were given together most of the time in the activities in the private school which makes sense considering the needs of the age group. Therefore, the students used *texts with visuals* for 40.4% of their class time. In addition, the audios supported with visuals and thus *audiovisuals* were the second most common materials (%7.5) and used more when compared to the *audio* only (%1.1). Similarly, the *minimal texts* without any visuals and the use of *visuals* (without any text) were used equally in the total observed time (5.6%) whereas no *extended texts* were given to the EFL learners in this school. Finally, it is also understood that the students spent 41.1% of their class time without using any materials at all. For the material type used in the public school lessons, Table 12 summarizes the findings and further interpretations are offered below the table.

Table 12. Material Type for the Public School

Public School		MATERIAL											
		Type											
		Text				Text + Visual	Audio	Visual	Audio + Visual				
		Minimal	Extended										
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%
1	35	8	22.9	-	0	14	40	-	0	-	0	-	0
2	32	4	12.5	-	0	1	3.1	-	0	1	3.1	9	28.1
3	38	-	0	-	0	4	10.5	3	7.9	-	0	14	36.8
4	35	-	0	-	0	6	17.1	3	8.6	1	2.9	4	11.4
5	34	5	14.7	-	0	22	64.7	-	0	-	0	-	0

6	29	-	0	-	0	-	0	5	17.2	1	3.4	20	69
7	35	-	0	-	0	19	54.3	-	0	2	5.7	-	0
8	34	-	0	-	0	25	73.5	-	0	-	0	-	0
9	33	-	0	-	0	10	30.3	-	0	-	0	17	51.5
10	36	-	0	-	0	6	16.7	-	0	18	50	-	0
11	32	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	17	53.1	8	25
12	35	6	17.1	-	0	21	60	-	0	3	8.6	-	0
Total	408	23	5.6	0	0	128	31.4	11	2.7	43	10.5	72	17.6

As can be understood in Table 12, the EFL learners in the public school used similar materials to those used in the private school. First, it is understood that *texts with visuals* were used together most of the time (31.4%) making this type the dominant material in this context. The second most observed materials were *audiovisuals* with a percentage of 17.6. Third, the use of *visuals* was detected 10.5% of the time. Similar to the pattern in the private school, *minimal text* was used for 5.6% of the lessons whereas the use of *audio* (without visuals) was recognized only 2.7% of the time. Finally, the students were never exposed to *extended texts*, and they spent 32.2% of their observed class time without using any materials at all.

As a result, the comparison of the material type most regularly utilized in the two EFL contexts under observation is shown in Figure 5 below. That is, the figure provides the pie charts for each school along with the percentages for all material type categories.

Figure 5. A Comparison of Private and Public Schools Regarding Material Type

The comparison in Figure 5 shows that the EFL learners in both schools benefitted from similar types of materials in their L2 learning. First, it can be seen that *texts with visuals* have the highest percentages in both schools. That is, the most common material type in both EFL contexts is texts with visuals. Second, they used *minimal texts*, *audiovisuals*, *visuals*, and *audio* in both EFL classes with close percentages. Still, all these types of materials were used much less frequently when compared to *texts with visuals*. One final similarity between the two contexts regarding the material types is that during the observed EFL lessons, the students spent a significant amount of their time (41.1% in the private school and 32.2% in the public school) without using any materials at all.

4.1.6 Findings Regarding the Material Source

“Material source” is the last heading under the last category of material. Regarding this category, an explanation is provided for each EFL context. Later, their comparison is

given to demonstrate the extent to which they are similar or different. So, Table 13 below provides the results about the source of the material used in the private school.

Table 13. Material Source for the Private School

Private School		MATERIALS							
		Source							
		L2-NNS		L2-NS		L2-NSA		Student-Made	
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%
1	29	18	62.1	-	0	-	0	-	0
2	29	14	48.3	-	0	-	0	-	0
3	33	22	66.7	-	0	-	0	-	0
4	33	28	84.8	-	0	-	0	-	0
5	30	24	80	-	0	-	0	-	0
6	31	19	61.3	-	0	-	0	-	0
7	30	21	70	-	0	-	0	-	0
8	26	11	42.3	1	3.8	-	0	-	0
9	33	15	45.5	5	15.2	-	0	-	0
10	35	22	62.9	-	0	-	0	-	0
11	32	19	59.4	-	0	-	0	-	0
12	33	7	21.2	-	0	-	0	-	0
Total	374	220	58.8	6	1.6	0	0	0	0

As can be understood in Table 13, the EFL students in the private school used materials coming from almost a single source. When a material was used in their lessons, it was almost always the one designed to teach a second language to non-native speakers (L2-NNS). Therefore, they spent 58.8% of their class time with such unauthentic materials. The students in the private school spent only 1.6% of their time (f=2) with authentic materials (L2-NS) which were movies or songs designed for native speakers of

English. Moreover, the table shows that no materials adapted for the learners (L2-NSA) or made by the students themselves were used in the observed lessons.

Similar to Table 13, Table 14 presents the findings for the material source used in the public school lessons. Detailed explanations are provided under the table.

Table 14. Material Source for the Public School

Public School		MATERIALS							
		Source							
		L2-NNS		L2-NS		L2-NSA		Student-Made	
Lesson	Time (minutes)	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%	Time	%
1	35	22	62.9	-	0	-	0	-	0
2	32	18	56.3	-	0	-	0	-	0
3	38	21	55.3	-	0	-	0	-	0
4	35	14	40	-	0	-	0	-	0
5	34	26	76.5	-	0	-	0	-	0
6	29	26	89.7	-	0	-	0	-	0
7	35	21	60	-	0	-	0	-	0
8	34	27	79.4	-	0	-	0	-	0
9	33	27	81.8	-	0	-	0	-	0
10	36	24	66.7	-	0	-	0	-	0
11	32	25	78.1	-	0	-	0	-	0
12	35	24	68.6	-	0	-	0	6	17.1
Total	408	275	67.4	0	0	0	0	6	1.5

Table 14 shows that the students in the public school predominantly used the materials that were designed for L2 non-native speakers. That is, they spent 67.4% of their total class time with unauthentic materials which were prepared to teach an L2 to the non-natives. In addition, they were never exposed to authentic materials (L2-NS) produced for native speakers or any adapted ones (L2-NSA) during the observed lessons. However,

they used the materials they themselves produced (student-made) only once which covers only 1.5% of the observed time. Further, the pie charts shown in Figure 6 below are given to depict the distinction between two observed EFL contexts in terms of the source of the materials.

Figure 6. A Comparison of Private and Public Schools Regarding Material Source

The comparison of the private and public school EFL contexts regarding the sources of the materials reveals almost the same pattern. It is obvious from Figure 6 that the source was L2-NNS almost every time whenever a material was used both in the private school and in the public school. The only slight difference is that in the private school authentic materials were used for a very limited time whereas in the public school the learners were once observed using some student-made materials which were animal posters.

4.2 Findings from the Interview Data

The other data source of the current study was the interviews held with the participating teachers. The findings are classified into six main categories according to the mostly emerged patterns in the transcriptions of both interviews. The categories are listed as *objectives of L2 teaching, types of learning and teaching activities, role of instructional*

materials, learner and teacher roles, role of L1 use in L2 instruction, and perceptions of the communicative approach, respectively.

4.2.1 Objectives of L2 Teaching

The very first theme emerging from the interview data is related to the participant teachers' language teaching goals. First of all, both teachers aimed at developing positive perceptions and attitudes towards English and learning a foreign language as well as to create awareness and familiarity. For instance, the private-school teacher stated that she tried to facilitate the kids to discover the language on their own to make them love the language and language learning process. Also, she hoped to break down the prejudices against English that the kids brought from their families. She explained her perspective with the following words: *“Let them love me first. Academic studies will come later... Sometimes the really important thing is to love first and get rid of that prejudice. Now we call it opening an English folder in one's brain. Let them get that familiarity. The rest will come later.”* Likewise, for the public-school teacher, the primary goal in her L2 instruction was to make the children love the language and to familiarize them with the new language. That is why, she claimed to spend all her energy to be appealing to the children, using age-appropriate methods and so to teach in a way that the children liked and enjoyed.

The other common goals stated by both teachers were to develop vocabulary, listening, and speaking as well as to make them acquainted with L2 writing. The private school teacher stated that she covered the curriculum and vocabulary within the units by teaching some extra words since she expected the kids to use the language as a means of communication, comprehend the language and respond either verbally or non-verbally. In addition, she claimed to focus on listening and speaking in the first year with the first graders whereas she concentrated on writing letters and words in the second grade. Similarly, the public-school teacher said that her students were studying some vocabulary, learning how to write, and how to answer simple questions while covering the curriculum. She summarized her teaching objectives as follows: *“Now, for the second graders, the important thing is to make them love the language and to ensure that they learn English well from the basics.”*

As a difference in their language objectives, the private school teacher valued teaching grammar implicitly in context whereas the public-school teacher focused on grammar less in primary school and more in secondary school. In addition, she gave importance to pronunciation which was not mentioned by the private school teacher.

4.2.2 Types of Learning and Teaching Activities

The second theme emerging from the interview data is related to the learning and teaching activities implemented by the participant teachers. First, it is understood that both teachers were in favor of TPR-like (Total Physical Response) activities to teach English to this age group. The private school teacher found TPR tasks beneficial considering students with different learning styles (e.g., kinesthetic, visual, or auditory learners). In other words, she believed that she could design lessons in which all her students are active and can get exposed to visual and audio materials meeting the needs and expectations of learners with different learning styles. Consequently, she mentioned activities including drama, role-play, music, dancing, singing, and repeating with the rhythm as her favorites. Similarly, the public-school teacher believed that her students benefit from activities which address different senses. Therefore, she mentioned using the projector and making students listen to and sing songs in her lessons. On the other hand, she confessed that although she wanted to use game-like activities more in her lessons, there was not much time for them as she had to cover the book and the curriculum. Finally, both teachers referred to “pass the ball” in which the student throwing the ball asks the question while the one catching it answers as a popular activity in their lessons and which reflects their opinions about TPR-like activities in L2 instruction. The private school teacher briefly stated her opinion as follows: *“As a favorite activity, I can say ‘pass the ball’, which is a simple but quite an enjoyable one.”*

Second, it is understood that the participant teachers differed in their teaching regarding the extra activities they implemented. That is, the private school teacher claimed to be supporting her students with extra activities other than the ones in their coursebooks whereas the public-school teacher complained about the limited time to cover the intense curriculum and the coursebooks preventing her from using extra activities. Namely, the

private school teacher said that she always intended to add more activities, otherwise she would not be satisfied with her lessons. She gave an example from the extra authentic activities she used in her lessons as follows: *“In the food topic, we did a Sandwich Shop activity in which the students sold sandwiches to their friends.”* On the other hand, the public-school teacher explained her reasons for not using additional activities in her lessons with the following words: *“Since I am meticulous in every job, I do not want children to go on without learning. Of course, teaching in one way tires me a lot. Talking all the time, being on the move... That's why we don't have many opportunities to play... Actually, because time is limited... But you can do these while working in a private school. When your lesson time is eight hours, you do it much better.”*

Finally, the third issue regarding the learning and teaching activities reveals that the participant teachers had different perspectives for their use of pair and group work. That is, the private school teacher stated prioritizing those activities whereas the public school teacher put plainly that she could do pair or group work rarely because of the noise in the classroom. The private school teacher believed in the benefits of working in pairs or groups claiming that otherwise, the lessons would become too individualistic. She also stated preferring group work design mostly for project-like tasks. It was also observed that the students were seated in groups even when they were not working as a group, and this teacher explained that it was mainly related to her classroom management strategies. She summarized her perspective as in this quote: *“Pair and group work... Yes, they are my essentials. Even if they [the students] sit in the classical seating plan, they know their groups, and I use those activities.”* On the other hand, the public school teacher generally avoided pair or group work since she did not find them effective. She argued that students make too much noise while working in pairs or groups, which prevents her from achieving lesson objectives. Rather, her students worked in pairs or groups very rarely just to ask and answer some questions to each other or act a ready dialogue in front of the whiteboard for other students. In short, she justified her avoidance as follows: *“It [group work] creates so much noise, and the activity gets out of control. I cannot be successful in that. And I also think that nobody can achieve it.”*

4.2.3 Role of Instructional Materials

The third theme coming up from the interview data is concerned with the role of the instructional materials utilized by the participant teachers. Accordingly, both teachers stated following EFL books as their primary material while designing their annual plans and in-class activities as well as benefitting from audio-visual materials for the target-age group. First, the course book in the private school was issued by an international publishing house and it was chosen by their English committee whereas the one used in the public school was provided by the Ministry of National Education. Accordingly, the private school teacher expressed her contentment with the book in general whereas the public-school teacher did not find the book efficient enough in many aspects. She argued that the course book provided by the government did not support language teaching properly, did not provide a sufficient number of exercises or enough opportunities for speaking practice, and neither the audio files for the listening sections nor the other physical posters or yearly plans were given which caused the lessons to become more teacher-centered. She expressed her perceptions about the book she used with the following words: *“Even the songs on the CD do not exist in the books. Even if all of those listening texts are in books... there are more gaps. Too short, no exercise. Very weak in terms of exercise. Of course, the book is also insufficient because the course hours are insufficient.”* Second, both teachers enriched their instruction with ample audio-visual materials such as slides, songs or videos considering the age group. The private school teacher, for instance, mentioned creating slide shows for the students and it was also observed that she included flashcards, posters, online games, and tests as well as video songs related to the content. Similarly, she expressed that she loved using a calendar which allowed them to talk about the days, the date, and the weather. The public school teacher, on the other hand, claimed that if she had more lesson time, she would love to use more activities including puppets, cut and paste, and word cards...

On the other hand, it is understood that the participant teachers differed regarding their use of supplementary resources in addition to the above-mentioned primary course books and benefitting from realia in their teaching. First, the private school teacher did not need to get her students to use any other extra resources whereas the public school

teacher supported the primary course book with two additional resources: one for extra activities and another for practicing multiple choice questions (test preparation). The public school teacher explained her justification for the extra resources as follows: *“But the books given by the government in primary school, the books are like zero... Really insufficient... XXX (brand name) English Book and Test Book. They are good books. In other words, it is the book that I cannot stop them from doing it.”* Finally, the private school teacher mentioned using realia such as clothes, toys, and puppets in contrast to the public school teacher who did not refer to them when she was asked about her instructional materials. The private school teacher described how she used realia in her teaching as follows: *“For example, I have fashion shows in the class. It also becomes very good with clothes and stuff. We had a sandwich shop, for example, it was about food, we sold sandwiches to children and to their friends. Then we gave that money somewhere. Like charity. I like that. I told you; I love enrichment. I like to use more visual and auditory things with these methods.”*

4.2.4 Learner and Teacher Roles

Another theme revealed in the descriptive analysis of the interview data is about the roles teachers and learners fulfill in the classroom. First, both teachers stated to be the authority figure although they differed in the degree of their control over the students. That is, they took on traditional roles; however, the public school teacher seemed a lot more traditional and authoritarian. This is mainly because she was a control freak determining every single thing in her lessons such as the content of the lessons, the materials, and the interaction patterns. Moreover, she had strict rules and did not tolerate the students for breaking the rules or not studying. She believed that some level of punishment was also necessary to discipline students for success. She described her role as a teacher with the following words: *“I love children so much and reflect it to the students as well. However, I am also disciplined and authoritarian. In what way am I harsh? Homework will be done, books will come. You will learn. You will work hard. I'm tougher that way. But everything is a mistake now, we gave up those kinds of old techniques.”*

Likewise, the private school teacher preferred controlling almost everything in the classroom by choosing the content, materials, activities, or determining the interaction patterns. However, she was in favor of classroom rules and routines so that the kids would feel safe in her lessons. Additionally, she acted as a group process manager to manage her classes effectively for which she utilized rewarding and punishment. In other words, she formed groups and punished them by cutting off their group points when they did not follow the rules or rewarded them by giving extra points when they participated actively. It is possible to conclude that she was less authoritarian when compared to the public school teacher since her main aim was to push the students to active participation in lessons. The following quote from the private school teacher summarizes her self-perceived role as an English teacher: *“I also love to start with the rules. I love routines. I always like to go with those rules and routines. Because of the classroom layout, little ones love routines. Well, children feel safer with routines. I mean that what I call a routine will be the lesson order. At the beginning of the lesson, tidying up, etc. And having all those books in front of them when they see me, I mean when they see me because they are illiterate. In fact, in the second year, all the books will be in front of them according to the curriculum. They will know. We are ready for the English lesson at that moment. They won't have anything else. They will sit back, breathe deeply like they're going to start that way.”* Other than that, she explained that she used emojis and grouping to discipline the students. As clear from her sentences: *“For example, this creating teams thing of mine makes my job much easier. I give points, I give names to them. In addition, working together... We have the technique of teaching in English or running the children all together. Collaboration, cooperation, or something like that. In that sense, I gain from it... as classroom management...”*

Not surprisingly, the above-mentioned teacher roles bring about traditional learner roles. The students had almost no word in their learning process in both contexts. All the decisions were made by the authority and almost everything was determined by their teachers. They were expected to follow the rules and routines and were punished or rewarded accordingly. However, it is possible to argue that the students in the private school were a bit more autonomous as their teacher considered their opinions while

designing some activities. For instance, she explained an activity called surprise box: *“You may have noticed that there is a Surprise Box, for example. And I wanted something from them. I asked them to write an activity. They wrote the activity at first. We are doing an activity that is in it.”* In addition, during the year, the teacher reminded them that they would play the games in that box if they could do what they meant to do during the lesson time, as the researcher observed. Moreover, the private school students’ main responsibility was to show active participation in the lessons. The private school teacher explained her perspective as follows: *“The teacher should be like a director of an orchestra; you should direct it but at the same time leave the lesson to the students.”*

4.2.5 Role of L1 Use in L2 Instruction

The fifth theme emerging from the interview data is related to the teachers’ opinions about L1 use in their L2 instruction. Both teachers believed that L1 should be avoided as much as possible in L2 teaching; however, they stated that they spoke in Turkish in their lessons for various reasons. For instance, the private school teacher argued that she had to use Turkish for disciplinary issues since her students were not ready for all-English instruction due to the online education in the previous academic year. Although she admitted switching to Turkish to create a secure atmosphere in and out of the classroom, she also claimed to be quite strict and insistent in giving her instructions in English to encourage the kids to use the L2. The following quote describes her perspective on L1 use quite well: *‘I psychologically feel insufficient when I use Turkish.’* Likewise, the teacher in the public school came up with a similar utterance regarding her L1 use: *“The fact that I use Turkish makes me very upset and it is the thing that I most criticize about myself.”* Then, she explained her reasons for speaking in Turkish while teaching as follows: *“I can't try to express a word in English throughout a lesson. Or I can't spend a lesson on a word or a few words. But there is such a curriculum that we must finish, and I am always behind it. Let them learn if two units are missing.”* Additionally, she admitted that she is not as proficient as should be in English and that she was speaking Turkish for almost half of the lesson when the students did not understand what she was trying to convey despite using body language, gestures, and visuals or when they misbehaved.

4.2.6 Perceptions of the Communicative Approach

The last theme coming out of the interview data is related to the teachers' perceptions of the Communicative Approach. First of all, neither of the participant teachers could explain the method in academic terms. Nevertheless, the private school teacher stated prioritizing communication, especially with this age group, and trying her best to make the students internalize the language so that they could express themselves in English and use it as a means of communication. She emphasized valuing communication so much and claimed to have created her own teaching methodology based on this understanding. She expressed herself with the following words: *“Of course, first of all, it [communication] is inevitable. It is not like that I'm applying that method exactly and know everything and every principle. You will go by merging it with your own methods and adapting it to the dynamics of the class, that's a separate issue.”*

On the other hand, the public school teacher seemed unaware of the Communicative Approach as a method since she gave an irrelevant description of it by talking about how she loved the children. When explained what was meant by it, she expressed her preference for teaching grammar and explained her reasons for why CLT was inapplicable in her context as follows: *‘If we don't take exams, if our success is not measured by an exam to test whether we have learned that language..., of course, speaking is important. In fact, encouragement should be given, to be able to express oneself without being bound by grammatical rules. I don't want to say I'm a teacher when I meet someone because we make mistakes while speaking. There are much fewer errors when typing. But we make mistakes when we speak. I realize that mistake, it comes out of my mouth. And when I realize my mistake, I feel very sad. ... That's how we were brought up in terms of English. Even though I am obsessed with them, I wish there were no rules.’* In short, she believed it was impossible to teach English with communicative activities in her context due to the testing system and heavy curriculum as well as the insufficient and limited teaching hours. Finally, she exemplified her recommendations for her students to develop their communicative skills as follows: *“All I say to the children is to go to a shop in the Grand Bazaar, next to the spice shop, during the summer vacation. They speak three or five languages there. Practice there even if you don't make any money. Bring tea, I*

don't know, and gain experience in Sultan Ahmet. Or there are foreigners around, play in the park together, and practice English. These are the ones I can recommend the most. We were chasing tourists.”

5. RESULTS, DISCUSSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The current study aimed to investigate the actual practices of two Turkish EFL teachers from a public and a private primary school and to see their perceptions about teaching English in general, and CLT in particular as well as to depict the inconsistencies between their practices and beliefs if there are any. First, this section briefly summarizes the findings obtained from the observations and interviews. Then, the two contexts are compared to highlight the similarities and differences regarding the use of CLT with young learners. Next, the findings are discussed in the light of the related literature and the latest EFL curriculum. Finally, some practical recommendations are given for policy makers, foreign language teachers, and for researchers interested in the issue.

5.1 Results and Discussion

The results obtained from the COLT observation schemes and the interviews conducted with the teachers are summarized and discussed below. The discussion is presented under the following categories: participant organization indicating the roles of teachers and students, the content of the lessons along with the activities the students are engaged in, students' modalities, and the instructional materials used in the lessons.

5.1.1 Participant Organization, Teacher and Learner Roles

This study made the following conclusions regarding participant organization, and teacher and learner roles. First, the dominant interaction patterns in both schools were *teacher to students* and *teacher to whole class*. Second, the private school students could initiate the interaction relatively more often due to the activities with *student to student / whole class* interaction patterns whereas the learners in the public school were engaged in more *choral* work repeating after their teacher or audio. Third, the students in both schools were predominantly engaged with *individual* work although the ones in the private school context were observed working in pairs or groups for a limited period of time. Accordingly, it can be concluded that the English lessons in the public school were relatively more teacher-centered and traditional reflecting the features of ALM whereas the students in the private school had comparably more voice and were more active in the

lessons. Fourth, a similar picture was revealed for teacher and learner roles. Both teachers displayed quite traditional roles feeling the need to control lessons, materials, and interaction types. Accordingly, the content of the lessons was always determined by the teacher or the textbook in both schools giving no voice to learners. However, the public school teacher was found much more authoritarian leaving no room for breaking rules and favoring punishment more to reinforce good behavior whereas the private school teacher seemed to reward learners by giving extra points in addition to punishments through cut-offs.

Based on the above-mentioned findings, the following comments can be made. First, neither the interaction patterns nor the teacher and learner roles in the observed lessons were compatible with the principles of CLT. Unlike the traditional and authoritarian roles revealed in this study, communicative teachers act as a facilitator of the communicative atmosphere and a member of the learning and teaching group rather than determining everything going on in lessons (Breen & Candlin, 1980). Moreover, communicative lessons are more learner-centered and students are autonomous working collaboratively in pairs or groups instead of dealing with individual work (Richards, 2006). In other words, CLT does not mean controlled role-play activities, but learners have some control over their learning (Savignon, 1991). On the other hand, the relatively more *student to student* interaction observed in the private school context was due to the games and role plays applied in the lessons. Second, there was a mismatch between what was expected in the official curriculum document and what happened in the observed lessons regarding teacher and learner roles because the role of the teacher has been defined as a facilitator in the Turkish EFL curriculum since 1997 (Kırkgöz, 2020). Third, these findings are consistent with the results of various studies on EFL instruction in the literature showing that most classrooms are teacher-centered, and the students have little or no voice in deciding the content or activities, and do not participate in the lessons actively (Al-Nouh 2008; An, 2020; Hoque et. al., 2018; Islam, 2016; Kırkgöz, 2007b; Kim, 2008; Muhridza & Satanihpy, 2019). Fourth, this teacher-centeredness and avoidance of collaborative work can be explained by the participant teachers' perceptions and beliefs regarding EFL teaching. That is, the public school teacher plainly did not find

group and pair work activities effective arguing that they caused too much noise, and prevented achieving the curriculum goals. As for the private school teacher, such collaborative tasks were quite rare in her lessons although she claimed that group work was essential in her teaching, which demonstrates that she cannot or does not apply what she believes in reality. In the same vein, various studies in the literature point out such mismatches between teachers' perceptions and applications (Coşkun, 2011; Gürsoy & Eken, 2018; Rahman et. al., 2018). Finally, the participant teachers' tendency to control the whole process can be explained by the age group they were addressing. That is, they were teaching young learners who needed some kind of guidance in the classroom not to have chaos and to have smooth transitions between the phases of the lesson. Being a more traditional and authoritarian teacher figure might be helping with their classroom management in young learner groups.

5.1.2 Content of the Lessons, Teaching and Learning Activities

The results concerning the topic of the lessons revealed several different conclusions. First of all, in both schools, the content of the lessons usually focused on *language* and *form* activities, which were mostly targeting vocabulary learning while tasks highlighting sociolinguistic or discourse competence were completely ignored. However, CLT aims to work on and develop students' communicative competence which covers not only grammatical, but also discourse, strategic, and sociolinguistic competencies (Brown, 2000). Second, it was found that the textbooks used in the lessons were more language-oriented, as in traditional classrooms, in which there is much emphasis on forms, grammar structures, and vocabulary development (Kumaravadivelu, 2003). Third, it was revealed that learning about and using language functions was very limited both in the private and the public school even though it is valued in CLT to a great extent (Larsen-Freeman, 2000). The fact that the content was slightly more about *language functions* in the public school can point that the coursebook provided by the government for 2nd graders included some elements pertaining to functions of language; though, it may not be enough to develop learners' communicative competence. Parallel to the results of this study, a bulk of research in the field found that the content of primary EFL lessons included more

grammar/form and translation activities with a focus on accuracy and lacked communicative ones (Al-Nouh, 2008; Hamid & Honan, 2012; Islam 2016; Kırkgöz, 2007b) and similar cases were detected for the EFL instruction at Korean secondary and high schools as well (Han, 2016; Kim, 2008).

However, CLT does not mean ‘*no grammar/form*’. As far as it is meaningful to the learners and the activities do not solely consist of isolated drills and word lists given for memorization, forms including grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation can be touched on during the lessons in communicative classrooms. Studies suggest that teaching form-focused and meaning-focused activities in a balanced way is way more beneficial for students (Spada & Lightbown, 2013) because successful communication also requires the correct use of language. Similarly, grammar teaching addressing the communicative needs of learners makes the learning process easier (Savignon, 1991). At the same time, the use of more controlled and form-focused activities is accepted as the weak version of CLT as long as the aim is communication (Nassaji & Fotos, 2011). In this respect, the current study may conclude that the public school lessons were closer to the weak version of CLT with more emphasis on language exercises while it was stronger in the private school as the focus was more on meaning. However, because communicative competence is the focus of instruction in CLT (Brown, 2000), meaning-based activities should not be ignored at all because young learners acquire the language more indirectly with a focus on meaning (Kırkgöz, 2018).

Additionally, there were some particular activities detected in both schools. First, there was frequent use of games in the private school (though led by the teacher most of the time) whereas it was quite rare in the public school. Second, while the private school teacher tried to enrich the lessons through games, cut-and-paste activities, and slides, the public school teacher preferred to use more language exercises from the additional course books she was using in addition to the ones involving some songs and flashcards. Third, although both teachers used repetition as a teaching strategy, the public school teacher wanted the students to repeat more in chorus both after her and the audio provided in the book, and she paid special attention to her students’ pronunciation. All these made her lessons more ALM-oriented since it is a method obsessed with repetition and accurate and

native-like pronunciation (Larsen-Freeman, 2000). Furthermore, it is significant to note that the public school teacher occasionally benefitted from explicit grammar teaching and translations for vocabulary activities and instructions, which was not observed in the private school. Confirming these findings, the public school teacher herself also stated teaching grammar at the primary level as well although less than she did at the secondary school level. On the other hand, the private school teacher was in favor of implicit grammar instruction, and accordingly, explicit grammar instruction was never observed in her lessons.

As for the regular patterns in lessons, homework checks, explaining stuff by writing on the whiteboard, and question-answer drills were observed in the public school which was different from the private school. In addition to these kinds of pre-communicative ones (Littlewood, 1981), the activities in real language classrooms lie in a continuum from non-communicative to communicative (Harmer, 2007). Hence, it can be concluded that the lessons were more meaning-based in the private school because activities requiring the children to do things based on what they heard and understood were more common while there was a mixture of traditional elements and meaningful activities in the public school. Considering the latest EFL curriculum which suggests teachers use communicative activities with the provided units (MEB, 2018), the private school teacher's implementations were more aligned with the objectives of the curriculum. Likewise, various studies on the use of the communicative approach also demonstrated that EFL lessons were reflecting communicative features to a great extent (Guzmán-Alcón, 2019), while some others concluded that language teachers were still using a mixture of communicative and traditional methodologies in their classrooms (Shrestha, 2013).

Moreover, the public school teacher mentioned some obstacles to using communicative activities in the lessons such as the testing system, heavy curriculum, and limited instructional time devoted to English. In addition to those, she did not find herself proficient enough in the target language. In the literature, numerous studies also conclude that teachers had almost the same handicaps while teaching a foreign language communicatively (Ansarey, 2012; Çapan, 2021; Hunutlu, 2011; Kırkgöz, 2007a; Li &

Baldauf, 2011; Mutlu & Kaşlıoğlu, 2015; Özşevik, 2010; Sherwani & Kılıç, 2017). Thereby, it is possible that the public school teacher felt stressed to cover all the units because the time devoted to English lessons is only two hours per week for 2nd graders, which is not sufficient for learning a language. However, another recent study conducted in the Turkish context (Başok, 2020) found that even though what the curriculum suggests (CLT) and how the students are assessed (grammar-based) may not match in policy, the primary school teacher did not feel demotivated because she was not preparing her students to an exam and there was no assessment in primary school. Thus, it can be commented that the testing system that the students face in secondary school should not be a factor affecting the public school teacher's implementations, as it was not mentioned by the private school teacher.

The findings given above may allow for the following comments. First of all, just because the content centers on the form/vocabulary activities, one cannot claim that it is a traditional classroom. The way the teacher conducts the lessons has also some role in the classroom atmosphere. That is, using age-appropriate materials and making the content meaningful for children through games, songs, and pictures is significant while teaching young learners. Since younger learners learn differently from adult learners, teachers should use more TPR activities that are meaningful and engaging for them and encourage their active participation (Kırkgöz, 2018). Similarly, the teachers of this study benefitted from TPR, listening and speaking activities, and used visuals along with texts, as well as audiovisuals (video songs), which indicates that they valued using an appropriate methodology for the target age group.

Second, the perceptions of teachers may have also affected the teachers' teaching practices. Although the private school teacher could not explain what the communicative approach means in its own terms, she had an idea about it and an attitude towards it. For instance, she saw the L2 as a way of communication and tried to apply the method by merging it with her own methods and own classroom dynamics. On the contrary, the public school teacher did not have any idea about the approach and could not explain the communicative approach to the researcher. Similarly, the research in the field found that

while some teachers have positive attitudes towards CLT (Anani Sarab et. al., 2016; Rahmawati, 2018) some have negative or unclear perceptions of it (Hossen, 2008).

Third, the reason why the private school teacher's implementations were more comprehension-based and suitable for the target age group can be justified by the fact that she was more experienced in teaching young learners than the public school teacher because she had been teaching young learners since she graduated which made 16 years. On the other hand, although the public school teacher had 37 years of teaching experience, she had been teaching young learners only for 9 years. Before that she had taught different age groups including secondary and high school students as well as adult learners. So, the public school teacher was more experienced and older but had less experience in teaching young learners. Also, experienced/older teachers generally tend to use more traditional, grammar and translation-based activities in their lessons and they are slower in following recent innovations, which were called as laggards (Gürsoy & Eken, 2018; Kırkgöz, 2007b). Thus, although the public school teacher cannot be counted as one of those true laggards because of the activities and materials appropriate and engaging for her students observed in the lessons, she might have had established beliefs about how to teach and learn a foreign language coming from her own experience (Borg, 2003).

Finally, neither of the teachers in the current study completed an ELT program at the university. While the private school teacher completed English Language and Literature program, the public school teacher finished the College of Foreign Languages. Thus, it can be interpreted that these teachers did not take a course about TEYLs and CLT at university. After graduation, they both completed a pedagogical formation program, which was probably a general one without any course about teaching young learners. However, it is understood that the private school teacher valued her professional development and learned more about teaching young learners. Similarly, the public school teacher started to use more age-appropriate materials after she had quitted teaching adult learners. Considering all the results above, it can therefore be assumed that while the implementations of the private school teacher were closer to the interpretation-oriented teachers with more focus on meaning-based activities although mostly she led the lessons,

the public school teacher was more eclectic by combining traditional and communicative features (Kırkgöz, 2008b).

5.1.3 Students' Modality

Several conclusions can be made about the students' modalities indicating the language skills focused on during the lessons. First, the students were engaged in *listening* activities more than the other skills in both schools. Because the classes were more teacher-centered, students listened to their teachers, or the audios provided in the lessons rather than their peers. The *Comprehensible Input Hypothesis* proposed by Krashen argues that the only way for learners to acquire the language is through processing the meaningful language either by listening or reading (Ortega, 2013). In the same vein, Slattery and Willis (2001) suggest that young learners need to hear lots of language around them to acquire the language. However, the public school teacher used L1 occasionally in her lessons to explain the activity or a grammar topic, which lowered the amount of comprehensible input for the learners who were exposed to the language at school for only 2 class hours per week. On the other hand, L1 use was hardly observed in the private school such as in the written form on the board to translate the instructions but almost never in the spoken form because the teacher was determined to use L2 particularly to give instructions but sometimes used L1 in one-to-one interactions to sustain discipline in her lessons. Thus, the amount of exposure to meaningful L2 use was more in the private school because they also had 8 hours of English lessons in a week. According to the principles of CLT, L1 does not have to be banned from L2 classrooms because it has some advantages such as saving time and making some instructions clearer; but at the same time, L2 should be the main medium of instruction to ensure that learners are exposed to the target language as much as possible, especially in the EFL environment (Spada, 2007; Turnbull, 2001, Yıldız & Yeşilyurt, 2016). Thus, teachers should lower and minimize their L1 use as students get more proficient in the target language (Pan & Pan, 2010).

Second, activities requiring *listening* and *speaking* were rather common in both schools. In an environment with little student to student interaction, this may point that both the private and the public school students were answering the teachers' questions or

repeating after them or the audio most of the time. This is mostly consistent with the expectations of the latest EFL curriculum because it also advocates developing students' aural and oral skills (MEB, 2018). In addition, *listening* and doing *other* activities on what students heard or engaging only with *other* activities such as doing those hands-on activities including TPR, drawing, coloring, counting, clapping hands, or cutting and pasting were observed often in both contexts, but more in the private school. For instance, the private school teacher tended to use authentic and extra activities more often, and did not restrict the lessons to the course book activities. On the other hand, although the public school teacher tried to address different senses by using such *other* activities, she expressed that she could not find enough time for extra game-like activities due to insufficient class hours. This may demonstrate that while the students in both schools were busy with comprehension-based activities, the amount of time devoted to them was more in the private school. Various studies in the literature also concluded that meaningful contexts should be created for the target age group and a child-friendly pedagogy should be followed in EFL instruction (Kırkgöz, 2018; Nguyen, 2021; Shin, 2017; Zein, 2017).

On the other hand, *reading* activities were scarcely detected in both schools. In addition, the public school students spent a considerable amount of time on *writing* activities requiring them to write one or two words and sometimes short sentences either in their notebooks or on the whiteboard. Similarly, the public school teacher preferred to use two additional books to provide the students with more language exercises because she found the book given by the government quite insufficient. In addition to the in-class writing activities, the public school teacher assigned the students with other writing tasks and then checked them every week. However, writing activities were observed rarely in the private school as stated in the latest EFL curriculum since it suggests using reading and writing activities limitedly in the 2nd grade (MEB, 2018). Although both teachers expressed aiming at developing their students' vocabulary knowledge, listening, and speaking skills while making them get familiar with L2 writing, the public school teacher seemed to emphasize writing more than expected and needed, making her lessons a bit more traditional.

CLT suggests that teachers focus on all four skills from the beginning because there is also interaction in reading and writing and CLT is not limited only to listening and speaking activities (Larsen-Freeman, 2000). However, because the learners in this study were 2nd graders and they had just learned how to read and write in their L1, the primary goal of the curriculum and the teachers of the study is to make the students get used to a foreign language, and let them have positive attitudes towards it. Hence, reading and writing activities are not prioritized in the curriculum for young learners.

5.1.4 Instructional Materials Used in the Lessons

This study looked at the *type* and the *source* of materials to compare them with the ones used in typical CLT lessons. First, the most frequently used material type in both schools was *text with visuals*. The teachers also enhanced their lessons with the use of *text-only* materials, *visuals*, *audiovisuals* (video songs, in general), and just *audio*, but they were used less when compared to the text-with-visual materials. Hence, in both schools, the textbook supported by visuals was the primary material, and the use of visuals or flashcards with text (generally vocabulary) was observed to a considerable degree. In the same vein, Yuliawati and Aprilla (2019) mention the effectiveness of using pictures while teaching young learners and the latest Turkish curriculum encourages using such materials for this age group (MEB, 2018).

Second, the teachers and students in both contexts spent a considerable amount of time without using any materials at all. It was revealed that no-material time was spent on disciplinary issues to make the children behave appropriately and also procedural activities such as explaining the instructions and preparing the students for the lesson in addition to the use of role-plays, repetition drills, TPR activities, dealing with technical problems, and playing games. The public school teacher also used some of the class time to explain grammar and vocabulary to the students on the board without using any materials.

Finally, as for the source of the materials, the teachers were observed using materials prepared to teach a foreign language to non-native speakers almost all the time (L2-NNS). While the use of *authentic* materials was detected in the private school in one

lesson, the public school learners also once used materials prepared by themselves (*student-made*). However, CLT promotes the use of authentic materials to expose learners to real language use (Li, 1998). At the same time, in accordance with the present results, EFL teachers use a variety of materials including authentic, adapted, or pedagogic ones in reality (Mitchell, 2003).

5.2 Conclusion

Since there are few studies in the Turkish context as a typical EFL setting showing the current use of CLT in primary classes, this study aimed to display to what extent CLT is applied by two different teachers in two different schools in Istanbul, a private and a public school. The main conclusions of this study can be summarized as follows. First, neither of the teachers followed pure traditional approaches since they tried to make their lessons more meaningful and engaging for their young learners at varying degrees. That is, although both classes are teacher-centered, the private school teacher had relatively more communicative lessons because the students were more active and there were more comprehension-based activities including songs, games, TPR, and drawing and coloring. The public school teacher mixed both communicative activities with such traditional elements as choral repetition, explicit grammar and vocabulary explanations as well as focus on writing and homework checks. Thus, in a continuum, while the private school teacher was closer to the interpretation-oriented teachers, the public school teacher can be regarded as an eclectic one (Kırkgöz, 2008b). Furthermore, the teachers' perceptions of the communicative approach were found to have a significant effect on their way of teaching. Namely, it was revealed that the private school teacher approached the language as a medium of communication and expected her students to use it in that way while at the same time, she admitted that rather than applying all the principles of the approach she adapted it to her own class atmosphere, which is more in line with the context approach of CLT (Bax, 2003). On the other hand, the public school teacher was found to be obsessed with rules, and she believed that teaching through communicative activities is almost impossible due to the testing system, heavy curriculum, and insufficient teaching hours.

All in all, it is possible to conclude that teachers still hold the primary role in the effective implementation of any method or approach in real classrooms.

5.3 Practical Recommendations

Considering the conclusions and discussion above, it is possible to give some recommendations for policy makers, practicing teachers in the field, and for further research. They are presented under the related titles in the following sections.

5.3.1 Recommendations for Policy Makers

Since this study focused on language teaching and the use of CLT in primary classes, some recommendations especially for that level can be provided. First of all, it is rather understandable that while teaching in primary classes, the importance of teaching English to young learners (TEYLs) comes out. However, as in this study, not all teachers in Turkey were trained to teach an L2 to young learners, let alone get specialized in this field. In this respect, it can be suggested that the teachers practicing in primary classes should be trained and informed about TEYLs and CLT through various in-service training programs such as webinars, seminars, and workshops. Second, it is necessary to make sure that teacher training programs at universities involve a practical side to TEYLs courses so that pre-service teachers can also have experience in teaching that age group before graduating. Likewise, in-service teachers should be provided with practical tips and continuous supervision about TEYLs communicatively, especially in their own context rather than one-shot theoretical introductions. Third, it is understood that teachers avoid pair or group work activities in order to manage their classes more easily and effectively and to catch up with the curriculum. Therefore, some action should be taken to minimize class sizes and to increase EFL lessons in the weekly program so that teachers can allocate enough time for more pair and group work in EFL lessons. This might increase students' exposure to the target language and encourage teachers to design more communicative lessons. Finally, it is understood that students at private schools seem to be more advantageous at accessing more communicative EFL instruction. Therefore, all the related

policy makers including MNE should take action to minimize this inequality between the two contexts.

5.3.2 Recommendations for Practicing Teachers

The latest EFL curriculum in Turkey is based on the principles of CLT and sheds light on the significance of teaching age-appropriately in primary classrooms as well as providing teachers with suggested activities and strategies. Therefore, teachers can be recommended to read this document carefully to benefit from the given information. In addition, they can attend various professional development activities such as trainings, webinars, or workshops to design more communicative EFL lessons in their contexts. Likewise, they can be suggested to adopt a more scientific approach towards their teaching through reflective teaching, lesson observations and action research to raise their self-awareness for their own teaching. Also, they can collaborate with their colleagues to get and provide support for more communicative and age-appropriate EFL instruction. In a similar vein, EFL teachers are recommended to participate in post-graduate programs to deepen and update their professional knowledge.

5.3.3 Recommendations for Further Research

This study investigated the communicative orientations of two typical private and public school EFL teachers via observations and interviews to shed light on the current situation of primary English classes in Turkey. Further studies can be conducted with more teachers with different backgrounds (regarding their age, experience, gender, training, etc.) from different contexts (e.g., different regions or cities) teaching different age groups (other grades from the primary, secondary, or high school levels) to depict the case more comprehensively for EFL instruction regarding the use of CLT in Turkey. Also, experimental studies can be conducted with interventions that might lead to more communicative and age-appropriate EFL instruction. Other studies involving learners, parents, administrators, or teacher trainers as participants can be conducted to reveal their perspectives and roles regarding communicative EFL instruction in Turkey. Finally,

similar studies can be conducted with pre-service teachers to check to what extent they are prepared to teach English to young learners communicatively.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1. Informed Consent Form

Aydınlatıcı Onam Formu

“*Communicative Orientation of EFL Instruction in Primary Classrooms (İlkokul Sınıflarında Yabancı Dil Olarak İngilizce Öğretiminin İletişimsel Yönelimi)*” adlı çalışma, ilkokul seviyesinde işlenen İngilizce derslerinin ne düzeyde iletişime dayalı olduğunu ortaya koymayı amaçlamaktadır. Çalışmanın Aralık 2021-Haziran 2022 tarihleri arasında yapılması planlanmaktadır.

Bu çalışmaya katılmak tamamen gönüllülük esasına dayanmaktadır. Çalışmanın amacına ulaşması için sizden beklenen, on hafta süreyle haftada bir saat siz normal derslerinize devam ederken, sınıf ortamında sınıf etkinliklerinizin gözlemlenmesine izin vermenizdir. Gözlemler için sizden ayrıca bir çalışma talep edilmeyecektir. Gözlemler bittikten sonra 25-30 dakikalık bir görüşme talep edilecektir. Bu çalışmaya katılmak sizin için hiçbir risk barındırmazken, katılımınız sayesinde Türkiye’de yabancı dil eğitimiyle ilgili yapılan bir çalışmaya katkı sağlamış olacaksınız. Bu formu okuyup onaylamanız, araştırmaya katılmayı kabul ettiğiniz anlamına gelecektir. Ancak, çalışmaya katılmama veya katıldıktan sonra herhangi bir anda çalışmayı bırakma hakkına da sahiptir.

Bu çalışmadan elde edilecek bilgiler tamamen araştırma amacı ile kullanılacak olup kişisel bilgileriniz gizli tutulacaktır; ancak verileriniz yayın amacı ile kullanılabilir. Eğer araştırmanın amacı ile ilgili verilen bu bilgiler dışında şimdi veya sonra daha fazla bilgiye ihtiyaç duyarsanız araştırmacıya şimdi sorabilir, e-posta veya telefon numaramdan ulaşabilirsiniz.

“Aydınlatılmış Onam Formundaki tüm açıklamaları okudum. Bana, konusu ve amacı belirtilen araştırma ile ilgili yazılı ve sözlü açıklama, aşağıda adı belirtilen kişi tarafından yapıldı. Araştırmaya gönüllü olarak katıldığımı, istediğim zaman gerekçeli veya gerekçesiz olarak araştırmadan ayrılabileceğimi ve kendi isteğime bakılmaksızın araştırmacı tarafından araştırma dışı bırakılabileceğimi biliyorum. Söz konusu araştırmaya, hiçbir baskı ve zorlama olmaksızın kendi rızamla *katılmayı kabul ediyorum.*

...../...../20..

Açıklamaları Yapan Araştırmacının Unvanı, Adı Soyadı ve İmzası
Sena SAYICI (Yüksek Lisans Öğrencisi)
Gönüllünün Adı / Soyadı / İmzası / Tarih

Appendix 2. Permission from the Ministry of Education for the Study

43540522/01

İstanbul İl Millî Eğitim Müdürlüğü ANKET ARAŞTIRMA KOMİSYONU DEĞERLENDİRME FORMU									
ARAŞTIRMA SAHİBİNİN									
Adı Soyadı		Senah SAYICI							
Kurumu / Üniversitesi		İstanbul Medeniyet Üniversitesi							
Araştırma Yapılacak İller		İstanbul							
Araştırma Yapılacak Eğitim Kurumu ve Kademesi		,,,İlkokullar,,,							
Araştırmanın Konusu		İlkokul Sınıflarında Yabancı Dil Olarak İngilizce Öğretiminin İletişimsel Yönelimi							
Üniversite / Kurum Onayı		Var							
Veri Toplama Araçları									
MEB 21/01/2020 tarih ve 1563890 sayılı 2020/2 Genelge Kapsamında Araştırma, Yarışma ve Sosyal Etkinlik İzinlerinde Dikkat Edilecek Hususlar									
Maddeler	Uygun	Uygun Değil	Maddeler	Uygun	Uygun Değil	Maddeler	Uygun	Uygun Değil	
2020/2 Genelgenin 1. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 2. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 3. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2020/2 Genelgenin 4. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 5. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 6. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2020/2 Genelgenin 7. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 8. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 9. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2020/2 Genelgenin 10. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 11. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 12. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2020/2 Genelgenin 13. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 14. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 15. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2020/2 Genelgenin 16. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 17. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 18. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2020/2 Genelgenin 19. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 20. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 21. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2020/2 Genelgenin 22. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 23. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 24. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2020/2 Genelgenin 25. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 26. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 27. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2020/2 Genelgenin 28. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 28. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 30. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2020/2 Genelgenin 31. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 32. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	2020/2 Genelgenin 33. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2020/2 Genelgenin 34. Maddesi	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>							
KOMİSYON GÖRÜŞÜ <i>uygundur</i>									
Veri toplama araçlarının eğitim-öğretimi aksatmayacak şekilde gönüllülük esasına dayalı olarak uygulanması ve araştırma sonuç raporunun müdürlüğümüzden izin alınmadan kamuoyuyla paylaşılması koşuluyla yürütülmesinde bir sakınca bulunmamaktadır <input type="checkbox"/> bulunmamaktadır <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>									
Komisyon Kararı						Oybirliğiyle Alınmıştır.			
KOMİSYON									
Açıklama:						Ünvan-Adı Soyadı-İmza			
					02.2022 Üye: <i>Hayat Destemir YILMAZ</i>			
					02.2022 Üye: <i>Dr. İsmail KATİCİ</i>			
					02.2022 Üye: <i>Hakan GEYİK</i>			

**Appendix 3. Approval Form Received From Istanbul Medeniyet University
Educational Sciences Ethics Committee**

 İSTANBUL MEDENİYET ÜNİVERSİTESİ	T.C. İSTANBUL MEDENİYET ÜNİVERSİTESİ EĞİTİM BİLİMLERİ ETİK KURULU KARARI
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Tarihi 03/01/2022	Sayı 2022/01-01
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ARAŞTIRMA BAŞLIĞI	Communicative Orientation of EFL Instruction in Primary Classrooms (İlkokul Sınıflarında Yabancı Dil Olarak İngilizce Öğretiminin İletişimsel Yönelimi)
ARAŞTIRMANIN TÜRÜ	Nitel Araştırma
ARAŞTIRMACI(LAR)	Senah SAYICI
KARAR	Etik açıdan uygundur.

Görevi	Kurul Üyeleri	İmza
Başkan	Prof. Dr. Halil İbrahim SAĞLAM	
Üye	Prof. Dr. Ahmet AKIN	
Üye	Prof. Dr. Özlem FEDAI	
Üye	Prof. Dr. Selami AYDIN	
Üye	Prof. Dr. Yeşim GÜLEÇ ASLAN	
Üye	Doç. Dr. Özge CENGİZ	
Üye	Doç. Dr. Özcan Erkan AKGÜN	
Üye	Av. Fevziye DOĞRUER	

Appendix 4. Semi-Structured Interview Form

GÖRÜŞME PROTOKOLÜ

Araştırma Konusu: İlkokul Sınıflarında Yabancı Dil Olarak İngilizce Öğretiminin İletişimsel Yönelimi

Yer:

Tarih/saat:

Görüşmeci:

Sayın Katılımcı,

“İlkokul Sınıflarında Yabancı Dil Olarak İngilizce Öğretiminin İletişimsel Yönelimi” başlıklı çalışmamız için sizinle bir görüşme yapacağım. Araştırma kapsamında, sınıf içinde kullandığımız öğretim yöntemlerine yönelik çeşitli sorular yönelteceğim. Görüşmemiz yaklaşık 25-30 dakika sürecektir.

Amacımız: Bu çalışmanın amacı, Türkiye’de çocuklara yabancı dil öğretiminin ne düzeyde iletişime dayalı olduğunu ortaya koymaktır.

Elde edilen veriler bilimsel bir çalışma dışında hiçbir amaçla kullanılmayacak ve bulgular paylaşılırken kimliğiniz gizli tutulacaktır. Ancak, görüşmeye katılmama veya katıldıktan sonra istediğiniz herhangi bir anda görüşmeden ayrılma hakkına da sahiptir. Katılımınız ve katkılarınız için şimdiden teşekkür ederiz.

Görüşme Soruları

1. Kendinizden biraz bahsedebilir misiniz?
 - a. Eğitim durumunuz hakkında bilgi verebilir misiniz?
 - b. Mesleki deneyiminiz hakkında bilgi verebilir misiniz?
2. Çocuklara İngilizce öğretirken benimsediğiniz bir yöntem var mı?
 - a. Yoksa neden? / Varsa, yönteminizi nasıl açıklarsınız?
3. Derslerinizde dil becerilerinin (dinleme, konuşma, yazma, okuma, dilbilgisi ve kelime) yerini nasıl tanımlarsınız? Neden?

4. Çocuklara İngilizce öğretiminde temel hedefleriniz nelerdir?
 - a. Bu hedeflerin gerçekleşme düzeyini nasıl ölçüyorsunuz?
 - b. Bu hedeflere ne düzeyde ulaşabiliyorsunuz? Neden?
5. Derslerinizde en sık kullandığınız etkinlikler hangileridir? Neden?
 - a. Favori bir etkinliğinizi paylaşır mısınız?
 - b. Beklentilerinizin büyük ölçüde gerçekleştiği bir ders deneyiminden bahsedebilir misiniz?
6. Derslerinizde ikili çalışma (pair work) ve grup çalışmalarının (group work) yerini nasıl tanımlarsınız?
7. Derslerinizde İngilizce öğretimini desteklemek üzere kullandığınız materyaller nelerdir?
 - a. Kullandığınız ders kitabı sizin dil öğretim anlayışınızla örtüşüyor mu? Neden?
8. Derslerinizde anadil (Türkçe) kullanımına yer veriyor musunuz?
 - a. Hayırsa, neden?
 - b. Evetse, hangi durumlarda ve nasıl yer veriyorsunuz?
9. İletişimsel Yaklaşımın (Communicative Approach) çocuklara İngilizce öğretiminde kullanımı hakkında ne düşünüyorsunuz?
 - a. İletişimsel Dil Öğretim Yöntemi size ne ifade ediyor?

Appendix 5. Sample of the COLT Observation Scheme

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS								
		class			group		indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	type		source					
		T-S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
Total Time																																

Appendix 6. Private School Observation Schemes

Observation 1: 21.10.2021

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION						CONTENT						CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS										
		Class			Group		Indiv.	Manag.		Language			Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source							
		T-S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.									Narrow	Broad	Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
															Text	Text																
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
15:23 (3 min)	A1/E1: T makes the children remember the cl. rules.	✓								✓							✓			✓												
15:26 (1 min)	A2/E1: T gives commands: sit down / stand up, sleep/ wake up, and Ss act.	✓									✓						✓			✓				✓								
15:27 (5 min)	A3/E1: T wants the Ss to open their WB. Ss write the first letter of the words and match the words with the pictures.	✓					✓		✓		✓						✓			✓			✓	✓	✓			✓	✓			
15:32 (2 min)	A4/E1: T writes the letter of each word on the board and helps the Ss while walking around.	✓					✓				✓						✓			✓			✓	✓	✓				✓			
15:34 (1 min)	A5/E1: T gets the Ss quiet and seated.	✓									✓						✓			✓												
15:35 (5 min)	A6/E1: T explains the spinner game in	✓							✓								✓			✓								✓	✓			

Observation 2: 27.10.2021

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS								
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language					Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type				Source				
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow									Broad	Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
																Text																
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
09:25 (1 min)	A1/E1: T calls the groups and asks, "Are you ready?"	✓								✓							✓				✓	✓										
09:26 (3 min)	A2/E1: T wants the Ss to open their books and checks if they are on the right page.	✓							✓								✓				✓											
09:29 (1 min)	A3/E1: T says "listen and repeat the words" by snapping her fingers. (Ss did not get it and repeat it)	✓									✓						✓				✓				✓				✓			
09:30 (3 min)	A4/E1: Ss listen to the audio including toy words and follow from the book.						✓				✓						✓				✓		✓		✓		✓		✓			
09:33 (1 min)	A5/E1: Ss listen to the song: How many toys? and follow from the book.						✓				✓						✓				✓		✓		✓		✓		✓			

Observation 3: 03.11.2021

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS								
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language			Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type				Source				
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow									Broad	Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
09:22 (1 min)	A1/E1: T calls the groups and asks, "Are you ready?"	✓								✓							✓			✓	✓											
09:23 (1 min)	A2/E1: T wants the Ss to complete her sentence: "Today is...."	✓										✓			✓		✓			✓	✓											
09:24 (5 min)	A3/E1: T prepares the class for the lesson and turns on the smart board. -T gives a S star helper sticker and want him to write down the group names. -"take a deep breath" -"take out your books"	✓								✓							✓			✓				✓								
09:29 (1 min)	A8/E1: T gives the instructions about the activity. "Draw your family members."	✓							✓								✓			✓												

Observation 4: 10.11.2021

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS									
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source						
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made	
																	Text	Text															
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	
9:23 (4 min)	A1/E1: T prepares the classroom for the lesson and wants the Ss to take out their books. -T greets the students. -“Take a deep breath” - T gives a S star helper sticker.	✓								✓							✓			✓	✓												
9:27 (2 min)	A2/E1: T explains the activity: “How many toys?” “Pick up your crayons, count, draw, color and write the numbers and names of the toys.”	✓							✓								✓			✓					✓			✓	✓				
9:29 (14 min)	A2/E2: Ss start counting, drawing, coloring and writing.						✓				✓						✓					✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓				

Observation 5: 25.11.2021

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT									CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY						MATERIALS					
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language					Other topics			Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type				Source	
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad	Minimal	Extended									Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
																			Text													
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
15:22 (3 min)	A1/E1: T prepares the Ss for the lesson. -Take a deep breath. -Take up your books. -Are you ready for well done?	✓								✓							✓			✓	✓			✓								
15:25 (3 min)	A2/E1: T explains the miming game to the Ss and chooses a S to come to the board.	✓							✓								✓			✓												
15:28 (1 min)	A2/E3: Ss listen to the jobs from the recording and repeat. They also look at the pictures with the words under them on the board.			✓							✓						✓			✓	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓			
15:29 (23 min)	A2/E4: There are pictures on the board, Ss come and choose one of the jobs and mime it. The others try to guess what it is. Ss raise their hands and the S miming the jobs chooses a friend to say his/her guess.		✓								✓						✓			✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓	✓				
30 min		6	23	1					3	3	24						30			7	1			26	23		1	24	24			

Observation 6: 02.12.2021

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS								
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source					
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
																	Text	Source														
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
15:20 (3 min)	A1/E1: T wants the Ss to tidy up and get ready for the lesson.	✓								✓							✓			✓												
15:23 (2 min)	A2/E1: T wants the Ss to open their books and look at the pictures and read the words next to them individually, as a preparation before the test while showing the pages that they should study on the board, as well.	✓							✓								✓			✓					✓			✓	✓			
15:25 (6 min)	A2/E2: Ss read the words individually while looking at the pictures.						✓				✓						✓					✓		✓			✓	✓				
15:31 (2 min)	A3/E1: T writes <i>Sınav Kuralları</i> on the board, a S reads the rules in Turkish, and T explains them in English.	✓								✓							✓			✓		✓										
15:33 (2 min)	A3/E2: T wants the Ss to put their books under their desks while a S distributes the exam sheets.	✓								✓							✓			✓												

Observation 7: 14.12.2021

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS								
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source					
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
																	Text	Text														
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
10:45 (3 min)	A1/E1: T wants the Ss to be quiet and get ready for the lesson.	✓								✓							✓			✓												
10:48 (2 min)	A2/E1: T shows the numbers from a poster and Ss say what number they are.	✓									✓						✓			✓								✓	✓			
10:50 (4 min)	A3/E1: T explains the <i>buzz game</i> to the Ss.	✓							✓								✓			✓												
10:54 (7 min)	A3/E2: Ss start playing the game. One by one, they count till ten. T asks and Ss continue counting. For the even numbers, they say buzz. If they cannot say the correct number (or buzz), they go to the board. 2 Ss won the game.	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓											

<p>-T wants the Ss to cut the pictures together with the words under them and write their names at the back of each piece.</p> <p>- T opens a sheet on the board on which there are written the names of the groups and students under each group. T writes -10 next to Marmara Group because of their misbehaviors.</p> <p>- T writes on the board what the students should do in Turkish and explains it in English.</p> <p>- T writes on the board in Turkish and explains that Ss should turn over the pieces when the T says the name of the rooms.</p> <p>- T explains that the Ss should turn over each card (the rooms) when she says.</p> <p>- T writes on the board in Turkish and explains in English that the Ss should turn the cards when T says.</p> <p>& A student reads what is written on the board.</p>																															
--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

15:48 (4 min)	A2/E12: T says the names of the rooms, Ss find and turn the cards over. & T writes the names of the rooms on the board. When the Ss turn each card over, they say bingo.	✓																																	
15:52 (1 min)	A2/E13: T wants the Ss to shuffle their cards and turn them back again to play one more time. But they do not have time for that.	✓						✓													✓														
30 min		30						19	7	4					30					30				27	21				21	21					

Observation 8: 24.12.2021

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS								
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type			Source				
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
																	Text															
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
12:42 (6 min)	A1/E1: T wants the Ss to tidy up and get ready for the lesson. -Are you ready groups? -Take out your books. -What page are we on? -“Looking eyes, listening ears.” -“Pick up your pencils”	✓								✓							✓			✓	✓											
12:48 (3 min)	A2/E1: T and Ss complete 3 sentences with the given words about a picture together. T reads & Ss answer, T gives feedback. T writes the answers on the board and Ss write them in their books, as well.	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓			
12:51 (2 min)	A2/E2: A visitor came and took the Ss temperature due to covid precautions.																															
12:53 (1 min)	A2/E2: Ss finish their writing.						✓				✓						✓						✓		✓			✓	✓			

Observation 9: 30.12.2021

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT									CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY						MATERIALS					
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics			Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source				
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad	Minimal									Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
																		Text	Text													
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
15:23 (4 min)	A1/E1: T greets the Ss with a <i>hello</i> video. & T and Ss say hello to each other.	✓										✓					✓			✓	✓				✓		✓	✓		✓		
15:27 (9 min)	A2/E1: T shows her bedroom and says that 'I'm in the bedroom.' & T asks individual Ss <i>Where are you now?</i> Ss answer. (<i>I'm in the living room / kitchen etc.</i>) T scaffolds when needed.	✓									✓				✓		✓			✓	✓											
15:36 (5 min)	A2/E2: Ss look at the ppt on the screen. T asks individual Ss some Qs such as <i>'What are these? / Which room is it? / Where are the books?'</i> & Ss answer. (<i>Sofa, bedroom, on the desk...</i>)	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓				
15:41 (4 min)	A3/E1: T says that it is play time. She shares the instruction on the board, which is in Turkish, and a student reads it. &	✓							✓								✓			✓		✓	(L1)		✓							

Observation 10: 04.01.2021

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS								
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source					
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
13:00 (3 min)	A1/E1: T prepares the classroom for the lesson and wants them to get ready for the lesson. -T greets the students. -Are you ready black diamonds? -T chooses the star student of the day.	✓								✓							✓				✓	✓										
13:03 (3 min)	A2/E1: T does some hand gestures and say some words and sentences melodically such as "in/on/under/She is sleeping in the bedroom etc." Ss repeat after her.			✓							✓						✓				✓	✓										
13:06 (4 min)	A2/E2: T explains the bingo game and the rules about the game.	✓							✓								✓				✓											
13:10 (2 min)	A2/E3: T distributes the worksheets and wants the Ss to cut the pictures together.	✓							✓								✓				✓											

Observation 11: 14.12.2021

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT									CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY						MATERIALS							
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language					Other topics			Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source					
		T- S/C	S- S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad	Minimal	Extended									Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made		
		3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33		
13:02 (2 min)	A1/E1: T makes the Ss get ready for the lesson. -Are you ready groups? (Ss say yes) -Who is helper student today?	✓								✓						✓			✓	✓														
13:04 (1 min)	A2/E1: T says some sentences and Ss repeat after her. "I love pets/rabbits/chinchilla."			✓							✓					✓			✓	✓														
13:05 (2 min)	A2/E2: T wants the Ss to be ready for the surprise video. (A student tells something personal to the teacher-L1 use)	✓									✓					✓			✓	✓	L1 use													
13:07 (1 min)	A3/E1: T wants the Ss to listen to the different pets' names and sounds and explains the instruction.	✓								✓						✓			✓															
13:08 (7 min)	A3/E2: Ss watch the video. & T gives to and takes from the groups 10 points according to their behaviors while watching.	✓					✓				✓	✓				✓			✓							✓	✓	✓						
13:15 (2 min)	A3/E3: T opens a video of her bird and talks about it with the Ss. (<i>Why is it akkus? Because it's... Ss say white.</i>)	✓													✓	✓			✓	✓							✓	✓						
13:17 (6 min)	A4/E1: Individual Ss tell some anecdotes they had with pets in		✓													✓			✓	✓														

13:08 (7 min)	A3/E2: Ss watch the video. & T gives to and takes from the groups 10 points according to their behaviors while watching.	✓					✓			✓	✓								✓	✓	✓			
13:15 (2 min)	A3/E3: T opens a video of her bird and talks about it with the Ss. (<i>Why is it akkuş? Because it's... Ss say white.</i>)	✓								✓	✓									✓	✓			
13:17 (6 min)	A4/E1: Individual Ss tell some anecdotes they had with pets in the past in Turkish. T and Ss listen to them. T provides backchannels such as <i>yes, so nice</i> while listening.		✓							✓	✓									✓	✓			
13:23 (1 min)	A4/E2: T opens a ppt show and asks who is ready for the surprise activity.	✓									✓										✓	✓		
13:24 (2 min)	A5/E1: T shows some pictures and wants the Ss to find the hidden animal in the picture. T asks, "What is	✓									✓										✓	✓		

Observation 12: 18.01.2022

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT									CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY						MATERIALS						
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language					Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type				Source			
		T- S/C	S- S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad	Minimal									Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made	
																		Text															
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	
13:01 (4 min)	A1/E1: - T greets the Ss. -T calls the groups and asks, "Are you ready?" Ss say "yes". -T chooses the star helper of the day.	✓								✓							✓			✓	✓												
13:05 (3 min)	A2/E1: T says some sentences (Where is X student? S/he is in the kitchen/bedroom /under the desk etc.) rhythmically and Ss repeat after her. & T and Ss clap their hands.			✓							✓						✓			✓	✓				✓								
13:08 (3 min)	A3/E1: T says that if the Ss are ready they will continue with miming game. T makes the Ss ready for the game. (Take a	✓								✓							✓			✓				✓									

Appendix 7. Public School Observation Schemes

Observation 1: 12.10.21

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT									CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS						
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics			Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source				
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad	Minimal									Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
																		Text	Text													
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
10:45 (8 min)	A1/E1: Introduction + Revision of Turkish and English vowels + a/an revision in Turkish.	✓							✓		✓						✓			✓	✓											
10:53 (5 min)	A1/E2: This is / That is revision with Turkish explanation on theboard. T asks Qs, Ss answer together.	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓											
10:58 (3 min)	A2/E1: Ss match the sentences with the pictures. T asks Ss answer.	✓					✓				✓						✓			✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓			
11:01 (3 mins)	A2/E2: Ss write and color the letters of 'lemon'.	✓					✓				✓						✓			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓			

11:04 (5 mins)	A2/E3: Ss fill in the blanks: Ss write the words for each picture. They also write them on the board one by one. (T chooses the Ss to write).	✓			✓			✓			✓		✓		✓	✓										
11:09 (6 mins)	A2/E4: Fill in the blanks with <i>this</i> or <i>that</i> . T asks Ss answer.	✓			✓			✓			✓		✓		✓	✓										
11:15 (3 mins)	A3/E1: T reads sentences and Ss repeat.		✓				✓			✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓									
11:18 (2 mins)	A4/E1: HW control of a multiple-choice test. T asks, "What is this?"; Ss answer together.	✓					✓			✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓									
35 min		29	3		3			35					35		21	3		14		22			14	22		

Observation 2: 19.10.21

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS								
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics			Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type				Source		
		T- S/C	S- S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad	Minimal									Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
																		Text	Text	Text	Text	Text	Text									
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
10:45 (3 min)	A1/E1: Ss listen to the dialogue twice about getting to know each other and follow the pictures.						✓					✓		✓	✓		✓			✓							✓	✓	✓			
10:48 (1 min)	A1/E3: T writes the sentences on the board and says the names of the people in the book.	✓										✓		✓			✓			✓		✓			✓		✓	✓				
10:49 (3 min)	A1/E4: T asks ind. Ss their names and they answer. (T helps the Ss). T explains how to introduce oneself by using the structures "I am, I'm, My name is ..."	✓										✓		✓			✓			✓	✓											
10:52 (2 min)	A2/E1: Ss listen and write the names or match the names with the pictures.						✓					✓					✓			✓			✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				
10:54 (1 min)	A2/ E1: Ss check the answers: T asks, "Which one is Lily?" Ss answer together.	✓										✓					✓			✓	✓						✓	✓				
10:55 (2 min)	A2/E2: Ss listen and match the names with the pictures again.						✓					✓					✓			✓			✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				
10:57 (1 min)	A2: E2: They check the answers again.	✓										✓					✓			✓			✓	✓			✓					

Observation 3: 26.10.21

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY						MATERIALS							
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language					Other topics			Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source			
		T- S/C	S- S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad	Minimal	Extended									Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
10:42 (3 min)	A1/E1: T wants the Ss to clean the board and looks at the computer.	✓							✓	✓							✓			✓												
10:45 (3 min)	A2/E1: Ss listen to a song about greetings.						✓					✓					✓			✓							✓		✓			
10:48 (2 min)	A2/E2: Ss watch a video about greetings.						✓					✓					✓			✓		✓					✓	✓	✓			
10:50 (3 min)	A2/E3: Ss watch the same video twice.						✓					✓					✓			✓		✓					✓	✓	✓			
10:53 (2 min)	A2/E5: Ss watch a new video about introducing oneself.						✓					✓					✓			✓		✓					✓	✓	✓			
10:55 (4 min)	A3/E1: 8 Ss come to the board and introduce themselves.		✓									✓					✓			✓	✓											
10:59 (1 min)	A4/E1: T explains the phrases in Turkish. (Good morning neydi, günaydın.)	✓										✓	✓				✓			✓	✓											
11:00 (2 min)	A5/E1: Ss watch a video of a song about greetings (good morning, good afternoon etc.)						✓					✓					✓			✓		✓					✓	✓	✓			
11:02 (3 min)	A5/E2: Ss watch another video of a song about introducing oneself.						✓					✓					✓			✓		✓					✓	✓	✓			
11:05 (2 min)	A5/E3: Ss watch another video about greetings; T and some Ss sing.			✓			✓					✓					✓			✓	✓	✓					✓	✓	✓			

Observation 4: 09.11.21

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS							
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source				
		T- S/C	S- S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA
		3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
10:44 (2 min)	A1/E1: T wants the Ss to open their books.	✓							✓							✓			✓												
10:46 (2 min)	A2/E1: T wants the Ss to do the actions she says: "stand up, sit down, turn left, turn right" etc.			✓							✓					✓			✓				✓								
10:48 (1 min)	A3/E1: T shows some phrases by doing: "open your books, close your books, open the door, shut the door" etc.	✓									✓					✓			✓												
10:49 (1 min)	A3/E2: T writes some phrases on the board and draw them. "Turn right, turn left, turn around". Ss look and read them.	✓									✓					✓			✓		✓										
10:50 (2 min)	A3/E3: T shows some phrases by doing. -stand up, sit down, open/close your book, open/close the window, open/close the door.	✓									✓					✓			✓												
10:52 (5 min)	A4/E1: T gives some instructions and ind. Ss do what the T says in front of the board.	✓									✓					✓			✓				✓								

Observation 5: 23.11.21

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT								CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS							
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language					Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source				
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad	Minimal									Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
		3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
10:46 (2 min)	A1/E1: T wants the Ss to open their books.	✓						✓								✓			✓													
10:48 (3 min)	A1/E2: T and Ss match the phrases (<i>sit down, stand up, close your book, open the book</i>) with the pictures on pg. 41 together. T: <i>What is number 1?</i> Ss answer and say the letters. T writes the answers on the board. Ss write the letters in their books.	✓								✓						✓			✓	✓	✓		✓	✓			✓	✓				
10:51 (2 min)	A2/E1: T writes the letters that the Ss know on the board. T reads them and Ss repeat after her.			✓							✓					✓			✓	✓	✓											
10:53 (3 min)	A3/E1: T calls ind. Ss to the front and wants them to do some actions (<i>sit down, stand up, turn right...</i>)	✓									✓					✓			✓				✓									
10:56 (5 min)	A4/E1: T and Ss complete the sentences with the given words by looking at the	✓									✓					✓			✓	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓				

Observation 6: 19.10.21

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS								
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source					
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
																	Text	Text														
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
10:44 (7 min)	A1/E1: T deals with a technical issue with the projector.																															
10:51 (3 min)	A2/E1: Ss watch a video, listen, and repeat the numbers.			✓							✓						✓				✓	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓		
10:54 (1 min)	A2/E2: Ss watch the second part of the video and repeat the school objects.			✓							✓						✓				✓	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓		
10:55 (1 min)	A2/E3: Ss watch a video about <i>how many</i> and <i>numbers</i> with a grammatical expression at the end of it (we put an <i>-s</i> at the end of the words to make the words plural.)						✓				✓						✓					✓			✓		✓	✓	✓			
10:56 (2 min)	A2/E4: Ss listen to a song about counting till ten and backward, and they repeat while listening.			✓							✓						✓				✓	✓				✓		✓	✓	✓		
10:58 (3 min)	A2/E5: Ss listen to the song "How many fingers?", sing along, clap their hands, and stomp their feet.			✓							✓						✓				✓	✓		✓			✓	✓	✓			
11:01 (2 min)	A2/E6: Ss listen to a song about school objects and sing along while listening.			✓							✓						✓				✓	✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓		
11:03 (4 min)	A2/E7: Ss listen to the song "How many monkeys?" twice and they sing along while listening.			✓							✓						✓				✓	✓				✓		✓	✓	✓		
11:07 (2 min)	A2/E9: Ss watch another video entitled <i>how old are you?</i>						✓				✓						✓				✓					✓		✓	✓	✓		

11:09 (1 min)	A3/E1: Ss listen and repeat the numbers while looking at the written versions in their books.			✓				✓				✓		✓	✓					✓	✓	✓						
11:10 (1 min)	A3/E2: T reads and Ss repeat the numbers.			✓				✓				✓		✓	✓							✓	✓					
11:11 (2 min)	A3/E3: T shows some numbers with her fingers and wants the students to say what number it is. Ss answer. T gives feedback.	✓						✓				✓		✓	✓													
11:13 (1 min)	A3/E4: Ss listen to the song about numbers in the book and sing along.			✓				✓				✓		✓	✓							✓						
11:14 (1 min)	A3/E5: T wants the Ss to listen, count and tick the numbers in their books.	✓					✓					✓		✓														
11:15 (2 min)	A3/E6: T wants the Ss to write the numbers instead of ticking and Ss listen to the beats and write the numbers.					✓				✓			✓		✓			✓	✓	✓		✓						
11:17 (2 min)	A3/E7: Ss do the same activity again. T asks <i>how many</i> , Ss answer. They write the number of the beats they hear next to the numbers.	✓						✓				✓		✓	✓			✓	✓	✓		✓						
11:19 (1 min)	A4/E1: Ss listen to a dialogue and follow the pictures in their books, "How old are you, Lily?"					✓			✓		✓		✓				✓				✓	✓	✓					
29 min		5	18			6	1		28				29		27	19				2	12					25	21	26

Observation 7: 14.12.21

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT									CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS						
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language					Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source				
		T-S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad	Minimal									Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
10:45 (3 min)	A1/E1: T wants the Ss to be quiet and get ready for the lesson.	✓								✓							✓			✓												
10:48 (2 min)	A2/E1: T shows the numbers from a poster and Ss say what number they are.	✓									✓						✓			✓							✓	✓				
10:50 (4 min)	A3/E1: T explains the <i>buzz game</i> to the Ss.	✓							✓								✓			✓												
10:54 (7 min)	A3/E2: Ss start playing the game. One by one, they count till ten. T asks and Ss continue counting. For the even numbers, they say buzz. If they cannot say the correct number (or buzz), they go to the board. 2 Ss won the game.	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓											

11:01 (5 min)	A3/E3: T wants the Ss open their books and explains what they should do on the 3 pages of the book.	✓						✓									✓			✓						✓			✓	✓						
11:06 (14 min)	A3/E4: Ss start doing the activities in their books while the T checks the Ss' homework one by one. (Ss write the missing words, count & circle the correct number, count the fingers & write, match the words with the pictures, find the written versions of numbers in the puzzle and circle, read & count & draw – such as drawing 3 tables)	✓						✓									✓			✓	✓	✓	✓							✓	✓					
35 min		35						9	3	23							35			21	7				14	19				21	21					

Observation 8: 19.10.21

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS								
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source					
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
																	Text	Text														
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
10:46 (2 min)	A1/E1: T shows the Ss <i>number mobile</i> and wants 2 Ss to clean the board.	✓							✓								✓			✓												
10:48 (3 min)	A2/E1: T shows flashcards with words about classroom objects and asks, "What is it". Ss shout out their answers. T gives feedback.	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓	✓			✓			✓	✓			
10:51 (1 min)	A3/E1: T shows a poster with the pictures and the words for 10 classroom objects. T reads and Ss repeat after her.			✓							✓						✓			✓	✓	✓			✓			✓	✓			
10:52 (1 min)	A3/E2: T asks, "Is this a book?" Ss answer as Yes/No. T asks what is it? Ss answer.	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓				✓			✓	✓			
10:53 (2 min)	A4/E1: T shows a poster and asks individual Ss "How old are you?", Ss answer. T gives feedback by showing two different versions (I'm eight/ I'm eight years old.)	✓									✓	✓					✓			✓	✓				✓			✓	✓			
10:55 (2 min)	A4/E2: Individual Ss ask "How old are you?" to their friends. The student answering the question, asks the same question to another friend.		✓								✓	✓					✓			✓	✓											

10:57 (2 min)	A4/E3: T walks around the classroom with the poster and asks individual Ss "How old are you?", and they answer.	✓								✓	✓							✓			✓	✓										
10:59 (1 min)	A5/E1: T shows the book and wants the Ss to open page 56.	✓						✓										✓						✓								
11:00 (2 min)	A5/E2: T says 6/7/9/2 etc. eggs and Ss raise their fingers showing the number the teacher has just said.	✓						✓										✓														
11:02 (1 min)	A5/E3: T shows her fingers and asks, "How many fingers?", Ss answer.	✓						✓										✓		✓	✓											
11:03 (6 min)	A6/E1: T asks individual Ss about the objects in the pictures "What is 1?", they answer, and write the answer on the board. & Ss write the answers in their books. (There are pictures in the book and the letters are in a mixed order, they write the words)	✓						✓										✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓						
11:09 (1 min)	A6/E2: T reads the words and Ss repeat after her.			✓				✓										✓		✓	✓			✓	✓							
11:10 (1 min)	A7/E1: T explains that we put an -s at the end of the words while making them plural. (The rule is written in the book, too.)	✓						✓										✓		✓				✓	✓							
11:11 (9 min)	A7/E2: T asks individual Ss "How many notebooks/doors...?" etc. They answer according to the pictures and write the answers on the board. & Other Ss also write the answers in their books.	✓						✓										✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓						
34 min		30	2	2				3										34		17	13		15	2	25		25	27				

Observation 9: 28.12.21

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS							
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source				
		T-S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA
		3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
10:43 (4 min)	A1/E1: T takes the attendance. Ss say <i>here/absent</i> . T asks how many Ss are absent and Ss say 9.	✓								✓						✓				✓	✓										
10:47 (4 min)	A2/E1: T turns the projector on, but the computer is so slow.																														
10:51 (1 min)	A2/E2: T wants the Ss to turn off the lights and be quiet for the videos of the new unit.	✓								✓						✓				✓											
10:52 (4 min)	A2/E3: Ss watch a video about colors and say the translations while watching. & Ss watch other videos including colors & classroom objects & how many & I like...			✓				✓								✓				✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓			
10:56 (3 min)	A2/E4: Ss watch a video about colors and repeat after it. (T shows the flashcards because the colors are not seen well enough on the screen)			✓												✓				✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓			
10:59 (5 min)	A2/E5: Ss watch a video song about colors and sing along it. (T shows the flashcards because the colors are not seen well enough on the screen)			✓												✓				✓	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓			
11:04 (3 min)	A2/E6: Ss watch a video including 'My favorite color is...'						✓									✓				✓				✓		✓	✓	✓			

Observation 10: 04.01.22

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY						MATERIALS							
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source					
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
10:44 (3 min)	A1/E1: T takes the attendance. Ss say <i>here/absent</i> .	✓								✓							✓			✓	✓											
10:47 (1 min)	A2/E1: T and Ss sing the song called "twinkle twinkle little star"			✓											✓		✓			✓	✓											
10:48 (3 min)	A2/E2: 3 Ss come to the board one by one and sing the same song with the help of the teacher while the others are listening.		✓												✓		✓			✓	✓											
10:51 (2 min)	A3/E1: T shows different objects in the classroom and asks, "What color is it?" Ss answer altogether.	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓											
10:53 (3 min)	A3/E1: T asks individual Ss by showing some objects, "What color is it?" / "Is it red?" and wants the Ss to answer "Yes, it is." / "No, it isn't." (T scaffolds when needed.)	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓											
10:56 (3 min)	A4/E1: Ss open page 69. T says the colors of the	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓	✓			✓			✓	✓			

Observation 11: 11.01.22

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY						MATERIALS							
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language			Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type		Source						
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow									Broad	Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made
																Text	Text															
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33
10:46 (1 min)	A1/E1: T wants the Ss to take out their English course books.	✓							✓								✓			✓												
10:47 (2 min)	A2/E1: T deals with the problem related to the sound system.																															
10:49 (1 min)	A3/E1: Ss listen to the audio of color words in the book twice and repeat after it.			✓							✓						✓			✓	✓				✓		✓	✓	✓			
10:50 (2 min)	A3/E2: T shows different objects in the classroom and asks "What color is it? / Is it blue?" etc. Ss answer together.	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓											
10:52 (1 min)	A4/E1: T tells the Ss to look at the pictures of colors and listen and number.	✓							✓								✓			✓								✓	✓			
10:53 (3 min)	A4/E2: Ss listen to the audio twice and number the colors. (There are colors and boxes next to them in the book)						✓				✓						✓			✓			✓				✓	✓	✓			
10:56 (1 min)	A4/E3: T checks the answers. She asks, Ss raise their hands. T chooses the Ss to answer and gives feedback.	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓							✓	✓			
10:57 (1 min)	A5/E1: T tells that they are going to listen to a song. (She explains the instruction)	✓							✓								✓			✓												
10:58 (2 min)	A5/E2: Ss listen to the song about colors in the book twice. (Red is for you, blue is for me...)						✓				✓						✓			✓							✓	✓	✓			
11:00 (8 min)	A6/E1: T asks the colors of missing balloons in the exercise. Ss raise their	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓		✓					✓	✓			

Observation 12: 18.01.22

TIME	ACTIVITIES & EPISODES	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION							CONTENT							CONTENT CONTROL			STUDENT MODALITY					MATERIALS									
		Class			Group		Indiv.		Manag.		Language				Other topics		Teacher/text	Teacher/text/student	Student	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing	Other	Type			Source					
		T- S/C	S-S/C	Choral	Same task	Different tasks	Same task	Different tasks	Procedure	Discipline	Form	Function	Discourse	Socioling.	Narrow	Broad									Minimal	Extended	Audio	Visual	L2-NNS	L2-NS	L2-NSA	Student made	
																	Text																
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	
10:45 (3 min)	A1/E1: T takes the attendance. Ss say <i>here/absent</i> .	✓								✓							✓			✓	✓												
10:48 (2 min)	A2/E1: T wants the Ss to open their books on page 69 and look at the puzzle they have already completed before.	✓							✓								✓			✓								✓	✓				
10:50 (4 min)	A2/E2: 6 Ss come to the board one by one and write the colors in the puzzle. & Other Ss check their puzzle.	✓									✓						✓					✓	✓		✓			✓	✓				
10:54 (6 min)	A3/E1: 8 Ss come to the board and classify the words into groups (school objects and colors). & Other Ss check their answers.	✓									✓						✓					✓	✓		✓			✓	✓				
11:00 (4 min)	A3/E2: T checks Ss' homework by walking around the classroom.	✓								✓							✓			✓		✓	✓		✓			✓	✓				
11:04 (1 min)	A6/E1: T asks, "What is yellow/purple?" etc. Ss answer in Turkish.	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓												
11:05 (1 min)	A7/E1: T asks the colors of the objects in the next activity. Individual Ss answer by looking	✓									✓						✓			✓	✓							✓	✓				

ÖZGEÇMİŞ

KİŞİSEL BİLGİLER

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EĞİTİM

Derece Yılı	Kurum	Mezuniyet
Lisans	Boğaziçi Üniversitesi, Eğitim Fakültesi, Yabancı Diller Eğitimi Bölümü	2017
Yüksek Lisans	İstanbul Medeniyet Üniversitesi, Lisansüstü Eğitim Enstitüsü, Yabancı Diller Eğitimi Ana Bilim Dalı	Devam ediyor

İŞ TECRÜBESİ

Tarih	Kurum	Görev
2021-2022 Öğretmeni	Asfa Eğitim Kurumları	İngilizce

YABANCI DİLLER

İngilizce	İleri Seviye
Fransızca	Orta Seviye